

EDEN ISS

D4.3 - Food Quality, Safety and Processing Manual

prepared for

WP 4.3 – Food Quality, Safety and Processing Experiments

Version: 1.0

Published: 2018-04-23

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Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2017-06-28	See author list	Initial release.
0.2	2017-09-15	See author list	General updates.
0.3	2018-04-17	See author list	Draft - Review of D4.3 – Food Quality, Safety and Processing Manual.
1.0	2018-04-23	See author list	Final Release.

Executive summary – WP 4.3 Experiment Test Plan

Overview

This work package, which details the Experiment Test Plan, encompasses all areas of qualitative, quantitative and organoleptic analysis of all plant tissue samples produced during three stages of experimental operations for EDEN ISS. These stages include (a) Pre-Mission testing; (b) Mission Operations and (c) Post-Mission sample analysis and data processing.

The experiment test plan is structured so that the documentation from each stage can act as a standalone document for use by the relevant stage users and will include stage overview, objectives, timeline, standard operating procedures (SOPs) and instrument operating procedures (IOPs) for each method employed, expected outputs / datasets, relevant references and a list of the equipment used. Each stage is further broken down into the three core areas of this work package: (i) Food Quality; (ii) Food Safety and (iii) Storage.

Overall Objectives & Timeline

Table E-1 illustrates the key objectives of this work package including the participant involvement and expected delivery date of final outputs.

Table E-1: WP 4.3. Key Objectives, Participant Involvement and Timeline.

<i>Obj. No.</i>	<i>Objective Description</i>	<i>Participant</i>	<i>Output Date</i>	<i>Delivery</i>
4.3.OB.1	Definition of plant material analysis procedures for Food Quality	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3.OB.1.1	Definition of SOPs and IOPs for preliminary composition analysis (non-destructive monitoring)	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3.OB.1.2	Definition of SOPs and IOPs for confirmatory composition analysis (destructive analysis)	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3.OB.1.3	Definition of SOPs for Organoleptic analysis (Sensory perception of taste & texture of fresh produce)	LIT	M32	
4.3.OB.2	Definition of plant material analysis procedures for Food Safety	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3. OB.2.1	Definition of SOPs for microbial determination during growth period per crop	CNR	M32	
4.3. OB.2.2	Definition of SOPs for microbial determination post-harvest per crop	CNR	M32	
4.3. OB.2.3	Definition of SOPs and IOPs for anti-nutritional composition determination	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3.OB.3	Definition of plant material analysis procedures for Food Storage (Short and Long Term)	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3. OB.3.1	Definition of SOPs for plant tissue processing post-harvest prior to transport back to participant labs	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3. OB.3.2	Definition of SOPs for storage of plant tissue during transport back to participant labs	CNR / LIT	M32	
4.3. OB.3.3	Definition of SOPs for Organoleptic analysis (Sensory perception of taste & texture of stored produce)	LIT	M32	

Overall Expected Outputs

Table E-2 illustrates the expected final outputs and datasets of this work package including associated documentation.

Table E-2: WP 4.3. Final Outputs including Dataset Documentation.

<i>Output No.</i>	<i>Output Description</i>	<i>Participant</i>	<i>Output Dataset Type</i>
4.3.OP.1	Pre-Mission Test Plan Report	CNR / LIT	Report
4.3.OP.1.1	Preliminary Composition Analysis Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1.2	Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1.3	Organoleptic Analysis Protocols	LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1.4	Food Safety Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1.5	Storage Protocols (Analytical and Organoleptic Samples)	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1.6	Sample Handling Document	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.2	Analogue Mission Test Plan Report	CNR / LIT	Report
4.3.OP.2.1	Preliminary Quality Data Report	CNR / LIT	Dataset
4.3.OP.2.2	Organoleptic Crew Surveys	LIT	Dataset
4.3.OP.2.3	Return Sample Logs	CNR / LIT	Sample List
4.3.OP.3	Post-Mission Test Plan Report	CNR / LIT	Report
4.3.OP.3.1	Composition Analysis Data Report	CNR / LIT	Result Report
4.3.OP.3.2	Organoleptic Analysis Data Report	LIT	Result Report
4.3.OP.3.3	Food Safety Report	CNR / LIT	Result Report

This Deliverable Report provides an updated review and data sets for outputs 4.3.OP.1.1 to 4.3.OP.1.6 in Table E-2 above.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
ANTO	Antocyanidin	LYCO	Lycopene
ASCO	Ascorbic Acid	MIN	Mineral composition
ASH	Ash Content	MRS	de Man, Rogosa, Sharpe (Agar)
BLSS	Bioregenerative Life Support	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
BRIX	Soluble solids	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
CE	Concurrent Engineering	NKH	Non-Killing Harvest
CFU	Colony forming units	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
CHL	Chlorophyll	NO ₃	Nitrate ion content
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	NSC	Non-structural carbohydrate
DAD	Diode Array Detector	FRAP	Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (Antioxidant Assay)
DLR	German Aerospace Center	ORGA	Organic Acid
DM	Dry Matter	OXA	Oxalic Acid
DW	Dry Weight	QDA	Quality Driving Attribute
FD	Freeze Dry	S/C	Species and Cultivars
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	SANTHO	Antioxidant identification
FOS	Oligo-fructosides	SCARO	Carotenoid Identification (Lutein, Zeaxanthin, Violaxanthin, Neoxanthin)
FQS	Food Quality and Safety	SGLUC	Glucosinolate identification
FW	Fresh Weight	SH	Spread Harvest
FRUCS	Fructans	SHTnF	Spread harvest number at time 1 n=1 SHT1, SH at time 2 SHT2, SHTF for the final harvest.
HI	Harvest Index	SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography	SPE	Solid Phase Extraction
HT	Harvest Time	SPOLY	Polyphenols
IBAF	Institute of Agro- Environmental and Forest Biology	SPROT	Soluble Proteins
IOP	Instrument Operating Procedure	TBD	To Be Determined
ISA	Istituto di Scienze dell' Alimentazione	TCARO	Total carotenoids
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	TF	Total Flavonoids
ISS	International Space Station	TGLUC	Total Glucosinolate
KH	Killing Harvest	TPOLY	Total Polyphenols
LAI	Leaf Area Index	TPROT	Total Proteins
LC-MS	Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry	WP	Work package
LED	Light-emitting diode	WUR	Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek

1 WP 4.3.A. Pre-mission Experiment Test Plan

1.1 Overview

This work package which details the Experiment Test Plan encompasses all areas of qualitative, quantitative and organoleptic analysis of all plant tissue samples produced during the Pre-Mission (Antarctica) testing stage of experimental operations for EDEN ISS. The experiment test plan is structured into the three core areas of this work package: (i) Food Quality; (ii) Food Safety and (iii) Storage.

One of the aims of the EDEN ISS project is that crops will be grown in a fully controlled environment so that not only growth and productivity as a function of growth environmental parameters can be assessed but also the nutritional and organoleptic quality and safety. This is a crucial step forward with respect to plant food production in space because it could allow future space growers to optimise the growing environment to maximise the production of key dietary nutrients required; rather than growing only to maximise biomass.

It is generally accepted that nutritional quality will be one of the driving forces for fruit and vegetables acceptance by consumers. On selecting the species and defining the quality aspects to analyse in MTF produce we decided to be guided by the nutritional and nutraceutical quality attributes that are most likely to be relevant for each species, for acceptance by the NM-III crew, for future space based consumers and for general consumers. The last focus is important if research outputs of EDEN ISS are to be disseminated to general growers and consumers on earth.

We should be aware that while we defined a list of species and quality attributes to be measured on them in EDEN-ISS, based on the aforementioned parameters, the feasibility of our planned activity will strongly depend on specific circumstances and not solely defined during the project itself. The NM3 station has space for a laboratory, but no equipment in that space, so most if not all chemical analysis should be performed after the NM3 mission on samples that should be collected stored and transported back to home laboratories. The amount of produce produced by the FEG has been estimated by WUR during his preliminary activity (2017-05-17 EDEN ISS-Cultivation recipe FROM WUR –WUR). On our side, we have planned to have 100 g of fresh weight per sample, that means less than 10 g of dry material (likely 5 g minimum). Testing has been performed to ensure that this amount of material would be sufficient to perform the planned analysis.

Cold storage is efficient to stabilise samples with respect to most quality parameter but not all. During the home lab activity, we have tested if sampling and storage, where possible in EDEN-ISS, what would be a good method to preserve ascorbic acid content, its oxidation state and in general the antioxidant potential of the plant tissue samples.

Several analytical procedures have been tested on plant material produced either by WUR and IBAF. Samples have been harvested, stabilised and pre-treated on both laboratories and exchanged between WUR, IBAF and LIT. Analysis on exchanged samples have been performed.

In conclusion, the pre-mission home lab activity was crucial to revise the number of samples, amount of samples, type of quality parameters to be measured and in general the planned activities

1.2 Objectives & Timeline

Table 1-1 illustrates the key objectives of this stage of the work package including the participant involvement and expected delivery date of final stage outputs. The associated equipment used can be found in Appendix 1.6.1

Table 1-1: WP 4.3.A. Key Objectives, Participant Involvement and Timeline.

<i>Obj. No.</i>	<i>Objective (Milestone) Description</i>	<i>Participant</i>	<i>Output Delivery Date</i>
4.3.OB.1.A.	Definition of plant material analysis procedures for Food Quality	CNR / LIT	M32
4.3.OB.1.1.A.	Definition of SOPs and IOPs for preliminary composition analysis (non-destructive monitoring)	CNR / LIT	M32
4.3.OB.1.2.A.	Definition of SOPs and IOPs for confirmatory composition analysis (destructive analysis)	CNR / LIT	M32
4.3.OB.1.3.A.	Definition of SOPs for Organoleptic analysis (Sensory perception of taste & texture of fresh produce)	LIT	M32

Growing conditions expected in the MTF are unusual, hence growth and productivity can only be estimated at this stage, as are the characteristics of produce that will be obtained in the FEG and ISPR. In order to properly verify estimates of plant performances, activities in home laboratories will be conducted in preparation for the mission. IBAF, CNR and LIT (as well as WUR) have their own plant growth facilities with capacity to control growth conditions.

Each of the IBAF-CNR chambers (Sanyo SGC, 2 twin chambers +1 spare) is equipped with:

- 8 x Osram, Power Star HQI-TS—250W/NDL, in addition to 8 x 60W tungsten lamps. Temperature control spans between +7°C and +40°C with all lights on.
- CO₂ is measured with IRGA technology (± 1 ppm) and can normally be controlled with a precision of ± 10 ppm after injection from cylinders.
- RH can be nominally controlled between 40 and 90% depending on temperature setting with a precision of $\pm 5\%$.
- Vertical flux of air is 0.2 m s^{-1}

Light can be scaled up in the morning (with the tungsten lamp or using 4 HQI lamps) to avoid a photo-inhibitory shock to plants passing from zero to full light intensity in a few seconds. This could also be considered for the light bars to be used in the MTF. A 5-10 minutes linear ramp of light increment would allow photosystems and the biochemistry to “warm-up” in a coordinated way avoiding damages to the PSII photosystem that would cause long lasting decrease of the quantum yield.

Light intensity can be reduced by switching off a fixed fraction of the lamps or by using neutral net filters.

The CELLS Research Laboratory at LIT contains 4 growth chambers manufactured by EGC, Ohio, USA. Two M48 Walk in chambers with 16 m² internal area and two M12 Reach in chambers with 4m² internal area. All chambers provide chamber temperature uniformity within $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ of setpoint throughout the operating range of 4°C to 40°C. Lighting ranges from 500 μmoles (at 36" from lamps) with the standard fluorescent/ incandescent array up to full sunlight brilliance with HID fixtures. CO₂ is controlled by PPE

Systems controller, and humidity range is comparable to those in CNR. CELLS also have three LED micro arrays, two of which were manufactured by Heliospectra. Two growing tents can also be utilised for ambient room temperature growth tests. Figure 1.1 illustrates the CELLS chambers in use.

Figure 1.1: CELLS M12 & EGC M48 Growth Chambers

A crucial environmental parameter determining plant performances is light, both as quantity and quality. Although light intensity inside the IBAF growth chambers is far higher (close to $1 \text{ K } \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30cm from the light compartment) than that in the FEG end ISPR, its quality is different. For this reason during the CE study Heliospectra and IBAF started to evaluate the possibility to upgrade the IBAF chambers with Heliospectra lamps having light quality similar to the LED lamp bars that Heliospectra will produce for implementation in the FEG. After the CE meeting, Heliospectra simulated scenarios with two of their LED lamps (LX60) with two optics and two different crop distances from the lamps.

Figure 1.2: Sanyo SGC Chambers at IBAF CNR

After simulation Heliospectra suggested the use of two lamps with narrow optic and also defined the optimal position and spacing of the lamps with respect to light intensity and distribution inside the IBAF growth chambers Figure 1.2)

Figure 1.3: Modelling of lam position

Simulation – 2 lamps
Narrow optic

Two lamps with the narrow optic provide an even distribution at both 140cm and 70cm. The separation of the lamps could likely be increased a more to further improve uniformity.

Intensities over 700umol/m2/s at floor level and over 1400umol/m2/s at 70cm can be expected.

Heliospectra is producing an up-grade version of their SX60 lamp that will be provided to IBAF for implementation in the growth chambers. IBAF is working at versatile solution for the SX60 lamps implementation in the chambers to maximise experimental potential to confront ad contrast light environment effects on plant quality performances. LIT will shortly negotiate with Heliospectra to have this process implemented for all four CELLS chambers.

As in-house pre-Antarctica activities CNR and LIT will perform growth cabinet experiments on select- ed species and varieties, to test their response to growth conditions that will be used in the MTF in terms of productivity of biomass for sampling and quality. This will allow to test all procedure of samples harvesting, subsampling, stabilisation, storage end analysis. Particular care will be devoted to the procedure necessary for positive integration of activities performed at the two laboratories (IBAF and LIT). This would increase the efficiency of operation and the result outcome. Please refer to table 1.2 for the list of species tested and the testing methods used.

1.3 Standard Operating Procedures

In version 0.1 of the WP4.3 CDR document, we listed the planned Standard Operating Procedures, including the Preliminary Composition Analysis Protocols. This document reports the procedures used during the real activity in home laboratories, that are now confirmed (Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols). Some of the procedures used are not the same listed in the WP4.3 CDR version 0.1 document. These changes will be highlighted in the following. The SOP that have not been tested so far are still reported as planned.

Food fibres components have been measured on selected Rocket samples. Plant food fibres derive mainly from cell wall structural components (cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin pectin). In view of the emerging importance of these plant food components for the gut microbiome functionality, the inclusion of component fibre fraction on the QDA list will be evaluated.

Table 1-2: Quality Driving Attributes (QDAs) for selected species.

Species	Cultivar /type	QDA 1	QDA 2	QDA 3	Comments
<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.	TBD	NO₃	OXA	FOS	Nitrate levels are monitored for antinutritional (toxic levels) before each sensory evaluation is carried out. Fructans are reported for roots of <i>Lactuca</i> , we will verify with home lab activities of fructans and particularly FOS are present also in leaves
<i>Eruca sativa</i> Mill.	Cultivated	ASCO	TGLUC	FIBRE	Methods to quantify polymeric composition of rocket produce were tested. Original data are available. Glucosinolate method development is complete. Data will be reported in updated version of this report.
<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L.	TBD	TGLUC	ANTIOX	NSC	Glucosinolate method development is complete. Data will be reported in updated version of this report. Nitrate levels are monitored for antinutritional (toxic levels) before each sensory evaluation is carried out.
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i> L.	TBD	ASCO	NO ₃	SCAR O	During home-lab activity we should verify the extent of Ascorbic acid degradation during storage.
<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.	TBD	SPROT	BRIX	NO ₃	Nitrate levels are monitored for antinutritional (toxic levels) before each sensory evaluation is carried out. Sucrose range have been established.
<i>Brassica</i> spp.	Red mustard	ANTO	TGLUC	NO ₃	Antocyanin levels have been determined. Glucosinolate method development is complete. Data will be reported in updated version of this report. Nitrate levels are monitored for antinutritional (toxic levels) before each sensory evaluation is carried out.
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> L. (<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i> Mill.)	TBD	LYCO	DM	NSC	Lycopene levels, total carotenoid and total flavonoid baseline levels have been established. LCMS data will be reported in the next version of this report.
<i>Capsicum annuum</i> L.	TBD	SCARO	NSC	ASCO	During home-lab activity we should verify the extent of Ascorbic acid degradation during storage.

During the Mission samples will be collected for future analysis of quality relevant attributes. The related procedures have been summarised in previous documents and have been better defined and tested were relevant during the reported period of activity.

1.3.1 Sampling

Sampling

Figure 1.4: Sampling procedures steps

Labelling

Labelling all samples produced during the mission is important and a common labelling procedure should be defined, agreed and adopted. Some of the samples will be analysed by different partners during the post-mission activity, and each should have access to relevant info about each sample. Sample coding should be written on bags and tubes where samples will be stored. This labelling should be unequivocal but concise.

Our proposal is to label bags and tubes as follows:

dd/m/y-ACT –XX- SX

where

dd= day
m=month
y=year

ACT= we can define codes for different activities, for example Food quality=Q; food safety=S, microbial contamination of FEG= M (TBD).

XX= progressive number for the set of samples defined by the previous codes.

SX= code for sub sampling when relevant. E.g. S1, S2

Labelling should be written by a black marker pen (to be tested in advance) on two opposite position on

15/4/2018									
Experiment name or number, Harvest n° 3: lettuce (Description of the experiment – including growing conditions set points and other relevant observations)									
Activity :Q, food quality									
Samples from: 15/4/2018-Q-1 to 15/4/2018-Q-4									
Sample N	Plant Species	Material type	Day-Time of harvest	Treatment	Replicate	Operator	Fresh weight (g)	Bag tare (g)	Other relevant info: ex total harvest weight (g) or codes for position of FEG. ADD Column as necessary
1		Full harvest	10:30	50% Blue	I	PZ	97.2	3.45	
2		Full harvest	10:35	70% Blue	I	PZ	100.3	3.99	
3		Full harvest	10:40	50% Blue	II	PZ	99.8	4.05	
4		Full harvest	10:45	70% Blue	II	PZ	101.8	4.12	

the bag and on the tubes. In addition to labels on bags and tubes, a Laboratory Book should be compiled. All other relevant info about each set of samples, sample and sub samples can be defined and recorded. For example:

Sampling sub-sampling and replicates

Food quality

Sampling is dramatically important to determine significant analytical data acquisition. Different species and varieties will be cultivated in the FEG. WUR has recently defined the plant density and tray distribution for each specie/variety (SV) during the Mission. WUR has also provided quantitative data on plant productivity for each S/V tested. These data are of fundamental importance for planning the sampling procedures. We have defined for each S/V the number and size of samples to harvest during the mission, keeping in mind that we should minimise the size of each sample in order:

- a) to leave sufficient produce for the crew to eat
- b) to limit the volume/weight to bring back from Antarctica.

Table 1-3: List of species to be tested and related information.

Species	Cultivar /type	N° of harvest sampled	N° samples per harvest	Type of sample	Tissue (and total amount of samples to	stabilisation	Storage	Analysis type	Site of analysis
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					transport in g)				
<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.	TBD	3	4	Fresh material (FM)	Leaves (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	CHL.; TCARO; DM; TPROT.; SPROT NSC; ASH; FRUCS; FOS OXA ASCO FIBRE	CNR IBAF
								MIN	LIT
								NO ₃	NM-III
<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.	TBD	1	5	FM	Roots (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	TCARO; DM; TPROT.; SPROT NSC; ASH; FRUCS; FOS OXA ASCO	LIT
								NO ₃	NM-III
<i>Eruca sativa</i> Mill.	Cultivated	3	4	FM	Leaves (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	CHL.; TCARO; SCARO; ASCO; DM; TPROT.; SPROT NSC; ASH TPOLY FIBRE	CNR IBAF LIT
								TGLUC; SGLUC; FRAP; SANTHO MIN SPOLY	LIT CNR
								NO ₃	NM-III
<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L.	TBD"	3	4	FM	Tap root (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	TGLUC; SGLUC; FRAP; SANTHO	LIT
								PTRO	NM-III

								BRIX	
								NSC	IBAF
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i> L.	TBD	3	4	FM	Leaves (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	CHL.; TCARO; SCARO; ASCO; DM; TPROT.; SPROT NSC; OXA	LIT
								NO3	NM-III
Brassica spp.	Red mustard	3	4	FM	Leaves (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	CHL.; SCARO; DM; NSC; ASH; ANTO; ASCO	IBAF
								NO3	NM-III
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> L. (<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i> Mill.)	TBD	3	4	FM	Fruit (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	DM; NSC; ORGA; LYCO; FIBRE	IBAF
								PTRO BRIX	NM-III
								SANTHO	LIT
<i>Capsicum annuum</i> L.	TBD	3	4	FM	Fruit (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	CHL.; SCARO; DM; NSC; ASCO	IBAF
								PTRO BRIX	NM-III
<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.	TBD	3	4	FM	Fruit (100 g)	Freezing	-20°C	NSC ASH FIBRE	IBAF
								MIN	LIT
								PTRO BRIX	NM-III

duced too much because the sample should be representative of the produce that crew would eat. All lettuce harvests, for example, will contain leaves of different age, size and maturation state that would have a quite variable chemical composition, the sample should be a good average of all leaf type, and averaging should be maintained while producing sub samples for different analytical streams.

Table 04: Analysis type and related information.

Type of analysis	Type of sample	Unit	Extraction	Main equipment	Laboratory	Data handling	CODE
Dry matter percentage	Fresh material (FM)	%	No	Freeze-drier/ventilated oven	IBAF	IBAF	DM%
Nitrate ion content	FM	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	Crushing	Nitrate Cardy Meter	LIT / NM-III	NM-III/IBAF/LIT	NO ₃
Chlorophylls	FM	mg kg ⁻¹ FM	80% acetone /water	Wet chemistry lab, VIS-Spectrophotometer/ Plate reader	IBAF / LIT	IBAF/LIT	CHL
Total carotenoids	FM	µg . g FM ⁻¹	80% acetone /water	Wet chemistry lab, VIS-Spectrophotometer/ Plate reader	IBAF / LIT	IBAF/LIT	TCARO
Total proteins	FM	% or µg gFW ⁻¹	Buffer	Wet chemistry lab Plate reader/VIS-Spectrophotometer	IBAF	IBAF	TPROT
Carotenoid identification	FM	µg . g FM ⁻¹	Acetone	Wet Chemistry Lab. and HPLC UV/VIS detector	IBAF / LIT	IBAF/LIT	SCARO
Soluble proteins	FM	% or µg gFW ⁻¹	Buffer	Wet chemistry lab Plate reader/VIS-Spectrophotometer	IBAF	IBAF	SPROT
Ascorbic acid	FM	µg . g FM ⁻¹	Trichloroacetic acid	Wet Chemistry Lab. and HPLC UV/VIS detector	IBAF	IBAF	ASCO
Non-structural carbohydrate (Glucose fructose, sucrose and others)	DM	% or µg gDM ⁻¹	80% ethanol /water	Wet Chemistry Lab. Plate reader and Ion chromatography system	IBAF	IBAF	NSC
Ash content	DM	% of DM	No	Muffle furnace	IBAF/LIT	IBAF/LIT	ASH
Fructans	DM	% of DM	80°C Buffer	Wet Chemistry Lab. And Ion chromatography system	IBAF	IBAF	FRUCS
Oligo-Fructosides	DM	% of DM	80 °C Buffer	Wet Chemistry Lab. And Ion chromatography system	IBAF	IBAF	FOS
Mineral composition	DM	% of DM	No	Wet Chemistry Lab, AAS, XRF	LIT	LIT	MIN
Antocyanidin	DM	µg . gDM ⁻¹	Methanol	Wet Chemistry Lab. and HPLC UV/VIS detector	IBAF	IBAF/LIT	ANTO

Organic acid	DM	$\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	80% ethanol /water	Wet Chemistry Lab. Plate reader and Ion chromatography system	IBAF	IBAF	ORGA
Oxalic Acid	DM	$\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	Water	Plate reader Spectro star nano (BMG) and HPLC UV/VIS detector	IBAF	IBAF	OXA
Lycopene	FM	$\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gFM}^{-1}$	Acetone	Wet chemistry lab, VIS-Spectrophotometer/ Plate reader	IBAF	IBAF	LYCO
Total polyphenols	DM	mg gallic acid equivalent gDM^{-1}	Methanol	Wet chemistry lab UV/VIS-Spectrophotometer	IBAF	IBAF/LIT	TPOLY
Polyphenols	DM	$\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	80% Ethanol/water	Wet Chemistry Lab. LC w/ tandem UV-Vis-Mass Spec Detector	LIT	LIT	SPOLY
Carotenoid identification	FM	$\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gFM}^{-1}$	Acetone; SCFE	Wet Chemistry Lab. LC w/ tandem UV-Vis-Mass Spec Detector	LIT	LIT	SCARO
Total Glucosinolate	DM	% or $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	80% Ethanol/water	Wet chemistry lab Plate reader/VIS-Spectrophotometer	LIT	LIT	TGLUC
Glucosinolate identification	DM	% or $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	80% Ethanol/water	Wet Chemistry Lab. LC w/ tandem UV-Vis-Mass Spec Detector	LIT	LIT	SGLUC
Antioxidant Capacity	DM	Trolox equiv	60% Acidified Methanol/ Water	Wet chemistry lab Plate reader/VIS-Spectrophotometer	LIT	LIT	FRAP
Antioxidant identification	DM	% or $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gDM}^{-1}$	60% Acidified Methanol/ Water; SCFE	Wet Chemistry Lab. LC w/ tandem UV-Vis-Mass Spec Detector	LIT	LIT	SANTHO
Oils/Fats	FM	% or $\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{gFM}^{-1}$	SCFE	Wet Chemistry Lab. LC w/ tandem UV-Vis-Mass Spec Detector	LIT	LIT	FATS
Hardiness	Whole Fruit	Kgf	No	Penetrometer	LIT / NM-III	NM-III	PTRO
Soluble solids	Tissue juice	°Brix	Tissue juice squeezing	Refractometer	LIT / NM-III	NM-III	BRIX
Fibre composition,	FM or DM	%	Sequential extraction	Biomass laboratory, Ion Chromatography	IBAF	IBAF	FIBER

polymeric components			methods			
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We have performed a detailed analysis of quantity of sample necessary for the different type of analysis planned in the case of Rocket. We also tested analysis possible with small amount of lettuce and red mustard provided by WUR.

Figure 1.5: Sample and sub-samples mass partitioning and use

Different S/V will be seeded with different density and will produce different type and amount of edible leafy or fruit material. Sampling procedures should take into account these differences and should be adapted to each S/V in order to obtain representative samples and replicates. Samples will be obtained at the time of produce harvest for consume, hence the operator should proceed to sample collection in accordance with harvesting time and procedures. The minimum size of samples is:

100 g of fresh material

Hence harvest for consume at the time of sample collection should be large enough to allow the subtraction of sample material. Reasonably at least of 1 kg of produce should be available. Not all harvest for consume will involve sample collection, that will occur only on defined harvest, planned depending on produce flow and availability. If that is not possible sample, produce for quality and safety determination should be collected by dedicated simulated harvests.

A) **Lettuce type large size plant.** In the hypothesis that big lettuce plants will be harvested the 4 replicates should be obtained from 4 different plants (possibly from different trays). If a plant weights 200 g the sample should be obtained by vertically halving the plant.

B) **Lettuce type spread harvest.** In this case, one sample should be obtained by sub-sampling single lot of spread-harvested leaves. The harvest lots can be build taking into account the plant distribution and the seeding density. If

possible, a harvest lot shall be obtained from a single tray (4 trays harvested at one time). If the crop occupies less than 4 trays, samples should be taken with reference to the position in the tray. Possible variability in the growing conditions should be taken into account simulating an experimental design to test spatial variability **Better planning will be possible during the mission.**

- C) **Dense crop for small plant species.** If the crop that is harvested is cultivated in 4 trays, each sample replicate should be obtained by a different tray. Otherwise, replicates should be obtained with reference to position inside the tray. While selecting a row for sampling, the entire row or a fraction of the row can be selected, taking into account the variability of the plant material in different position on the tray. **Better planning will be possible during the mission.**

- D) **Fruit sampling: tomato, pepper and cucumber.** In the case of large fruit, 100 g of material should be obtained as described for the large salad plant. Fraction of fruit should represent a good average of the total fruit characteristics. This would be obtained by cutting the fruit taking into account fruit symmetry. In general, cutting vertically from the petiole downward should be the best way, but taking into account the capillary structure of tomato and pepper will be helpful. Maturity stage at harvest can affect quantity and quality of produce. Testing different stages of ripeness may be a viable experimental condition for the FEG. **Better planning will be possible during the mission.**

Replicates

Measurement of quality characteristic will be affected by variability due to errors and variability of the plant material. Measuring this variability is necessary, and it should start by harvesting replicates samples as indicated above and doubling analytical measurements where necessary. We tested variability on rocket, red mustard and lettuce grown at WUR and rocket samples grown at IBAF under different environmental conditions. Differences among two sets of samples (rocket and red mustard) obtained at WUR were evidenced, highlighting the necessity of sampling, for quality analysis, crops that are in a perfect state before harvest with no record of growing problems.

In Test performed at IBAF we have **used 4 replicated** samples and performed single measurements of each variable. Samples obtained at IBAF have shown relatively low variability (standard error generally lower than 10%) and many of the variables tested showed statistically significant differences among samples obtained under different light environment (photoperiod and light spectrum distribution). This

show that the protocols adopted are adequate to test quality characteristics of FEG produce and to test their variability in relation to S/V and the effect of the growing environment. Environmental variability in different positions on each tray has to be accurately tested during the test phase campaign in Bremen. **Better planning will be possible during the mission.**

Unit selection and recording

Quality data can be expressed on different bases: fresh weight, dry weight, leaf area, chlorophyll content, protein content. The most frequent is fresh weight. This is a good reference base for quality variables since it links directly to the produce used as food. However, fresh weight in plant tissues can change rapidly because of changing growing conditions. Tissues of the S/V selected for growth in the FEG, have 90% or more of their fresh weight as water. Leafy material can lose water quite rapidly due to transpiration. Cold storage of frozen plant tissues can dehydrate tissue under long term storage. Hence, it is crucial that the sample fresh weight is accurately measured soon after harvest, and after any subsampling. Measurements of sample water content % would ensure that all variables expressed on a fresh weight basis can also be expressed on a more stable basis as dry weight. Different methods can be used to measure the water content of a sample. **Freeze-drying will be the selected method for this project**, because it is the best method in terms of metabolite content stability. We will also measure chlorophyll and proteins on the samples, the two variables can also be used as the base to express the content of metabolites in the produce, without extra work. The two reference methods are particularly useful when metabolic aspects are related to photosynthesis and metabolism. Referring to leaf area is a common practice when working with photosynthesis and related metabolism. To refer to leaf area we would need to measure the leaf area of a representative sub-sample or to harvest a leaf disc of known area on which to measure fresh and dry weight, chlorophylls and protein. Samples of leafy produce will be composed of leaves of different age and composition; hence it would be impossible to harvest representative leaf discs and it is impossible to displace an area meter to the NMII station. Hence Leaf area would not be used as a reference parameter.

In Test performed at IBAF we recorded fresh weight and dry weight, data expressed on both bases were adequate to describe relevant quality parameters. Protein content is also used as a reference base. A rapid and universally used method is the Bradford assay. It is relatively simple, rapid and accurate for comparison of samples whose aminoacidic composition does not vary largely. The colorimetric response is tested against a standard protein, general bovine serum albumin, and its response is monoacid sensitive. Hence it is highly valuable for comparison among samples but for absolute protein determination. It would be useful to link the Bradford assay to measurements of the protein content via the Kjeldahl method, if sufficient sample amount will be necessary. In conclusion, fresh and dry weight basis will be used for all produce quality characteristic reference; other bases will be used if possible.

Stabilisation.

Plant metabolism is fast, particularly metabolism linked to photosynthesis and respiration. Plant tissues can survive for weeks or months after detachment from the mother plant, during that time they will acclimate to the new conditions, changing even dramatically their composition. When analysing the FEG (ad ISPR) plant tissue composition for quality, we aim to have a reasonable indication of the quality of the produce available for consume, at least of its quality soon after harvest, considering that post-harvest can

also dramatically affect produce quality at the moment of consume. Hence it is important that plant tissues samples are stabilised to quench metabolism and the status of the quality attributes that will be measured. Metabolism can be quenched in different ways. We analysed the feasibility and the efficiency of different stabilisation procedures, namely a) drying at 105 °C in ventilated oven; b) freeze drying, and c) the use of stabilising media.

The availability of equipment at the NMII Station is very limited, no drying oven is available, transfer of chemicals is also largely impaired by the Environmental protection legislation that makes, together with the lack of a functional chemical lab in situ, the use of stabilising solution not handy. The short cut conclusion is that the handiest stabilisation procedure for the Mission is freezing at low temperature of -20 °C or less. We should take into account that the produce, and the samples, will be harvested in the MTF and transferred to the NMIII station for further processing (and consume). Space and working facilities are limited in MTF, so the working hypothesis is that very limited processing of samples will take place in the MTF, while most of it will occur in the NMII Station. Mobility between the MTF and the NMII Station is not trivial, since an accurate planning of experimental samples harvest, and transfer from the MTF to the NMII Station is necessary. This should be done in the coming months in coordination with the other groups in relation to the working schedule of the person in charge (PIC). The working hypothesis could be that the PIC harvests the samples (and replicates) in the FEG in a separate pre-tagged bag, as close as possible to its journey back to the NMIII Station, where all other operations can be conducted as rapidly as possible prior to quenching samples at -20°C. **Better planning will be possible during the mission.**

Low temperature should be maintained until further stabilisation procedures possible in home laboratories. Planning is that one sub sample will be pulverised in liquid N₂ to a fine powder that can be further stored at a low temp (better at -80°C but -20°C would be sufficient) and a second sub sample will be dried by freeze drying for further storage at -20°C or ambient temperature when necessary.

CNR, LIT and WUR tested these procedures with common experimentation. Rocket freeze dried samples were produced at IBAF and transferred from IBAF to LIT for glucosinolates, ash and other quality attribute analysis and results will be available shortly. Freeze dried samples were produced by the WUR and transferred by courier at the IBAF laboratories for analysis. LIT optimised the Labcon freeze drying system to be located in NMIII for the duration of the experiment in Antarctica with follow on stability testing of freeze dried samples ongoing. Several quality attributes were determined on those samples with good results and limited variability.

Storage.

The mission will span over an entire year, with no possibility for sample return to home laboratories until the end of the mission. This means that samples will be analysed several months after harvest, at least. Laboratories involved in EDEN-ISS have a long-standing experience on quality analysis of plant samples and sample storage is a normal practice. Storage at low temperature is the preferred way when possible. Liquid N₂ storage (and sample freezing) would ensure the complete stability of the quality relevant attributes we have planned to analyse, but it will be possible only in home laboratories. In home laboratories, there is the possibility to store sample at -80°C that should be the preferred way ranking second after liquid N₂. Dry ice is also a good mode to store (and freeze) sample but it is normally utilised for short period due to the relatively rapid vaporisation of the dry ice. Storage at -80°C will be available at the NMIII during the mission in the system provided by LIT. Hence, we have decided that **samples will be**

frozen and stored at -80°C during the mission and possibly during the return transfer. Transfer should occur maintaining the samples frozen. Upon arrival at home laboratories the frozen samples will be treated as already stated to feed the different sample analytical streams. Storage at the lowest temperature possible should be the preferred way but freeze-dried material can be stored also at room temperature. Stability testing currently on the way in LIT will determine any analyte degradation over the longest possible storage period. Freeze dried samples will also be transferred between home laboratories.

Storage bags.

In laboratories, it is frequent to use handmade aluminium bags to store samples. Aluminium bags can be easily made, (5 minutes tutorial needed) the size can be decided depending on the sample amount, sample coding can be written directly on the bag, bags can be stored in liquid N₂ without damage, can be inserted directly in freeze drying devices and they can be calibrated in advance. LIT have also investigated the use of pre-purchased resealable aluminium bags and used them in the freeze-drying process of plant material.

The plan is to store large samples taken during the mission in aluminium bags. Smaller samples can be stored in Falcon type tubes with screw cap provided they should not be immersed in liquid N₂. Cold storage can cause dehydration of samples if the sample is not enclosed in gas tight containers. In fact, water can sublime from the sample to the coolest part of the freezer. Handmade **aluminium bags are not gas tight, so they should be enclosed in gas tight bags if used.** Ziplock bags for food storage in the fridge can be used for this purpose. **Dry samples have to be stored in gas tight tubes to avoid re-humidification upon storing.** After long-term storage, it is always possible that some dehydration or re-humidification takes place. Hence, when relevant re-checking of the water status of the samples might be necessary.

1.3.2 Optical Measurement of Plant Pigments

The measurement of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total carotenoids of plants.

Spectrophotometric measurement

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

1. About 100 mg of fresh frozen plant tissue powdered with liquid nitrogen, using a mortar and pestle or about 10 mg of dry plant material were extracted in 2 ml of 80% acetone and 20% (v/v) of a buffer 100mM Hepes and 10 mM MgCl₂, and stirred for 30 min at 25 °C.
2. The samples were centrifuged at 16,000 x g for 5 min and the supernatant was removed. The pellet could be treated again with the same extraction buffer until it is clear.
3. The optical density of the supernatant was read at 664, 647 and 470 nm, using a spectrophotometer UV/Vis to determine chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total carotenoids content.
4. Chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total carotenoids content were estimated using the equations below for acetone obtain the amount of pigments in µg/ml of plant extract (Žnidarčič *et al*, 2011).

$$\text{Equation 1} \quad \text{Chlorophyll a} = 12.21 \cdot A_{664} - 2.81 \cdot A_{647}$$

$$\text{Equation 2} \quad \text{Chlorophyll b} = 20.13 \cdot A_{647} - 5.03 \cdot A_{664}$$

$$\text{Equation 3} \quad \text{Total carotenoids} = (1000 \cdot A_{470} - 3.27 \cdot Ca - 104 \cdot CB) / 229$$

HPLC analysis of pigments

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

Measurement of carotenoids (α and β carotenes), lutein, rutin, xanthophylls (zeaxanthin, neoxanthin and violaxanthin), and chlorophylls a and b (Chl a and b) in plants.

1. Leaf discs (1.8 cm², equivalent to 45-50 mg of fw) were extracted with 2 mL 100% acetone, at 4 °C in dark conditions, using a glass-glass homogeniser.
2. The samples were centrifuged at 16,000 × g for 5 min at 4 °C, and the supernatants were collected.
3. The supernatants were filtrated through a nylon 0.2 µm PPII syringe disposable filters (Whatman) and 15 µl of the clear extract were used to determine the profile and concentration of pigments on the HPLC system UltiMate 3000 (Dionex ThermoScientific, Sunnyvale, CA, USA), with an UV-Vis detector.
4. Separations were performed using a C18(2) LUNA analytical column (5 µm, 250 x 4.6 mm), and a guard column (Phenomenex), maintained at 30 °C.
5. All separations were achieved isocratically, using a from 0 min to 4 min a mobile phase constituted of solution A: 1.75 % Methanol, 1.75% Dichloromethane, 1.75 % water and 94.75% Acetonitrile and from 4.1 min to 18 min a mobile phase constituted of solution B: 50 % Acetonitrile and 50% di Ethyl Acetate, with a final re-equilibration of 4 min with the solution A. The flow rate was 1ml/min for a run time of 22 min. UV detector wavelength was set at 440 nm and concentrations of different pigments were determined against a standard curve specific for each pigment considered (Žnidarčič *et al.*, 2011).
6. The assay results were analyzed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).
7. The HPLC UltiMate 3000 systems control, data acquisition, and processing were performed by the software Chromeleon Data System 6.8 (ThermoScientific™, Dionex™).

1.3.3 Sample Preparation for FRAP, TPOLY & TF Assays

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

All samples in batches were washed, inedible parts removed (peeled if necessary) and chopped into small cubes. The cubes were mixed and ca. 300 g representative sample was blended until a uniform paste was achieved (duration dependent on the nature of the sample). 100 g of the blended sample was accurately weighed into a 200 ml freeze drying container, shell frozen at -42°C and stored at -80°C. Samples were then freeze-dried, the duration of which was also dependent on the nature of the sample.

When fully dried, the samples were weighed, ground to a fine powder using a mortar and pestle and stored in sterile plastic tubes at -20°C in the dark. The yield of dried sample from 100 g of each fruit/vegetable ranged from 10 g to 20 g.

Samples were extracted using a solvent mixture of Methanol:DMSO (50:50 v/v). 250mg of dried food sample was accurately weighed into a sterile plastic tube. 5 ml of Methanol:DMSO (50:50 v/v) was added and the tube was immediately covered with foil to protect from light. The tubes were vortexed for 10 seconds to mix, sonicated for 15 mins and analysed within 24 hrs. Before each assay samples were centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 5 minutes to separate solvent extract from un-dissolved food particulates (adapted from Marinova *et al.*, 2005).

1.3.4 Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The quantification of antioxidant activity of food samples was performed according to Benzie and Strain (1996). The method is based on the measurement of the free radical scavenging activity of the extract that reduce the complex of Fe^{3+} -TPTZ (2,4,6-tripyridyl-2-triazine - Fe^{3+}) to Fe^{2+} -TPTZ. The reaction was monitored using a colorimetric assay, following the variation of the absorbance at 593 nm.

Plant materials were reduced to a fine powder, with liquid nitrogen, using a mortar and pestle and the fresh powder was preserved at -80°C until analyses. Alternatively, plant material was freeze dried and lyophilised powder was used.

1. About 100 mg of fresh frozen powder or 10 mg of dry matter was extracted with 2ml of methanol 100% at 25°C in an ultrasonic bath for 1h.
2. The leaf extract was separated by centrifugation at 16,000 × *g* for 5 min and the supernatant was collected and used on the colorimetric assay.
3. An aliquot of 0.03 ml of extract was added to 1.8 ml of FRAP reagent, mixed thoroughly and the mixture was left at 37°C for 30 min.
4. To prepare the FRAP reagent, a mixture of 0.3 mM sodium acetate (pH 3.6), 10 mM 2,4,6-tripyridyl-2-triazine (TPTZ) in 40 mM HCl and 20 mM ferric chloride in a volume ratio of 10:1:1 was made.
5. Antioxidant activity of the extracts was quantified measuring the absorbance of assay solution at 593 nm and it was expressed as micromole (μmol) per 100 g of fresh weight of equivalents of Trolox (TE) used in a standard curve at different concentrations.
6. The assay results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).

1.3.5 Folin-Ciocalteu Total Polyphenol Assay

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The total polyphenol content of the food samples was determined using a spectrophotometric method adapted from Singleton *et al.*, 1965. The assay is based on the reduction of the phosphomolybdic-phototungstic acid (the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent) to a blue coloured complex in the presence of polyphenols in alkali conditions. The colour produced is proportional to the concentration of poly-phenols in the sample measured against a gallic acid standard.

1. 100 µl of extract/standard/blank was added to 100 µl of 1:5 Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Preparation 6) and 100 µl of methanol in a 1 ml Eppendorf (all analysis was carried out in triplicate).
2. 700 µl of 7 % sodium carbonate (Preparation 5) was added to the mixture and the tubes were vortexed to mix.
3. Assay tubes were incubated for 20 minutes in the dark at room temperature.
4. After this time the tubes were centrifuged for 2 minutes at 3000 rpm to remove any precipitate.
5. 200 µl of sample/standard/blank were then transferred to a clear 96-well plate and the absorbance was read at 750 nm using a micro-plate reader.
6. Sample concentrations were expressed as mg/l Gallic acid equivalents (GAE).
7. The assay results were transferred to SPSS statistical software.

1.3.6 Total Anthocyanins Determination

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

1. The extraction protocol described by Usenik *et al.* (2008) was used.
2. About 100 mg of fresh frozen plant tissue powdered with liquid nitrogen, using a mortar and pestle or about 10 mg of dry plant material were extracted in 2mL of methanol acidified with 1% HCl for 1h at 65 °C.
3. The liquid extract was separated by centrifugation at $16,000 \times g$ for 5 min.
4. After centrifugation, the supernatant was separated and the total anthocyanins content was quantified spectrophotometrically measuring the absorbance at 560 nm.
5. The concentrations were expressed as cyaniding-3-glucoside equivalent values, following the protocol described by Giusti and Wrolstad (2005).
6. The assay results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).

1.3.7 Flavonoid Analysis

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols for both methods

Method for the Aluminium Chloride Total Flavonoid Assay

The total flavonoid content of the food samples was determined using the spectrophotometric method adapted from Zhishen *et al.*, 1999. This method utilises the reaction between flavonoid molecules with aluminium chloride (AlCl_3) and sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) under alkali conditions created by the addition of 1M NaOH.

1. 100 µl of standard sample/blank was added to 400 µl of de-ionised water in a 1.5 ml eppendorf tube (all analysis was carried out in triplicate).
2. At time = 0, 30 µl of 5% NaNO_2 was added to each tube.

3. At time = 5 minutes, 30 μ l of 10 % $AlCl_3$ was added.
4. At time = 6 minutes, 200 μ l of 1M NaOH was added.
5. 240 μ l of de-ionised water was added to each tube to bring the final volume to 1 ml, and all tubes were vortexed to mix.
6. 200 μ l of each sample was transferred to a clear 96 well plate.
7. Absorbance was read at 510 nm using a micro-plate reader. And sample concentrations were expressed as mg/l catechin equivalents (CE).
8. The assay results were transferred to SPSS statistical software.

Identification using HPLC

1. HPLC analyses were performed on an Agilent 1200 series HPLC system equipped with a diode array detector (DAD). The HPLC method used was based a method previously published by Boros et al., (2010).
2. For aqueous methanol lettuce extract analysis, 2 μ L of the extract was injected into a 3.0 x 100 mm Agilent Poroshell 120 SB-C18 (Stable Bond, 2.7 μ m particle size) analytical column.
3. Mobile phase components consisted of (A) 0.1% formic acid in methanol and (B) 0.1% aqueous formic acid.
4. Injected samples were eluted with the following linear gradient; 0.00 min 3% B eluent, 7.00 min 20% B eluent, 7.10 min 30% B eluent, 17.00 min 40% B eluent, 25.00 min 100% B eluent, 25.10 min 3% B eluent and 30.00 min 3% B eluent.
5. Total sample run time was 30 minutes including wash step and post run. A flow rate of 200 μ L per minute was used. Column temperature was maintained at 50°C.
6. The DAD detector wavelengths were 280, 320, 360 and 520 nm to scan for phenolic acids, cinnamic acids, flavonols and anthocyanins respectively.

1.3.8 Total Glucosinolates Determination

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

Chemicals

- Methanol (70%)
- Sinigrin (sigmaAldrich Catalogue #: 85440, Lot # & Filling Code: 1379280 23808087)
- Aryl Sulfatase: type H-2 from *Helix pomatia*, >2000 unit/ml (SigmaAldrich Cat. No. S9751)
- DEAE Sephadex A-25
- Deionised Water
- Acetonitrile

Apparatus and equipment:

- Centrifuge
- 1ml pipette tips
- Water Bath
- HPLC
- Zorbax Eclipse XDB C18 column 3.5 μ m 150 x 3.0 mm
- 0.45 μ m filter disks
- Vacuum Filtration unit

Preparation (Hong et al. 2011)

1. Extract 50mg of lyophilised sample with 1.5ml 70% (v/v) boiling ethanol in a water bath at 70°C for 5 minutes.
2. Centrifuge for 20 min (13000g at 4°C) and collect supernatant in a test tube.
3. The residue was extracted twice using the same procedure.
4. Apply the combined extracts to a mini column using a 1ml pipette tip packed with DEAE-Sephadex A-25 (approx. 40mg).
5. Desulphate GSL's by adding a solution of aryl sulphatase (75 µl, 2.87 units) to the column.
6. Leave overnight at ambient temperature.
7. Elute with 3 x 0.5ml deionised water.
8. Obtain HPLC profiles by injecting samples of a known volume (20 µl).

Reverse phase-high performance liquid chromatography (Pasini *et al.* 2012)

1. Filter all solvents with a 0.45µm filter disk.
2. HPLC Parameters:
 - Column: Zorbax Eclipse XDB C18 column 3.5µm 150 x 3.0 mm
 - Injection volume: 20 µl
 - Flow rate: 0.550 ml/min
 - Column Temperature: 30°C
 - Wavelength Detection: 229nm
 - Mobile Phase A: Water
 - Mobile Phase B: Acetonitrile
 - Elution Gradient: Start 99% A, linear gradient to 75% A at min 17.5, linear gradient to 99% A at min 20, total analysis time 35 min.
3. For total and individual GLS quantification, create a calibration curve (wavelength detection 229 nm (from 10 to 1000 mg/l, at seven concentration levels).

1.3.9. Non-Structural Carbohydrate (glucose, fructose sucrose) and starch quantification

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The amount of NSC (glucose, fructose, sucrose) and of starch were evaluated in the plant tissues using fresh material powdered with liquid nitrogen in a mortar and pestle or using lyophilised plant material.

1. About 100 mg of fresh plant tissue or 10 mg of dry matter was extracted by 1 ml of 80% ethanol (v/v) water 20% (v/v) water, heating 80 °C for 45 min.
2. The extracts were centrifuged at 16,000 x g for 5 min, soluble sugars (glucose, fructose and sucrose) were recovered in the supernatant, starch was in the pellet.
3. Soluble sugars determination, by spectrophotometric-coupled enzymatic assay, was performed as in Proietti *et al.* 2013).
4. In particular, soluble sugars glucose and fructose were determined through an enzyme linked spectrophotometric assay with hexokinase (1.2 U), glucose phosphate dehydrogenase (0.3 U) and phosphoglucose isomerase (0.3 U) as described by Jones *et al.* (1977) including the modification of Antognozzi *et al.* (1996) and using an Elisa plate reader (Spectrostar Nano Labtech-BMG). Sucrose was first hydrolysed by acid invertase (30 U) and the resulting glucose and fructose were determined as above.
5. Starch was quantified from the pellet remaining after extraction of soluble sugars. The pellet was washed four times with 50 mM NaAcetate buffer (pH 4.5) and then resuspended in 1 ml of the same buffer and autoclaved at 120 °C for 45 min in 1 ml of the same buffer. After autoclaving, the

suspension was incubated at 50°C for 1 h with amyloglucosidase (70 U) and α -amylase (4U) to hydrolyse the starch to glucose, that was then measured enzymatically as described above.

6. The sucrose and starch contents are reported as glucose equivalents.
7. The assay results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).

1.3.10 Structural Carbohydrate: fiber characterisation

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

Lyophilised leaves were milled with a MF10 IKA mill (Werke GmbH & Co. KG) and sieved to screen particles until 500 μ m in size. After milling, the samples were oven dried 24 hours at 45°C and then used for the determination of biomass chemical composition.

1. The relative moisture was determined placing the samples at 105 °C for 24 hours in a ventilated oven.
2. The ash content was quantified after ignition of dried samples at 575 \pm 25 °C for 24 hours using a muffle furnace equipped with a ramping program (Nabertherm P300 Germany).
3. Approximately 150 mg of dried sample was used for the preparation of Alcohol Insoluble Residue (AIR) obtained by a first extraction in 1 ml of deionised water at 50 °C for 30 min. This step was repeated 4 times to a final extraction volume of 4 ml for each sample. The insoluble biomass was collected by centrifugation performed at 16,000 x g for 5 min at 4°C. The second extraction was performed at 25 °C using 95% ethanol and 5% water on the water insoluble material, following the same procedure described for the first step. Then a third extraction was performed at 25 °C using 100% acetone following the same procedure describe for above. Water, ethanol and acetone extracts were quantified gravimetrically drying the insoluble biomass obtained from the AIR in a ventilated oven for 24 hours at 45°C.
4. The AIR extracts were used for the determination of cell wall component as lignin and monomer of insoluble fiber polysaccharides. The chemical composition of rocket leaves cell wall was determined following NREL protocol (TP-510-42618, Sluiter et al. 2011) with 72% H₂SO₄ treatment at 30°C for 1 h and subsequent 4% H₂SO₄ treatment at 121 °C for 1 h in autoclave. After the two steps acid hydrolysis, the autoclaved solution was vacuum filtered using a calibrated glass filter (GF/A 55 mm diameter GE-Whatman, Maidstone, UK).
5. In the hydrolysed liquor the lignin is fractionated into acid soluble lignin and acid insoluble material (Klason lignin). The Klason lignin was determined gravimetrically of the solid residue on the glass filter after drying at 105 °C for 24 h. In addition, the acid soluble lignin was measured using UV–Vis spectrophotometer (Jenway 6715 Bibby Scientific) at 205 nm, with the extinction coefficient of 110 L g⁻¹ cm⁻¹.
6. The filtrate was subsequently analysed for monosaccharides resulting from the acid hydrolysis: fructose, glucose, arabinose, galactose, xylose, mannose, rhamnose and galacturonic acid. The monomeric sugars were analysed by The IC ICS-5000 Thermo Scientific™ Dionex™ equipped with a pulsed amperometric detector (HPAEC-PAD) with a Ag/AgCl reference electrode and an analytical CarboPac PA20 column (5 μ m 3 mm x 150 mm) with the guard column. The electrical signal was integrated in nanocoulomb (nC). Runs were carried out at 30 °C using a mobile phase gradient of NaOH and 100mM acetic acid plus 100 mM NAOH at a flow rate 0,4 ml min⁻¹. The gradient was as performed as following described: from 0 to 20 min 12mM NaOH; from 20 to 30 min 100mM NaOH; from 30 to 46 min 100mM acetic acid plus 100 mM NAOH; from 46 to 50 min 200mM NaOH and finally from 50 to 60 min 12mM NaOH as reequilibration. The eluents and the carbohydrate standard solutions were prepared using HPLC grade reagents (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany).
7. The results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).
8. The Ion chromatography ICS-5000 systems control, data acquisition, and processing were performed by the software Chromeleon Data System 6.8 (ThermoScientific™, Dionex™).

1.3.11 Isoflavonoid analysis

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

Extraction

Isoflavonoids were extracted as per Downey et al 2012, with modification

1. Freeze-dried tissues of known weights were milled manually to a fine to medium meal in situ, in the vessels in which they were contained.
2. A volume of 80% ethanol, predetermined through calculation, was added to each sample and the sample was left to extract for an hour at room temperature.
3. The samples were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes before the supernatant was removed and transferred to a clean sample tube. Samples were extracted twice.
4. After the second extraction, the samples were centrifuged at 4000 rpm to ensure sufficient formation of a pellet.
5. The supernatant was removed and added to the previous extraction supernatant and was made up to volume using 80% ethanol.
6. A predetermined portion of the supernatant was filtered into a clean, glass test tube and evaporated by centrifugal evaporation before being reconstituted and concentrated using a determined volume of 75% ethanol.
7. Samples were further filtered and added to amber HPLC vials and stored at -20 °C prior to analysis.

Stock Preparation

1. Isoflavonoid stock solutions of daidzin, genistin, formononetin and biochanin A were prepared by dissolving 5 mg of each respectively (CAS #: 552-66-9, 529-59-9, 485-72-3, 491-80-5, respectively, Sigma Aldrich, Ireland) in 80% ethanol in a 25 ml volumetric flask, resulting in stock concentrations of 462.55 nmol/ml and 480.34 nmol/ml for genistin and daidzin, respectively and 745.54 nmol/ml and 703.48 nmol/ml for formononetin and biochanin A, respectively.
2. A small amount of heat needed to be applied in order to fully dissolve daidzin.
3. After complete dissolution, the stock was filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane and aliquoted in 1 ml batches into amber-coloured HPLC vials and stored at -20°C. Dilutions were prepared as outlined in Table 1.3.7a. Triplicate standard solutions per concentration level were made.

Table 1.6 – Isoflavonoid stock preparation

Std	V. (µl) of stock	V (µl) 75% ethanol	Concentration (nmol/ml)			
			Daidzin	Genistin	Biochanin A	Formononetin
L1	5.00	995.00	2.40	2.31	3.52	3.73
L2	10.00	990.00	4.80	4.63	7.03	7.46
L3	50.00	950.00	24.02	23.13	35.17	37.28
L4	100.00	900.00	48.03	46.26	70.35	74.55
L5	200.00	800.00	96.07	92.51	140.70	149.10
L6	400.00	600.00	192.14	185.02	281.39	298.21
L7	500.00	500.00	240.17	231.28	351.74	372.76
L8	750.00	250.00			527.61	
Stock			480.34	462.55	703.48	745.52

Spectrometric Determination

1. Extracts (from callus and seedling samples) were diluted 5 times directly in a UV transparent cuvette (BrandTech Scientific, Inc., Essex, CT, USA). Parafilm was used to cover the cuvettes before mixing the samples by inversion.
2. Absorbance readings were taken at 252, 260 and 263 nm using a Beckman Coulter DU730 spectrophotometer.
3. Calibration curves were developed from the working standard solutions detailed in Table 1.3.7a for each batch of samples from which the total isoflavonoid concentration (measured in nmol/mg fresh weight (FW)) of the callus and seedling samples was calculated.

1.3.12 Polyphenol Analysis using tandem LC-MS

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

1. Compounds were separated using an Acquity UPLC BEH Phenyl 2.1 x 50 mm 1.7 μ m column. The flow rate was 0.5 ml/min. The column temperature was 50°C.
2. A gradient mobile phase of 0.5 % formic acid in water (A) and 0.5 % formic acid in acetonitrile, the composition over a 10-minute run was as follows: 0 mins, 2 % B; 1 min, 2 % B; 2.5 mins, 10 % B; 3 mins, 20 % B; 6 mins, 20 % B; 7.5 mins, 35 % B; 8.5 mins, 98 % B; 9.5 mins, 98 % B; 9.51, 2 % B; 10 mins, 2 % B.
3. MS/MS detection was carried out in negative electron ionization (EI) mode. The source parameters for detection were as follows: capillary voltage 3. kV (positive); cone voltage, 30 V; desolvation temperature, 350°C; flow rate 50 L/hr and source temperature, 120°C.
4. Both samples and standards were extracted/prepared in methanol. Samples were analysed for rutin, luteolin, epicatechin, chlorogenic acid, 4-hydroxy benzoic acid, procatechuic acid, caffeic acid, ferulic acid, gallic acid, and quercetin.
5. Data was acquired using Mass Lynx software.

1.3.13 Ascorbic Acid Analysis by HPLC

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The ascorbic acid content was determined using the fresh plant material, powdered with liquid nitrogen in a mortar and pestle.

1. About 60 mg of frozen plant material was extract in a glass/glass homogeniser with 2 mL of 3% TCA at 4°C.
 2. The mixtures were centrifuged at 16,000 $\times g$ for 5 min at 4°C. The supernatants were filtrated through a nylon 0.45 μ m disposable syringe filter (Whatman) and used to determine the concentration of ascorbic acid using the HPLC UltiMate 3000 Dionex ThermoScientific.
 3. The HPLC system was equipped with an Acclaim™ PolarAdvantage C16 analytical column (5 μ m, 250 x 4.6 mm) (Dionex ThermoScientific), and a related guard column, maintained at 30 °C.
 4. Extract was eluted using of 200mM KH₂PO₄ (pH 2.8) as the mobile phase, in isocratic condition and at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. The autosampler was at 4 °C, and the UV detector wavelength was set at 254 nm.
 5. The concentration of ascorbate was determined against ascorbic acid standard curve.
 6. The results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).
- The HPLC UltiMate 3000 systems control, data acquisition, and processing were performed by the software Chromeleon Data System 6.8 (ThermoScientific™, Dionex™).

1.3.14 β -carotene Analysis using LC-MS

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The method was carried out as outlined by Saha et al., 2013 with partial validation of the linearity and precision of the method.

Sample Preparation

1. All standards were prepared in HPLC grade acetone.
2. Samples were extracted in to 100% acetone by adding 1 g of freeze dried and ground sample to a sample tube and adding 10 ml of solvent.
3. The samples were vortexed for 10 seconds, sonicated for 15 mins then centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 20 mins at 4°C using a Thermo Biofuge Stratos centrifuge.
4. The resulting supernatant was filtered through 0.45 μ m syringe filters in to amber vials.
5. Exposure of the standards and samples to light was kept to a minimum throughout preparation to avoid degradation.

Analysis

1. β -carotene was resolved using an ACE C18 5 μ m (250 x 4.6 mm id) HPLC column using a gradient mobile phase system.
2. Mobile phase A was methyl tertbutyl ether (MTBE)/methanol/water (90:5:5) and mobile phase B was MTBE/methanol/water (55:43:2).
3. The flow rate was 0.6 ml/min and separation was carried out in 26 minutes as follows; 0 mins, 0% B; 5 mins, 0.1% B; 7 mins, 40% B; 10 mins, 50% B; 12 mins, 100% B, 20 mins, 100%; 22 mins, 0% B.
4. The detection system used was a diode array detector (DAD) set to monitor at 478.8 nm.
5. Data acquisition was performed using Agilent Mass Hunter Qualitative software.

1.3.15 Organic Acid and Inorganic Anions Analysis

Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols

The ethanolic extracts, used for NSC determination, were also used for quantification of organic acids and inorganic anions. After extraction, samples were centrifuged at 16,000 \times g for 5 min at 4°C and the supernatants were filtrated through a nylon 0.2 μ m PPII syringe filters (Whatman) prior to injection in the chromatography system.

1. The quantification was performed by a Ion Chromatography System Dionex™ ICS-5000, equipped with a conductivity detector, an analytical IonPac AS11-HC column (4 mm x 250 mm), with related guard column and a IonPac ATC-1 (Anion Trap column).
2. The system was coupled with the ERS™ 500 Electrolytically Regenerated Suppressors (ThermoScientific™, Dionex™) operating in the external water mode, using 100% methanol and a flow rate of this organic solvent of 3,5 ml min⁻¹.
3. Runs were carried out at 30° C and a flow rate of 1,0 ml min⁻¹ using the following gradient: from 0 to 18min of 1mM NaOH; 18 to 28min of 15mM NaOH and 20% methanol; 28 to 38min of 30mM NaOH and 20% methanol; from 38 to 41 min of 60mM NaOH; from 41 to 51 min of 1mM NaOH as re-equilibration step. The electrical signal was integrated in micro Siemens (μ S).
4. The eluents and the organic acid standard solutions were prepared using HPLC grade reagents (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany).
5. The results were analysed by STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows).
6. The Ion chromatography ICS-5000 systems control, data acquisition, and processing were performed by the software Chromeleon Data System 6.8 (ThermoScientific™, Dionex™).

1.3.16 Organoleptic Analysis

Purpose

Food sensory evaluation is a scientific discipline that analyses and measures human responses to the composition of food and drinks, e.g. appearance, touch, odour, texture, temperature and taste. Sensory evaluation can be used to compare similarities/differences in a range of foods, verify whether a final food product meets its pre-determined specification and provide objective feedback to enable informed decisions for product development. Sensory evaluation can be utilised in a closed environment crop growth system to determine the palatability of the fresh produce for consumption. A trained sensory panel will assess sensory aspects of crops pre -Antarctica at the research facility Food@LIT. EDEN ISS will utilise these trained panellists to determine food sensory quality of the closed environment crops. The interactive nature of the trained panel will help to identify key product characteristics and provide insights to the crew perception of the crops. This information will then be used to enhance growth and train the crew in sensory evaluation prior to Antarctica. This way, EDEN ISS will add value to the knowledge and understanding of important food sensory factors essential for crew's acceptance of crops grown in closed environments. In addition, this may be of particular importance for long-duration space flights as positive sensory responses by astronauts to their food may stimulate positive psychological responses.

Consumables and Equipment

- Paper plates, cups, knives, forks, spoons (white)
- White booths for sensory analysis.
- Fruit and vegetable samples
- Lettuce spinner
- Chopping board and knives
- Serving spoons
- Napkins

Sensory Panel Training

The Food@LIT sensory panel was recruited in January 2011 with consideration given to the Institute of Food Science and Technology Guidelines for Ethical and Professional Practices for the Sensory Analysis of Foods 2010. The criteria for participants were that they were available to volunteer for the project; they were non-smokers, in good health and regular consumers of the samples included in the study. Participants who were willing to volunteer were then asked to complete a consent form and diet survey. Training in sensory analysis and quantitative descriptive analysis commenced with ten participants according to ISO International standards (8586-1, 1993).

The panellists were first educated on the meaning of sensory analysis, its uses, and the nature and aims of the present research. The theory of the senses and their use in food selection was then discussed and the panel was given examples and tests throughout this section e.g.:

- Identification of aromas of food, e.g. citrus and fruit aromas, mint, cloves, herbs.
- Identification of crisp flavours without the help of packaging.
- Identification of sweet, sour, salt, bitter and umami tastes.
- Rating of different concentrations of one taste as low, high or medium.
- Descriptive analysis of texture of a range of foods e.g. marshmallow, rice cakes, crisps, banana, carrot.

The panel was then educated on the different types of sensory analysis methods, i.e., acceptability tests, discrimination tests, duo-trio tests, triangle tests, and descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis was then discussed in more detail, the panels' vocabulary on food descriptors was expanded using examples and brainstorming sessions. Over the remaining weeks of training the panel were asked to describe a range of foods that would be tested in the study in terms of appearance, aroma, texture and taste and were tested on their ability to rank the descriptive numerically with good panel agreement (precision).

The panel was finally evaluated for correct detection of basic taste solutions (salt, sweet, bitter, sour and umami) and consistent scoring of descriptors of fruit and vegetable samples.

panellist

Figure 1.6: A sensory

scoring carrots in a white booth.

Sample Preparation

All samples should be harvested, washed in water, dried (as appropriate) and stored in zip lock bags at 4°C. Samples should be tested within 2 weeks of harvesting. Immediately prior to testing samples should be prepared in a manner appropriate to the sample this may include, removal of stalks, roots, chopping, peeling and coring etc. Samples (appropriate quantity) should be presented on/in coded (3 figure codes) white containers and plates. Panellists should be provided with water and plain crackers to cleanse their palate in between sample tastings. Booths maybe set up as per the example below. The test room is also equipped with special white lighting and kept free from any strong smells.

Figure 1.7: Example of a sensory evaluation booth set up.

Sensory Evaluation

Panellists evaluate the acceptability of each product as per the hedonic acceptability scale (Table 1.7) giving a score 1-9 for each product. The mean/average score for each product is calculated and an acceptability bar chart is generated.

Table 1.7: Acceptability scale used to score each product

Following for each food type the panel will first brainstorm appropriate descriptors that maybe be used to assess the samples (descriptors used in literature are also consulted where available The panellists are instructed to assess each sample in order of aroma, appearance, texture and taste. Each sample is scored between 1 and 9 for each of the descriptors on a test sheet with printed scales and place an X on the scale to rank the sample.

All sensory results are transferred to an Excel worksheet the means and standard deviations are calculated and a spider chart generated.

Descriptor	Mean \pm Std Dev (N=3)
Colour intensity	4.8 \pm 0.36
Aroma	3.3 \pm 0.43
Hardness (on bite)	4.2 \pm 0.79
Juiciness (on chew)	5.5 \pm 0.22
Leathery skin (after, residual)	4.6 \pm 1.23
Sourness	4.4 \pm 0.44
Sweetness	4.3 \pm 0.16

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Sensory Evaluation Antarctica

Prior to Antarctica the crew will be trained in relation to sensory evaluation and subsequently assessed for correctness in detection as per Sensory Panel Training section above. This will take approximately 5 days of 2 x 2 hrs per day.

The crew will be trained in sensory analysis and quantitative descriptive analysis according to ISO International standards (8586, 2012). The crew will be first educated on the meaning of sensory analysis, its uses, and the nature and aims of the research. The theory of the senses and their use in food selection will then be discussed and the crew will be trained in:

- Sample storage and preparation
- Acceptability analysis
- Descriptive analysis

Crop evaluations will be carried out by the crew as per the 'Sample Evaluation' and 'Sensory Evaluation' sections with possible modifications as identified during the pre-Antarctica studies (Appendices 1.7.2 and 1.7.3).

1.3.17 Microbial Analysis

The aim of microbial analysis is to evaluate the microflora composition of different vegetables, which will be grown in a second phase of the project at the NM3. In a first step, the analyses are performed at CNR labs.

Sample Preparation

Fresh/frozen plants (edible portions) are weighted in sterile tubes, cut using sterile scissors, kept (rate 1:10 w:vol) in sterile physiological solution, and added to a Stomacher sterile bags; then, it is subjected to three cycles (30-60 sec each, depending on the structure of vegetables: for leafy vegetables 3x30" are sufficient, as well as for tomato; when the structure is harder, 3x60" cycles are necessary) of homogenization by using a the Stomacher circulator machine, a paddle blender homogenizer. If it is impossible to use the stomacher, the homogenization is performed using a simple sterile pipette and "stamping" sample, contained into sterile tube, into physiological solution, centrifuging (using sterile tubes) at 4000 x g at 4°C for 10-15 minutes, and collecting the liquid portion. This last is collected into sterile tubes and serially diluted (1:10 for at least 4 times) using sterile physiological solution.

From the two last dilutions, 1 ml is used and plated onto agar plates for the specific analysis.

Samples are so ready to be analyzed to monitor the presence and type of microflora.

For total microbial count is used Nutrient growth medium or TY medium.

- **For total microbial count**

- 1) Preparation of growth medium Nutrient Broth

Suspend 13 grams of the medium in one liter of distilled water. To prepare the basis for the agar plates, add microbiological or technical agar powder (1.2-1.5%). The solution is well mixed, dissolved by heating with frequent agitation and boiled 1 minute until complete dissolution. The solution is dispensed into appropriate containers (bottle, tubes, flasks), which are sterilized in autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes or under pressure cooker at least for 45 minutes (to check through the color change of appropriate strip). Preparation of Nutrient Agar: in this case technical or microbiological agar (1.2-1.5% w:vol) is added to the medium before the operations of sterilization. This medium will be dispensed (20 ml/plate) in sterile plates, in sterile conditions (under lamina flow hood or near a Bunsen dispenser). Plates filled are kept for 10 minutes to allow the drying and polymerization of the medium, so plates are stored at 4°C until use.

Or

- 2) Preparation of Ty medium (Tryptone glucose yeast extract). This is a medium used for the counting of viable microorganisms in general. It is composed of tryptone (5g/l); yeast extract (2.5 g/l); glucose (1.0 g/l) and (for plating) agar (1.2-1.5% w:vol). The ingredients are dissolved (17.5 g/l) in a liter of distilled water. The solution is well mixed, dissolved by heating with frequent agitation and boiled 1 minute until complete dissolution. The solution is dispensed into appropriate containers (bottle, tubes, flasks), which are sterilized in autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes or under pressure cooker at least for 45 minutes (to check through the color change of appropriate strip). Plates are prepared in sterile conditions (20 ml/plate), dried under the same conditions and stored at 2-8 °C until use. 1 ml of liquid portion (sample) is added and distributed onto the surface of plates. Incubation of plates: 32-35°C for 48 h.

- **For lactic acid bacteria**

We use MRS medium, a formula optimized by De Man, Rogosa and Sharp in 1960. With such medium we grow bacteria belonging to the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Streptococcus*, *Pediococcus* and *Leuconostoc*. The growth of such genera is enhanced in the absence of oxygen or the presence of a little amount of oxygen. The pH is adjusted to values of 6.5. Suspend 52 grams of the medium in one liter of distilled water. To prepare the basis for the agar plates, add microbiological or technical agar powder (1.2-1.5%). The solution is well mixed, dissolved by heating with frequent agitation and boiled 1 minute until complete dissolution. The solution is dispensed into appropriate containers (bottle, tubes, flasks), which are sterilized in autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes or under pressure cooker at least for 45 minutes (to check through the color change of appropriate strip). Preparation of MRS Agar: in this case technical or microbiological agar (1.2-1.5% w:vol) is added to the medium before the operations of sterilization. This medium will be dispensed (20 ml/plate) in sterile plates, in sterile conditions (under lamina flow hood or near a Bunsen dispenser). Plates filled are kept for 10 minutes to allow the drying and polymerization of the medium, so plates are stored at 4°C until use. Samples are generally mixed with the agar medium (before its polymerization and in any case at temperature no so high to avoid the death of eventual microorganisms present in) or plated onto the surface. After polymerization or drying, respectively, plates are incubated at different temperatures: thermophilic bacteria at 42°C for 2 days; mesophilic bacteria at 35°C for 2 days; meso-psicrofilic bacteria: 30°C for 2 days; psicrofilic bacteria: 25°C for 3 days. Plates are incubated in the presence of humidity, to avoid the concentration of selective factors on the plate surface.

As positive control is used *Lactobacillus acidophilus* (37°C for two days); as negative control is used *Staphylococcus aureus* (37°C for 1 day).

Composition of medium (g/l): Enzymatic digest of casein 10; Meat extract 10; Yeast extract 4; Tri-ammonium citrate 2; Sodium acetate 5; Magnesium sulphate heptahydrate 0.2; Manganese sulphate tetrahydrate 0.05; Di-potassium hydrogen phosphate 2; Sorbitan mono-oleate 1.08; Glucose 20; Agar 12.4 (necessary for counting on plates). TOTAL: 66.73g/L

- **For molds and yeasts: Potato Dextrose medium or Sabouraud dextrose medium are used.**
- **Potato dextrose agar**

Suspend 39 grams of the medium (Potato dextrose medium) or 30 grams (of Sabouraud) in one liter of distilled water. To prepare the basis for the agar plates, add microbiological or technical agar powder (1.2-1.5%). The solution is well mixed, dissolved by heating with frequent agitation and boiled 1 minute until complete dissolution. The solution is dispensed into appropriate containers (bottle, tubes, flasks), which are sterilized in autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes or under pressure cooker at least for 45 minutes (to check through the color change of appropriate strip). To inhibit microbial growth is opportune to acidify the medium by adding 1 ml of lactic acid 10% when the medium has a temperature not higher than 50°C. When Sabouraud medium is used for the preparation of the agar plates, it must not be heated after the addition of acid, because the heat would cause the agar hydrolysis destroying the gelling properties. The medium will be dispensed (20 ml/plate) in sterile plates, in sterile conditions (under lamina flow hood or near a Bunsen dispenser). Plates filled are kept for 10 minutes to allow the polymerization and the drying of the medium, then plates are stored at 4°C until use.

Formula of Potato dextrose agar medium

Formula / Liter of Saboraud Medium:

Enzymatic Digest of Casein 5 g;

Enzymatic Digest of Animal Tissue 5 g;

Dextrose 40 g;

Agar 15 g;

Final pH: 5.6 ± 0.2 at 25°C

Grams/l	Ingredient
~1000	water
200	Potatoes (sliced washed unpeeled)
20	dextrose
20	agar powder

- **For the isolation and count of Staphylococci**

Mannitol salt agar is a selective medium mainly used for staphylococci. Using such medium, pathogenic staphylococci produce colonies surrounded of a yellow halo, the not pathogenic staphylococci form colonies with red-purple halos. Suspend 111 grams of the medium in one liter of distilled water. To prepare the basis for the agar plates, add microbiological or technical agar powder (1.2-1.5%). The solution is well mixed, dissolved by heating with frequent agitation and boiled 1 minute until complete dissolution. The solution is dispensed into appropriate containers (bottle, tubes, flasks), which are sterilized in autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes or under pressure cooker at least for 45 minutes (to check through the color change of appropriate strip). When the containers reach a temperature close to 45-50 °C, plates are filled by adding 20 ml/each, in sterile conditions, dried under sterile conditions (laminar flow hood or near a Bunsen), and stored at 4°C before use. For the counting of potential staphylococci, after the serial dilution, 1 ml is used to inoculate the plates. These are incubated at 35°C for 36 h. Then, the eventual colonies are counted, and the result is expressed for gram of product (taking into account the weight of the initial sample).

As positive control, two strains are used: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 25923 and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228; *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 is used as negative control.

- **For the enrichment and eventual detection of Salmonella**

RAPPAPORT-VASSILIADIS SALMONELLA ENRICHMENT BROTH.

Rappaport et al formulated an enrichment medium for *Salmonella* spp. that was modified by Vassiliadis et al. The Rappaport formulation, designated R 25/37°C, recommended incubation at 37°C. The Vassiliadis modification, designated R 10/43°C, had a reduced level of Malachite Green and recommended incubation at 43°C. Peterz later showed that incubation at 41.5 ± 0.5°C for 24 hours improved recovery of *Salmonella* spp. In Rappaport-Vassiliadis Salmonella Enrichment Broth, Soy Peptone has replaced Enzymatic Digest of Casein as the nitrogen and vitamin source. Soy Peptone has shown to enhance the growth of *Salmonella* spp. and minimizes Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy (BSE) risk. Rappaport-Vassiliadis Salmonella Enrichment Broth conforms to Harmonized United States Pharmacopoeia (USP), European Pharmacopoeia (EU), and Japanese Pharmacopoeia (JP). This medium selectively enriches for *Salmonella* spp. because bacteria, including other intestinal bacteria, are typically susceptible to or inhibited by Malachite Green, high osmotic pressure and/or low pH. *S. typhi* and *S. choleraesuis* are sensitive to Malachite Green and may be inhibited.

Soy Peptone is the carbon and nitrogen sources for general growth requirements in Rappaport-Vassiliadis

Salmonella Enrichment Broth. Magnesium Chloride raises the osmotic pressure in the medium, and Potassium Phosphate acts as a buffer. Malachite Green is inhibitory to organisms other than *Salmonella* spp. The low pH of the medium, combined with the presence of Malachite Green and Magnesium Chloride, select for the highly resistant *Salmonella* spp.

Formula / Liter: Soy Peptone 4.50 g, Sodium Chloride 8.0 g, Potassium Phosphate, monobasic 0.60 g, Potassium Phosphate, dibasic 0.40 g, Magnesium Chloride, anhydrous 13.58 g (Equivalent to 29.0 g/L Magnesium Chloride hexahydrate, Malachite Green 0.036 g, Final pH: 5.2 ± 0.2 at 25°C.

Formula may be adjusted and/or supplemented as required to meet performance specifications. *

Precautions: IRRITANT. Irritating to eyes, respiratory system, and skin.

Directions: 27.2 g of the medium are dissolved in one liter of purified water and mixed thoroughly. 10 mL into glass tubes are dispensed into glass tubes, cap and autoclaved at 115°C for 15 minutes or in domestic pressure cooker for 45 minutes. Proceed following the instruction given for the other media of growth. *Salmonella typhimurium* is used as positive control; *Escherichia coli* is used as negative control. Plates are incubated at 42°C for 24-48 hours.

The above described are the conventional media used.

- **For the simultaneous detection of total coliforms and *Escherichia coli* is used the HiCrome Coliform Agar w/ SLS**

Principle and Interpretation: HiCrome Coliform Agar w/SLS is a selective medium recommended for the simultaneous detection of *Escherichia coli* and total coliforms. Peptone special and sodium pyruvate provide essential growth nutrients to the organisms. The phosphates buffer the medium well. The medium composition helps even the sub-lethally injured coliforms to grow rapidly. Sodium lauryl sulphate inhibits gram-positive organisms. The chromogenic mixture contains two chromogenic substrates. The enzyme β -galactosidase produced by coliforms cleaves one chromogen, resulting in the salmon red colouration of coliform colonies. The enzyme β -glucuronidase produced by *E. coli*, cleaves X-glucuronide. *E. coli* forms dark blue to violet coloured colonies due to cleavage of both the chromogens (1, 2,3). The addition of L-Tryptophan improves the indole reaction, thereby increasing detection reliability in combination with the two chromogens. To confirm *E. coli*, a drop of Kovacs reagent (R008) is added on the dark-blue to violet colony. Formation of cherry-red colour indicates positive reaction.

Composition of the medium (Grams/Liter): Peptone, special 3; Sodium chloride 5; Dipotassium hydrogen phosphate 3; Potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1.7; Sodium pyruvate 1; L-Tryptophan 1; Sodium lauryl sulphate 0.1; Chromogenic mixture 0.2; Agar 12; Final pH (at 25°C) 6.8

Suspend 27 grams in 1000 ml distilled water. Heat to boiling to dissolve the medium completely. Sterilize by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes, or for at least 45 minutes at 121°C; Add 5mg/l novobiocin before autoclaving the medium, when a high number of Gram positive accompanying bacteria are expected. When the containers reach a temperature close to 45-50 °C, plates are filled by adding 20 ml/each, in sterile conditions, dried under sterile conditions (laminar flow hood or near a Bunsen), and stored at 4°C before use. For the counting of potential staphylococci, after the serial dilution, 1 ml is used to inoculate the plates. These are incubated at 35°C for 36 h. Then, the eventual colonies are counted, and result is

expressed for gram of product (taking into account the weight of the initial sample).

1.4 Sample Handling and Transport Requirements

1.4.1 Food Quality

Procedures for sample sampling handling and transport have been discussed in previous chapters. Here it is particularly relevant to note that cold storage during sample transport from Antarctica to home laboratories will be crucial for adequate sample stability and then for quality of analytical results on post-mission activities.

1.4.2 Food Safety

During home laboratories activities, procedures of sample harvest sub-sampling, stabilisation storage and testing have been revised and applied by ISA to vegetables produced at the IBAF laboratory. If not all types of plant material will be produced from the IBAF experiments, commercial product will be used.

Sampling protocol example

The sampling scheme is as follows:

- Labelling – this will follow the scheme proposed by CNR-LIT for food quality
- Sub-sampling – the aim is to collect a specific number of plant tissue for microbial analysis and each analysis will be performed in triplicates
- Stabilisation and storage – freeze-drying to minimise the potential damage and to enable long term storage

CNR will determine the effect of short term and long-term storage on food safety with respect to the edible portion of vegetables already identified in a previous meeting. Both short term and long-term storage analysis will be performed on fresh and frozen samples: this last aspect is due to the conditions which will be encountered in the extreme habitat (*in primis* at the Neumayer Station III) and by the no chance that samples grown there could, of course, be transported as fresh to Europe. This means also that, taking into account the analysis on frozen products, the microbial analysis on them will be performed as soon as possible or also after some days/weeks after their arrival at the CNR labs. The Analysis of fresh products will also be performed at the CNR labs. This also to have a sort of threshold in preparation of the analyses which will interest samples arriving from the Antarctic station. At CNR the analyses will be performed taking into account the conventional methods, such as the plate count and the measure of microbial density by spectrophotometer at specific wavelengths (generally 600nm).

1.4.3 Storage

LIT will determine the effect of short term and long-term storage on food quality with respect to Sensory Analysis. The minimum duration after harvesting that sensory analysis can take place is five days. Therefore, cold storage of produce of predetermined mass will be stored in ziplock bags at 4 °C. Samples to be analysed for food safety will be stored in sterile polypropylene tubes containing 20% sterile glycerol. Long term storage of plant tissue for Sensory Analysis will not be required as it is planned that training of the NM-III crew in sensory analysis will be carried out by LIT specialist Dr. Tracey Larkin in Bremen pre-Antarctic departure.

In preparation for the assessment of MTF and ISPR produce by a trained sensory panel, assessment of microbial profiles and mapping to potential toxin production must first be carried out, to ensure the safety of sensory panel members. Simple washing protocols post-harvest (agreed with IBAF, CNR) will be

utilised and followed by stringent microbial investigation. Those microbes identified will then be mapped with known bio toxins that they may produce. If such a microbe / toxin profile is identified, a bio toxicological protocol will be developed and utilised to ensure that toxin is not present on the produce. To ensure no unknown microbe toxin profile is identified, a full screening of all produce from the home lab pre-Antarctic testing will be completed in the first round of growth tests for all S/C.

Long term storage of all samples for compositional analysis will be investigated using freeze drying procedures. As explained above, some nutraceutically important molecules are damaged by some freezing techniques. LIT will investigate the effect of freeze-drying on this prior to the initiation of the project on the MTF. Should no protocol be identified for the safe storage of plant tissue that will not affect sensitive molecules of interest, then simple lab-based tests will be investigated to aid the crew of NM3 to potentially determine some of the molecules in question on the fresh produce.

Organoleptic analysis will also be utilised in this task to ensure food stored in this manner remains palatable for the NM-III crew. Microbial analysis will can be done: 1) on freeze-dried samples [pre- pared, at CNR labs, simulating the conditions suggested by LIT-CNR for storage at NM3] and 2) using the same samples prepared by CNR for the analysis of food quality. Food quality and safety analysis will be performed concurrently LIT, with the contribution of CNR, plans to test storage of fresh produce of selected species for a period of 30 days in sealed bags with modified atmosphere at temperature in the range of 0-5°C. The possibility to use biodegradable plastic bag will be tested in house thanks to contacts with a leading Italian industry on the field of bio-based polymers. The plan is to select a few species (a selection of leafy and fruit), sanitise them, collect initial samples for quality and safety and seal in a controlled atmosphere and low temperature and store for up to 30 days. Transparent bags should allow visual testing of the produce to verify its appearance during storage. If no visual degradation is detected, samples of produce for quality and safety analysis will be taken at the end of the storage cycle and treated as those obtained from a normal production cycle. (Stabilisation by freezing and transport to home laboratories for analysis will also be involved). Home laboratories pre-mission activities will be crucial in defining feasibility of the proposed approach and the choice of the species and cultivar selected and the number of samples required.

1.5 Overall Expected Outputs

Table 1-8 illustrates the expected final outputs and datasets of this work package including associated documentation.

Table 1-8: WP 4.3.A. Final Outputs including Dataset Documentation.

<i>Output. No.</i>	<i>Output Description</i>	<i>Participant</i>	<i>Output Type</i>
4.3.OP.1A	Pre-Mission Test Plan Report	CNR / LIT	Report
4.3.OP.1A.1	Preliminary Composition Analysis Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.2	Confirmatory Composition Analysis Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.3	Organoleptic Analysis Protocols	LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.4	Food Safety Protocols	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.5	Storage Protocols (Analytical and Organoleptic Samples)	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.7	Optimised SOP's for use of handheld meters	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report
4.3.OP.1A.7	Sample Handling Document	CNR / LIT	Protocol Set/Preliminary Report

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1.7 Appendix A – General Supporting Information

1.7.1 Equipment

A substantial amount of the equipment was already established in the CNR and LIT labs, while some was acquired directly as part of the project (Table 1-9).

Table 1-9: WP 4.3.A. Equipment.

<i>IOP No.</i>	<i>Equipment Description</i>	<i>Participant Location</i>
	UV/VIS-Spectrophotometer	CNR / LIT
	Plate reader Spectro starnano (BMG)	CNR / LIT
	Micro titre Plate Reader with Fluorescence	CNR / LIT
	Freeze-drier	CNR / LIT
	Centrifuge	CNR / LIT
	Lab Plant Tissue Grinder	CNR / LIT
	Leaf Area Meter	CNR / LIT
	Ventilated oven	CNR / LIT
	Nitrate Cardy Meter	CNR / LIT
	HPLC UV/VIS Detector	CNR / LIT
	Thermo-Ultimate 3000	CNR / LIT
	SPAD Meter	CNR / LIT
	Penetrometer	CNR / LIT
	Hand Held Colorimeter	CNR / LIT
	Thermo (Dionex) Ion Chromatography system	CNR
	ICS 500 Plus Combined	CNR / LIT
	HPLC	CNR / LIT
	Thermo (Dionex) Anion IC System	CNR
	Muffle furnace	CNR / LIT
	Agilent 1200 Series LC System w/ 6450 QTOF	CNR / LIT
	Atomic Absorption Spectrometer	CNR / LIT
	Graphite Furnace AA	CNR / LIT
	Lachette Ion Detector	CNR / LIT
	Gas Chromatography Mass Spec	CNR / LIT
	Supercritical Fluid Extraction (SCFE) Agilent 1200 Series	CNR / LIT
	RapidRes LC with RI Detection	CNR / LIT

1.7.2 Sensory Acceptability Test Sheet

Name: _____

Date: _____

Please assess each sample separately

<p>Sample __XXX__</p> <p>9 ___ I like it extremely</p> <p>8 ___ I like it very much</p> <p>7 ___ I like it moderately</p> <p>6 ___ I like it slightly</p> <p>5 ___ I neither like or dislike</p> <p>4 ___ I dislike it slightly</p> <p>3 ___ I dislike it moderately</p> <p>2 ___ I dislike it very much</p> <p>1 ___ I dislike it extremely</p>	<p>Please write comments on rating of the product and how it could be improved.</p>
<p>Sample __XXX__</p> <p>9 ___ I like it extremely</p> <p>8 ___ I like it very much</p> <p>7 ___ I like it moderately</p> <p>6 ___ I like it slightly</p> <p>5 ___ I neither like or dislike</p> <p>4 ___ I dislike it slightly</p> <p>3 ___ I dislike it moderately</p> <p>2 ___ I dislike it very much</p> <p>1 ___ I dislike it extremely</p>	<p>Please write comments on rating of the product and how it could be improved.</p>
<p>Sample __XXX__</p> <p>9 ___ I like it extremely</p> <p>8 ___ I like it very much</p> <p>7 ___ I like it moderately</p> <p>6 ___ I like it slightly</p> <p>5 ___ I neither like or dislike</p> <p>4 ___ I dislike it slightly</p> <p>3 ___ I dislike it moderately</p> <p>2 ___ I dislike it very much</p> <p>1 ___ I dislike it extremely</p>	<p>Please write comments on rating of the product and how it could be improved.</p>

1.7.3 Sensory Descriptive Analysis Test Sheet

Please rate the samples for the following: (Insert code and mark an 'X' on scale 1-9)

Descriptor _____:

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: ___XXX_____ Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: ___XXX_____ Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Descriptor _____:

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: _____XXX Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: ___XXX_____ Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Code: ___XXX_____ Scale: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

1.8 Results and Data Sets from Pre-Antarctica Testing

1.8.1 Food Quality CNR-IBAF

Overview

This appendix report in a concise and preliminary way, experimental activity performed at IBAF CNR as part of the WP 4.3 pre-mission activity. Common experimental planning and common experiments were performed (and are still under way) among IBAF, WUR and LIT. WUR produced samples that were transferred at IBAF for analysis. Some of these samples have been transferred to LIT for further analysis. IBAF produced samples and some have also been transferred to LIT. This activity will eventually produce scientific papers and is of crucial importance to guide further pre- and post-mission activities. More common activities among CNR, LIT, WUR and DLR are under planning stage, a crucial opportunity will be the test phase of the MTF at the DLR institute in Bremen during summer 2017.

Experiments Performed At IBAF-CNR

Test facilities CNR-IBAF (Porano)

One growth chamber, 140 cm long and 140 cm height and 80 cm width was used to cultivate rocket salad (*Eruca sativa* Mill.) plants at CNR-IBAF. This chamber (Fitotron SGD170 Sanyo Gallenkamp UK) allows the control of all environmental parameters.

Temperature control spans between +7°C and +40°C with all lights on.

CO₂ is measured with IRGA technology (± 1 ppm) and can normally be controlled with a precision of ± 10 ppm after injection from cylinders.

RH can be nominally controlled between 40 and 90% depending on temperature setting with a precision of $\pm 5\%$.

Vertical flux of air is 0.2 m s^{-1} .

The growth chamber was upgraded with two LED (LX60) Heliospectra (HS, BA Goteborg Sweden), similar to the LED lamps designed for the FEG and ISPR. Lamps design was suggested, after careful simulation, by HS, that proposed the use of two lamps with narrow optic and also modelled the optimal position and spacing of the lamps with respect to light intensity and distribution inside the IBAF growth chambers (Figure 1.8; Figure 1.9).

Figure 1.8: Simulation- two lamps with the narrow optic in the CNR IBAF growth chamber.

Figure 1.9: an overview of the IBAF growth chamber upgraded with Heliospectra LED (LX60).

Rocket plants were seeded in two plastic plates of 24 cm x 34 cm x 0.1 cm, each with 224 seats, filled with perlite substrate. Each plate was placed in a container (25 cm x 35 cm x 40 cm) with 8 liters of nutrient solution (Figure 1.10). Plants were cultivated at high final density of 2740 plants per square meter (Picture 2), one rocket seed per seat. Germination took place under 150 $\mu\text{mol quanta m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ photosynthetically photon flux density (PPFD), provided for 12 h per day (12h dark) by cool white LED LX60, 5700 K. The relative humidity and ambient temperature were constant at $70 \pm 5\%$, and $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ respectively. Average CO_2 concentration was 600 ppm as defined on the guideline of EDEN ISS project. The nutrient solution (provided by WUR) was aerated, renewed every week, maintaining pH of 6.5 and EC 1.7 mS cm^{-1} . The effects of three different light spectra treatments and continuous lighting, applied during the growth of *E. sativa* were investigated and measured on plant growth, production and on different quality parameters decided previously by IBAF-CNR and LIT as the “Quality Driving Attributes” (QDAs).

Figure 1.10: *E. sativa* Mill. cultivated in the IBAF growth chamber.

Crop: *Eruca sativa* Mill.

A large number of crops were considered in the EDEN ISS project. CNR-IBAF chose to test the rocket (*E. sativa* Mill.) among the different species indicated by the project because characterised by a fast and uniform germination, fast growth, short size and very appetising taste. Seeds of *E. sativa* cv *coltivata*, was supplied by Semiorto Sementi Salerno Italy (Figure 1.11). The seeds were shared with the project partners for the different experiments.

Figure 1.11: *E. sativa* Mill cultivated by Semiorto Sementi Salerno-Italy.

Growing conditions:

Light

LED light was provided with HS lamps (LX60) with 4 channels and peaks at: 450 nm (blue), 660 nm (red), 735 nm (far-red) and 5700K (white). Each channel was regulated on a relative scale (0-1000) through a computer linked to a router. The photoperiod was simulated by starting the day with a low light intensity and then increasing it. After sowing, the light intensity was set to a maximum of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, and then increased to $300 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ or gradually to $600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, in relation to different photoperiod applied, when the first leaves had been formed. Photoperiod was of 12h/12h day/night and 24h of lighting for the experiment of plant growth under continuous lighting (CN) (Table 1.10). All crops

developed, grew and produced well under $300 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and also $600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ although some differences on production and in relation to the nutritional and quality parameters were detected in rocket plants grown under different light treatments.

Table 1.10: Scheme of light intensity and photoperiod during germination and cultivation.

Time	After sowing ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	After seedling stage until the end of the cultivation in photoperiod of 12h ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Time	After seedling stage until the end of the cultivation in photoperiod of 24h (CL) ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
7:45	Start: sunrise	Start: sunrise	1:00	300
8:00	150	600	12:59:59	300
20:00	150	600		
20:15	sunset	sunset		
20:30	Lamps off	Lamps off		

Light intensity, for each light treatment, were measured at different position inside the growth chamber considering also the crop height and a fine tuning was done, in order to obtain a uniform light distribution above the crop canopy on the growth chamber (Figure 1.12). The three different light treatments are indicated in the table 1.11.

Table 1.11: Scheme of settings of the 3 channels blue, red and white of HS LED lamps.

Photoperiod and PPF value	Treatment	Blu (450nm)	Red (660nm)	FR (730nm)	Cool white 5700K
12h/12h PPFD= $600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	A-12h	15%	71%	2%	12%
24h (CN) PPFD= $300 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	B-CL	0	0	0	100%
24h (CN) PPFD= $300 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	C-CL	27%	73%	0	0

Figure 1.12: *E. sativa* Mill. cultivated under Red-Blue LED.

Plant measurements

CNR and LIT defined the “Quality Driving Attributes” (QDAs), as those compounds that most characterize the nutritional quality of this vegetable, and a list of quality attributes to measure (Table 1.12).

Table 1.12: Qualitative analysis on rocket plants.

Species Cultivar/type	Analysis type	Site of analysis
<i>Eruca sativa</i> Mill. Cultivated	Fresh matter production; Dry Matter; Non-Structural Carbohydrate; Nitrate; Organic acid; Chlorophylls; Total carotenoids; Total polyphenols; Ascorbic acid; Total anthocyanins. Fibre (this is a newly introduced quality QDA)	CNR IBAF
	Total glucosinolates, total nitrogen (and protein), ash.	LIT

Experimental design and statistical analysis

Due to the limitation of the number of LED lamps, we carried out three sets of experiments, each set take in to account one of the light treatment described in the table 1.11. Statistical analysis was performed by ANOVA using the STATISTICA software package (StatSoft for Windows, 1998). Variables were analyzed by One Way ANOVA. When the F test was significant, differences between averages were tested by the LSD test with $P \leq 0,05$.

Growth analysis

Plants were harvested at 30 days after germination, and used for the measurements of plant growth parameters, including shoot fresh weight (FW), root FW, shoot dry weight (DW), root DW, shoot/root (S/R), and specific leaf dry weight (SLDW) and quality attributes quantifications.

A portion of plant tissue samples were dried in a freeze-dried to constant weight for the determination of dry matter percentage (DM%). The quantification of leaf area parameters was measured by a leaf area-meter (LI-3100, LI-COR). The SLDW (dry weight/leaf area) was measured on leaf discs of 1.88 cm² cut from the lamina with a cork borer. A portion of plant harvested was immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80° C for the preservation of different metabolites then used for the measurements of non-structural carbohydrate, total anthocyanins, pigments, total phenolic compounds, ascorbic acid, organic acid and inorganic anions concentration. For the quantification of different phytochemicals, plants were reduced to a fine powder, whit liquid nitrogen, using a mortar and pestle and the powder was preserved at -80°C until analyses. Monomeric components of cell wall polymers were quantified by Ion chromatography after sequential extraction and hydrolysis.

RESULT: Growth analysis

The rocket plants grown under different lighting conditions showed significant differences in growth parameters such as fresh and dry biomass, Harvest Index percentage (HI %), fresh, dry weight and dry matter percentage (SDM%) of shoot and roots. (Table 1.13).

Table 1.13: Total fresh and dry weight of rocket plant from a nominal growth area of 0,0204 m² (1/4 of the tray area). Actual area available is larger due expansion of the plants on toward the sided of the tray, Harvest Index percentage (HI%), fresh and dry weight and dry matter percentage (DM%) of leaves and roots in *E. sativa* Mill. grown under different light treatment.

Light treatment	A-12h	B-CL	C-CL
Total fresh matter (g)	130,71± 8,10 b	189,47 ± 13,63 a	145,70 ± 7,12 b
Total dry matter (g)	8,79 ± 0,18 c	14,73 ± 0,57 a	12,85 ± 0,61 b
HI%	88,11 ± 1,13 b	95,39 ± 2,66 a	86,87 ± 1,49 b
Leaf fresh weight (g)	113,41 ± 5,26 b	170,93 ± 7,07 a	113,89 ± 7,25 b
Leaf dry weight (g)	7,74 ± 0,16 c	13,45 ± 0,56 a	11,17 ± 0,74 b
DM%	6,89 ± 0,39 b	7,81 ± 0,20 b	9,40 ± 0,30 a
SLDW (g/m ²)	43,9 ± 2,2 c	56,19 ± 4,47 b	68,71 ± 4,19 a
Root fresh weight (g)	17,30 ± 3,03 b	18,54 ± 0,51 b	31,81 ± 2,09 a
Root dry weight (g)	1,05 ± 0,11 b	1,28 ± 0,05 b	1,68 ± 0,16 a
DM%	6,25 ± 0,46	6,88 ± 0,09	6,22 ± 0,12
Shoot/Root	7,37 ± 0,72 b	10,51 ± 0,41 a	6,88 ± 0,27 b

Values are expressed as mean ± standard error. Mean values with different letters are statistically different (p -value ≤ 0.05).

At final harvest (30 days after germination), rocket plants, grown under B-CL accumulated significantly more fresh and dry total biomass (shoot + root, in mean for each sector of growth) compared to plants cultivated under C-CL and A-12h light treatments. B-CL light-grown rocket plants showed a value of fresh total biomass of 8% and 11% higher with respect to the plants grown under C-CL and A-12h treatments (Table 1.13). Rocket plants grown with B-CL with 24 h of lighting showed, with respect to the C-CL and A-12h light growth conditions, a lower partitioning of photo-assimilates towards the root system, as described by the lower roots fresh and dry weight and by the higher value of S/R ratio (Tab. 1.13). The HI% value was in agreements of the parameters mentioned above and was significantly higher in plants grown under B-CL with respect to the other light treatments.

The SLDW was significantly higher in plants produced under C-CL light treatment resulting 18% higher with respect to the value obtained in leaves grown under B-CL light treatment and 36% higher compared to the value obtained under the A-12h light growth condition (Table 1.13).

RESULT: Pigments

The pigments measured (chl a; chl b, α- and β-carotens, violaxantin; neoxantin; lutein) in rocket leaves were significantly affected by different growth light conditions (A-12h; B-CL; C-CL. Tab. 1.11) These data showed a large difference among treatments that requires further verification, in particular in relation to stability of carotenoid standards.

RESULT: Evaluation of antioxidant activity, total phenols, total anthocyanins and ascorbic acid:

The antioxidant parameter evaluated in rocket leaves (antioxidant activity, total polyphenols contents, total anthocyanins and ascorbic acid) are reported in the Table 1.14.

Table 1.14: Antioxidant activity (FRAP), Total Polyphenols content (TPC), Total Anthocyanins and Ascorbic acid content in *E. sativa* Mill. leaves grown under different light treatment.

Light Treatment	A-12h	B-CL	C-CL
FRAP ($\mu\text{mol TE} \cdot 100\text{g FW}^{-1}$)	511,06 \pm 8,91 b	527,55 \pm 14,18 b	570,04 \pm 14,56 a
TPC (mg GAE \cdot 100g FW ⁻¹)	122,42 \pm 4,42 b	158,15 \pm 4,48 a	160,95 \pm 3,49 a
Anthocyanins (mg (Cy3GE) \cdot 100g FW ⁻¹)	--	1,21 \pm 0,17 ab	2,18 \pm 0,24 a
Ascorbic acid (mg \cdot 100 g FW ⁻¹)	96,35 \pm 4,73 b	104,39 \pm 1,51 a	99,57 \pm 1,35 ab

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard error. Mean values with different letters are statistically different (p -value \leq 0.05).

All the metabolites related to the antioxidant capacity of *E. sativa* Mill. were significantly affected by different growth light conditions (A-12h; B-CL; C-CL. Tab.1.11).

The antioxidant activity measured by FRAP assay, resulted significantly greater in plants grown under C-CL and this value was higher of about 8% and 11% compared to the antioxidant capacity quantified in B-CL and A-12h respectively (Table 1.14).

The total polyphenols content (TPC), was similar in rocket leaves grown under continuous light (B-CL and C-CL), while it decreased significantly (of about 24%) under A-12h light treatment (Table 1.14).

The anthocyanins assay provided measurable value only in rocket leaves grown under continuous lighting. In particular, the value quantified in plant grown under the C-CL light treatment was approximately twice than those of plant grown under B-CL light treatment. The leaves of A-12h light treatment did not show anthocyanins, in according with the qualitative characteristic of *Eruca sativa* Mill developed under natural environmental growth conditions (Table 1.14).

The highest amount of ascorbic acid in rocket leaves was measured in plants grown under the B-CL light treatment (Table 1.14), with a significant variation of about 8% with respect to the content obtained under A-12h light treatment. The ascorbate content measured in leaves grown with the only Red and Blue LED (C-CL) did not show significant changes compared to the other two treatments (Table 1.14).

RESULT: Non-structural carbohydrate

The different light treatment significantly affected the amount of non-structural carbohydrate measured in rocket leaves and roots.

Table 1.15: Non structural carbohydrate (NSC) content (mg 100 g FW⁻¹) in *E. sativa* Mill. leaves grown under different light treatment.

NSC	Light treatment	Light treatment	Light treatment
	A-12h	B-CL	C-CL
Glucose	375,00 ± 26,49 b	458,93 ± 16,09 a	471,13 ± 18,91 a
Fructose	71,62 ± 6,18 b	94,57 ± 2,95 a	76,06 ± 8,30 b
Sucrose	70,46 ± 3,58 b	78,92 ± 4,19 b	126,88 ± 5,13 a
Starch	394,73 ± 31,73 b	776,78 ± 35,99 a	893,31 ± 53,71 a
Starch / Sucrose	5,66 ± 0,43 b	10,10 ± 0,67 a	7,26 ± 0,61 b
Total Soluble	517,07 ± 32,73 b	632,42 ± 20,46 a	647,07 ± 29,1 a
Total Carbohydrate	911,80 ± 57,05 c	1409,20 ± 44,9 b	1567,37 ± 56,28 a

Values are expressed as mean ± standard error. Mean values with different letters are statistically different (p -value ≤ 0.05).

Rocket leaves grown under continuous lighting (B-CL and C-CL) showed a significantly higher content of soluble (glucose, fructose and sucrose) and total carbohydrate (soluble + starch) compared with the leaves growth under a photoperiod of 12h day/night (A-12h) (Table 1.15).

The soluble carbohydrate were higher in leaves grown under C-CL and statistically similar in leaves grown under B-CL and A-12h (Table 1.15). Total carbohydrate showed the highest amounts in leaves grown under C-CL that decreased respectively of 10% and 42% in leaves grown under B-CL and A-12h (Table 1.15). In particular, under C-CL treatment, rocket leaves accumulated a significant higher amount of glucose, comparable to the leaves grown under B-CL treatment and 20% higher to glucose content of leaves grown under A-12h lighting. Sucrose was 38% higher in C-CL treatment with respect to the sucrose content in leaves of B-CL growth condition and 44% higher with respect to the sucrose content in leaves of A-12h growth condition. Fructose was highest in leaves of B-CL treatment while the leaves grown under C-CL and A-12h showed similar fructose content. Rocket leaves grown under B-CL and C-CL light treatment showed statistically similar amount of starch that was about a half in leaves grown under a photoperiod of 12h day/night (A-12h). The starch/sucrose ratio was statistically higher in rocket leaves grown under B-CL.

In rocket roots, the carbohydrate content was about ten times lower in comparison to the value measured in leaves (Table 1.16).

Table 1.16: Non structural carbohydrate (NSC) content (mg 100 g FW⁻¹) in *E. sativa* Mill. roots grown under different light treatment.

NSC	Light treatment	Light treatment	Light treatment
	A-12h	B-CL	C-CL
Glucose	30,27 ± 2,24 b	72,34 ± 3,75 a	38,84 ± 2,26 b
Fructose	8,94 ± 0,65 ab	11,05 ± 0,52 a	7,51 ± 0,76 b
Sucrose	94,98 ± 3,74 a	82,84 ± 5,38 a	49,56 ± 4,25 b
Starch	9,08 ± 0,90	8,65 ± 0,48	10,57 ± 1,38
Starch / Sucrose	0,10 ± 0,01 b	0,11 ± 0,01 b	0,21 ± 0,01 a
Total Soluble	134,19 ± 6,62 b	166,24 ± 6,49 a	95,92 ± 5,26 c

Total Carbohydrate	143,27 ± 7,36 b	174,90 ± 6,39 a	106,49 ± 6,38 c
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Values are expressed as mean ± standard error. Mean values with different letters are statistically different (p-value ≤ 0.05).

The content of soluble carbohydrate was statistically higher in roots grown under B-CL, it decreased of 19% in A-12h and of 42% in C-CL. Total carbohydrate content was statistically higher in roots grown under B-CL treatment, it decreased of 18% and 39% respectively in A-12h and in C-CL. Glucose, fructose and sucrose were significantly higher in roots of B-CL light-grown plants (Table 1.16). Glucose and fructose measured were statistically similar in roots of plants grown under A-12h and C-CL. Glucose was half in A-12h with respect to the amount measured in roots from B-CL. The amount of sucrose was statistically similar in rocket roots from A-12h e B-CL light treatments, decreasing of about an half in C-CL light conditions. Starch content was statistically similar among the treatments, and the ratio starch/sucrose was significantly higher in C-CL with respect to other treatments (Table 1.16).

RESULT: Organic acid and inorganic anions

Nitrate content was significantly reduced in rocket plants grown under continuous lighting compared to the plants grown with a photoperiod of 12h of lighting (A-12h) (Table 1.17).

Table 1.17: Inorganic anion content (ppm) and organic acid (mg 100 g FW⁻¹) in *E. sativa* Mill. leaves grown under different light treatments.

Inorganic anion (ppm)	Light treatment A-12h	Light treatment B-CL	Light treatment C-CL
Nitrate	4396,86 ± 196,24 a	3582,73 ± 211,33 b	3848,89 ± 135,06 ab
Sulphate	121,17 ± 16,56	99,19 ± 6,23	150,91 ± 11,35
Phosphate	181,26 ± 14,43	276,60 ± 71,52	289,46 ± 69,86
Organic acid (mg 100 g FW ⁻¹)	Light treatment A-12h	Light treatment B-CL	Light treatment C-CL
Malic acid	201,00 ± 5,99 b	278,34 ± 12,63 ab	343,05 ± 15,60 a
Citric acid	17,66 ± 2,59	20,99 ± 0,61	28,32 ± 4,70

Values are expressed as mean ± standard error. Mean values with different letters are statistically different (p-value ≤ 0.05).

The reduction was of 22.7% in relation to the growth under B-CL and of and 12% in relation to the growth under C-CL light treatments. Nitrate measured in these two treatments under continuous lighting are statistically similar. In all cases nitrate content was lower that the legal threshold for consume. Rocket leaves showed also sulphate and phosphate contents, but the values measured was non-statistically different among the plants grown under the light treatments applied. In rocket plants two organic acid were also quantified: malic and citric acid (Table 1.17). The malic acid content measured in rocket leaves of plants cultivated under C-CL and B-CL light treatments light was approximately 1.5 times higher compared to the value obtained in leaves of A-12h. The citric acid amount was slightly higher in rocket leaves under continuous lighting, but the values measured among the plants grown under the three light treatments were not statistically different (Table 1.17).

The content of sugars and of organic acid can affect taste of produce; analytical data will be evaluated in relation to sensory panel quality evaluation results.

Fiber determination from leaves of *Eruca sativa* Mill.

The different light treatment significantly affected the polymeric components of the cell wall in rocket leaves. Cell wall represent the largest pool of organic carbon in plants and consist in different compounds, mainly structural polymers as cellulose, hemicellulose, pectin (polysaccharides) and lignin.

The structural and compositional complexity of these components are important for determining cell wall function during plant growth. Cell wall structure defines a number of functional properties of plant derivate biomass. In particular, pectin has a fundamental role in plant growth, cell-cell adhesion, and fruit development and also it can be considered a dietary fiber that is not hydrolysed by enzymes in the stomach or small intestine, and for this characteristic pectin has multiple positive effects on human health including lowering cholesterol and serum glucose level and reducing some degenerative diseases. 70% of pectin can be accounted by galacturonic acid, the most abundant pectic polysaccharide is a linear homogalacturonan that can have branching linkages with rhamnose, xylose, fructose, galactose, arabinose. This biochemical composition of pectin includes a main chain of alternating galacturonic acid with xylose on the xylogalacturonan and rhamnose on (rhamnogalacturonan I, RGI). In *E. sativa* we have adopted a two-step acid hydrolysis protocol for the simultaneous determination of lignin, cellulose, neutral sugars and uronic acid by high-performance anion exchange chromatography (HPAEC-PAD) (Sluiter et al., 2008; Christiaens et al., 2011). Hemicelluloses are another important sugar polymer of the plant cell wall that has positive effects on the gut microbiome. The main component of hemicellulose is xylose that forma a linear backbone of the polymer and show branching linkages with other monomeric unit such as mannose, galactose, glucose, arabinose and acetic acid.

Chemical composition of the cell wall of *E. sativa* is reported in Table 1.18. Ash showed values significantly different in relation to the light treatments. Extractives were higher in leaves grown under C-CL light treatment. Lignin content was higher on B-CL light treatment. The value of residual humidity (HR%) was similar in leaves grown under continuous lighting (Table 1.18).

Table 1.18: Chemical composition of cell wall of *E.sativa* Mill.

(% DM)	A-12h treatment	B-CL treatment	C-CL treatment
HR %	3,25 ± 0,01 b	4,39 ± 0,14 a	4,55 ± 0,11 a
Ash	16,03 ± 0,06 a	15,25 ± 0,17 b	13,66 ± 0,09 c
Total extractives	33,77 ± 0,21 c	41,32 ± 0,19 b	42,47 ± 0,14 a
Insoluble lignin	5,12 ± 0,26 b	5,95 ± 0,50 a	4,21 ± 0,15 c
Total lignin	5,95 ± 0,20 b	6,18 ± 0,56 a	4,73 ± 0,24 c
Monomer composition of insoluble fibers polysaccharides			
Glucose	28,38 ± 1,73 a	23,03 ± 0,52 b	25,34 ± 0,37 b
Cellulose	25,54 ± 1,56 a	20,73 ± 0,47 b	22,81 ± 0,33 b
Fucose	0,15 ± 0,01 a	0,13 ± 0,01 b	0,12 ± 0,004 b
Arabinose	1,42 ± 0,03 a	1,27 ± 0,02 b	1,27 ± 0,007 b
Galactose	1,58 ± 0,04 a	1,39 ± 0,04 b	1,34 ± 0,019 b
Xylose	1,69 ± 0,10 a	1,10 ± 0,06 b	1,33 ± 0,012 b
Mannose	0,73 ± 0,14 a	0,36 ± 0,04 b	0,70 ± 0,013 a
Rhamnose	0,72 ± 0,03 a	0,54 ± 0,03 b	0,51 ± 0,004 b
Galacturonic acid	10,14 ± 0,37 a	7,64 ± 0,33 b	6,57 ± 0,275 b
Starch	5,26 ± 0,35 b	6,07 ± 0,28 a	5,25 ± 0,32 b

Statistically significant differences were recorded for all component of the cell wall. Lignin content was affected by the light period duration and by the light spectrum in a different way with respect to the sugar components of the cell wall. It was highest in B-CL and lowest on C-CL. All the carbohydrate related polymers were higher in A-12h than in the two 224 h treatments that has similar values. Glucose was the main constituent of cell wall material from *E. sativa*, and it was mainly originated from cellulose. Galacturonic acid was the second most abundant sugar obtained by cell wall polymers hydrolysis. It is the main component of pectin hence it shows that pectin was the second abundant polymer in the cell wall.

Rocket cell wall was altered in relation to growth under different light quality and photoperiod, with different amount of pectic polysaccharides contents. This observation might be very important to define and control the quality of this vegetable food.

Cellulose, lignin, pectin and hemicellulose are all food fibre, but they have different role during human digestion. In recent years, the importance of carbohydrate polysaccharides for gut microbiota proliferation and consequently for human wellbeing is gaining increasing attention. Our results indicate that fibre vegetables component abundance, type, and the effect of environment control on them should be deeply re-evaluated as a crucial component of plant food quality and nutritional value.

1.8.2 Experiments performed at WUR, analysis performed at IBAF-CNR

Experiment 1 Red mustard and Rocket.

Growth experiments were performed at WUR. Iteration for sampling stabilisation, storage, and transfer procedures took place among WUR and IBAF. A first lot of samples were transferred to IBAF at 19/09/2016:

Description of samples:

Freeze dried samples of Rucola cultivated and Red mustard.

Plants were grown in the same climate chamber under 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ and 21/19°C (day/night).

The only difference was the spectrum of the lamps in the PAR region:

	Blue (400-500nm) (%)	Green (500-600 nm) (%)	Red (600-700 nm) (%)
Reference	17	12	72
50% blue	50	12	38

Plant dry weight: from 0.5g to 1 g

Replication: 9 plants of two species for each treatment.

Analytical methods will be described in a separate document.

Antioxidant activity (by FRAP assay), Total Polyphenols Content (TPC), Total Anthocyanins and Ascorbic acid in Red Mustard and Rocket plants growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		FRAP ($\mu\text{mol Trolox} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)	TPC ($\text{mg GAE} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)	Anthocyanins ($\text{mg Cy3GE} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)	Ascorbic acid ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)
Red	17% Blue	64,8 ± 5,87	9,6 ± 0,94	5,34 ± 0,81	-
Mustard	50 % Blue	70,9 ± 2,88	11,0 ± 0,48	4,7 ± 0,96	-
Rocket	17% Blue	54,4 ± 5,93	11,4 ± 1,57	-	8,5 ± 0,99 a
	50 % Blue	61,6 ± 4,29	14,6 ± 1,50	-	5,45 ± 0,71 b

Total anthocyanins concentration was expressed as cyanidin-3-glucoside equivalent values, following the protocol described by Giusti and Wrolstad (2005). Handbook of Food Analytical Chemistry: Pigments, Colorants, Flavors, Texture, and Bioactive Food Components. Wiley & Sons. pp.19-31.

Chlorophylls and Carotenoids contents in Red Mustard and Rocket plants growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		Chl a (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl b (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl a+b (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl a/b	Carotenoids (mg · g DW ⁻¹)
Red Mustard	17% Blue	4,33 ± 0,13	1,64 ± 0,17	5,97 ± 0,26	2,25 ± 0,55	0,99 ± 0,05
	50 % Blue	4,80 ± 0,06	1,85 ± 0,14	6,65 ± 0,17	2,63 ± 0,19	1,05 ± 0,05
Rocket	17% Blue	4,39 ± 0,26	1,85 ± 0,13 b	6,24 ± 0,36	2,39 ± 0,14 a	0,92 ± 0,09 a
	50 % Blue	4,34 ± 0,28	2,69 ± 0,23 a	7,03 ± 0,41	1,65 ± 0,16 b	0,64 ± 0,05 b

Carbohydrate content in Red Mustard and Rocket plants growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

	Blue	Glucose (mg g DW ⁻¹)	Fructose (mg g DW ⁻¹)	Sucrose (mg g DW ⁻¹)	Starch (mg g DW ⁻¹)	Soluble (mg g DW ⁻¹)	Total (mg g DW ⁻¹)
Red Mustard	17%	83,1 ± 5,38 a	18,7 ± 1,99 a	6,5 ± 0,40	12,2 ± 2,4 a	108,23 ± 7,0 a	120,5 ± 8,5 a
	50%	50,0 ± 5,59 b	12,37 ± 2,15 b	6,4 ± 1,78	3,1 ± 1,24 b	68,7 ± 6,57 b	71,8 ± 7,3 b
Rocket	17%	122,4 ± 29,2	39,8 ± 1,36	7,6 ± 1,81	95,1 ± 2,7	169,8 ± 4,22	264,9 ± 5,37
	50%	122,6 ± 10,77	30,0 ± 4,24	7,78 ± 0,43	84,9 ± 1,2	160,4 ± 12,9	245,2 ± 4,19

Anion analysis and organic acid content in Red Mustard and Rocket plants growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		Nitrate (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chloride (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Sulfate (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Malic acid (mg · g DW ⁻¹)
Red Mustard	17% Blue	91,51 ± 8,86 b	11,64 ± 0,179	1,17 ± 0,32	8,39 ± 1,34
	50 % Blue	139,44 ± 6,41 a	12,84 ± 0,213	1,37 ± 0,41	5,55 ± 1,39
Rocket	17% Blue	30,21 ± 2,57 a	8,65 ± 0,45	-	7,33 ± 3,56 b
	50 % Blue	17,93 ± 1,63 b	7,95 ± 1,26	0,48 ± 0,14	21,81 ± 1,66 a

Data were analysed by one-way analysis of variance, considering the species separately and using the percentage of blue light (15% and 50%) as the only factor. Mean values represent four replications (four plants) per treatment. Different letters indicate significant differences of mean values (P=0,05).

Part of the samples were transferred to LIT for further analysis (glucosinolates).

Experiment 2 Lettuce - red romaine.

Growth experiments were performed at WUR. Iteration for sampling stabilisation, storage, and transfer procedures took place among WUR and IBAF. A first lot of samples were transferred to IBAF at 23/01/2017:

Description of samples:

Freeze dried samples of red leaf lettuce: *Lactuca sativa* cv. Outredgeous.

Plants were grown in the same climate chamber under 300 µmol/m²/s and 21/19°C (day/night) and 750 ppm CO₂.

The only difference was the spectrum of the lamps in the PAR region:

Plant dry weight: from 1.2 g to 2.9 g

Replication: 16 plants for each light treatment.

Analytical methods will be described in a separate document.

Antioxidant activity (by FRAP assay), Total Polyphenols Content (TPC), Total Anthocyanins in *Lactuca sativa* cv. Outredgeous growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		FRAP ($\mu\text{mol Trolox} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)	TPC ($\text{mg GAE} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)	Anthocyanins ($\text{mg Cy3GE} \cdot \text{g DW}^{-1}$)
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	17% Blue	501,89 \pm 31,26	84,92 \pm 5,37	3,13 \pm 0,16
cv. Outredgeous	50% Blue	415,43 \pm 43,92	72,39 \pm 11,13	4,80 \pm 0,78

Carbohydrate quantification.

Dry weight and Specific leaf area of *Lactuca sativa* cv. Outredgeous grown under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		DW plant (g)	SLA (m^2/g)
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	17% Blue	2,49 \pm 0,16	0,029 \pm 0,002 b
cv. Outredgeous	50% Blue	2,04 \pm 0,17	0,040 \pm 0,002 a

Carbohydrate content in *Lactuca sativa* cv. Outredgeous growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		Galactose (mg g DW^{-1})	Glucose (mg g DW^{-1})	Fructose (mg g DW^{-1})	Sucrose (mg g DW^{-1})	Starch (mg g DW^{-1})	Glycerol (mg g DW^{-1})
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	17% Blue	0,46 \pm 0,04 a	49,49 \pm 4,09	55,64 \pm 4,76	26,91 \pm 2,39 a	2,17 \pm 0,30 a	5,33 \pm 0,24 a
cv. Outredgeous	50% Blue	0,31 \pm 0,03 b	53,29 \pm 5,53	61,52 \pm 5,92	16,30 \pm 2,25 b	1,28 \pm 0,16 b	3,93 \pm 0,16 b

Soluble and Total Carbohydrate content in *Lactuca sativa* cv. Outredgeous growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.

		Soluble (mg g DW^{-1})	Total (mg g DW^{-1})
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	17% Blue	132,43 \pm 10,26	134,60 \pm 10,13
cv. Outredgeous	50% Blue	131,42 \pm 13,20	132,70 \pm 13,21

Antioxidant components and pigments quantification

Total anthocyanins concentration was expressed as cyanidin-3-glucoside equivalent values, following the protocol described by Giusti and Wrolstad (2005). *Handbook of Food Analytical Chemistry: Pigments, Colorants, Flavors, Texture, and Bioactive Food Components*. Wiley & Sons. pp.19-31.

Chlorophylls and Carotenoids contents in <i>Lactuca sativa</i> cv. Outredgeous growth under 17% or 50% LED Blue light.						
		Chl a (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl b (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl a+b (mg · g DW ⁻¹)	Chl a/b	Carotenoids (mg · g DW ⁻¹)
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	17% Blue	3,29 ± 0,21	1,01 ± 0,18	4,30 ± 0,26	3,15 ± 0,78 b	1,23 ± 0,09 b
cv. Outredgeous	50 % Blue	3,84 ± 0,28	0,61 ± 0,07	4,45 ± 0,23	5,31 ± 0,12 a	1,67 ± 0,12 a

Data was analysed by one-way analysis of variance, considering the percentage of blue light (17% and 50%) as the only factor. Mean values represent six replications (six plants) per treatment. Different letters indicate significant differences of mean values (P=0,05).

CNR-IBAF and WUR will perform data analysis after completion of analytical procedures.

1.8.3 Food Safety CNR-ISA

Conducting food safety and processing experiments in laboratory environment (WP 4.3 - leader). Deliverable D4.3

We decided to use different chromogenic media which, although do not allow us to have fast results, can show, on few plates, the concurrent presence of more genera/species of microorganisms. The media used were the following:

- 1) HICHROME™ Salmonella Agar, Improved (Salmonella Agar HiCrome™, Improved), a selective chromogenic medium used for simultaneous detection of *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* from food and water samples. The medium HiCrome Salmonella media is a modification of the original formulation of Rambach(1) used for the differentiation of *Salmonella* species from other enteric bacteria. The Rambach formulation differentiate *Salmonella* based on propylene glycol utilisation and presence of chromogenic indicator. However, HiCrome Salmonella Agar uses only a chromogenic mixture for identification and differentiation of *Salmonella* species. Peptone special and Yeast extract provides nitrogenous, carbonaceous compounds, vitamins and other essential growth nutrients. Deoxycholate inhibits most Gram-positive organisms. *E. coli* and *Salmonella* are easily distinguishable due to the colony characteristics. *Salmonella* give pink red colonies. *E. coli* has a characteristic blue colour, due to the presence by enzyme β -glucuronidase. Other organisms give colourless colonies. The characteristic light purple colour is due to the chromogenic mixture.

Generally, the results can be the following:

<i>Escherichia coli</i>	colonies blue to purple
<i>Salmonella enteritidis</i>	colonies: pink to red
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	colonies: light pink
<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	colonies: pink to red
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	colonies: light brown

And in general *Salmonella* spp colonies pink to red

- 2) The HICHROME™ rapid Coliforms medium allows for a rapid identification of total coliforms and *Escherichia coli*. The fluorogenic substrate (MUG) is split by the enzyme β -glucuronidase, specially present in *E. coli*.

The presence of total coliforms and *E. coli* is given by a blue green colour; but the colour is persistent for *E. coli* also under observation under UV light.

This is a typical plate made with HICHROME rapid coliforms agar medium. This plate indicates the presence of coliforms and potentially of *E. coli*, but, when we observed it under UV, the plate did not give any fluorescence, indicating the absence of *E. coli*.

- 3) The HICHROME™ Rapid Enterococci medium, which allows rapid identification and differentiation of Enterococci from different samples. The Enterococcus group, a subgroup of the faecal Streptococci serves as bacterial indicator for the determination of faecal contamination. The enzyme b-D glucuronidase present in Enterococci cleaves the chromogenic substrate (X-glu) resulting in blue green colour of colonies. With this medium, *Enterococcus faecalis* gives blue green colonies; *Staphylococcus aureus* gives colourless colonies.

The majority of such chromogenic media can be stored in a range of temperature from 2 to 25°C, thus even considering the possible temperature fluctuations occurring during transport by ship to the Antarctic station, they would not suffer any obvious damage that would not allow them to be used. We performed all the analyses using the conventional equipment present in the lab, which is first the laminar flow hood, and the stomacher. However, for the analyses to be made at the Neumayer III station, the same operation could be performed also simply with a Bunsen close to the working station, which is smaller, and homogenising sample also by stamping the sample within a sterile tube, as previously described. The Bunsen burner could substitute the laminar flow hood. Using the flame of the Bunsen burner close to the top of bottle or flask sterilized and containing the media or physiological solution, a strong contamination can be avoided even in the absence of a laminar flow hood; in fact, the Bunsen burner was used before the diffusion of more modern methods in microbiology. What about the benefits of using chromogenic media? They can be used mainly to avoid using too many plates, when, on a single plate, you can count and discriminate different bacteria. Unfortunately, now there are no so quick test to be realised in the Antarctic station. Since the laboratories that will be used at the Antarctic station do not allow them to work in conditions normally used in a research lab, nor the operator has the biology expertise, use of chromogenic substrates is, at the moment, is the easiest way to check that the vegetables to be eaten are safe. At same time, pressure cooker and a common heating/stirring plate, could substitute, if used in adequate way, the sterilisation through the conventional autoclave, which is sincerely very difficult to transport there. In this case, the temperature and the time of heating will be 270°C and at least 30 minutes, respectively (instead of 121°C and 15 minutes of autoclave). In each case, use of specific tapes (the o called autoclave tapes) can give to the operator the information about the correctness of the sterilisation (indicated by the black of lines onto the tape).

The figure shows a culture broth sterilised by using the pressure cooker, at 270°C for 30 minutes. The black lines of the tape are evident, indicating a correct sterilisation of the broth. Therefore, this broth was prepared 1 month before than the photo and, as you can see, the broth is clear, even if it was stored at room temperature. For a greater safety, when the operator prepares (always at least 1-2 day before all the analysis) the media for the microbial check, he should store plates and broth at 4°C until the moment of the analytical procedures.

The experiments performed both on commercial vegetables (rocket salad, sweet pepper and tomato) and on samples of rocket salad grown under specific conditions in Porano, at the labs of IBAF-CNR. The procedure described below was applied both on commercially vegetables and on vegetables grown at IBAF-CNR in Porano.

1) *Test of vegetables bought at a local market*

Rocket salad (packed), tomato (packed) and sweet pepper (packed) were grown in a local market in Avellino. Vegetables were washed under flow water, gently dried to eliminate water in excess, then divided in three aliquots:

- Control (vegetables that should not be subjected to further treatment)
- Amuchina (vegetables incubated for 10 minutes in a 5% solution of hypochlorite, washed two times under flow water). Note: we used 5% for further security, but it could be used in a domestic way also 2%.
- Sodium bicarbonate (vegetables incubated for 20 minutes in a 20% w/vol sodium bicarbonate, then washed under flow water).

25 grams-samples were put, with 100 ml of deionised water, in Stomacher bags, treated three times in Stomacher (260 rpm, 30" each). Also in this case: generally the ratio between sample and water is 1:10. For a deeper check, we used a ratio 1:4 (w:vol). The supernatant was recovered and used for microbial test.

In the following figure is shown the equipment used for the homogenization of vegetables (A) and, as example, a sample (in this case, cherry tomato, B) which was homogenised

A: The homogenizer «Stomacher» with (on the left) the typical bags used in the ISA CNR lab for the homogenization of samples. Closable bag shows a robust strainer element: this allows for an easy homogenization of solid and liquid (in our case, vegetables and physiological solution), and makes it easier to pipette the liquid portion after the homogenization, and concurrently avoids the mixing with solid waste after homogenization. In **B** is shown the homogenization of cherry tomato. The analyses are performed using the liquid portion of sample, while the solid portion (in this case, for the purposes of the type of analysis, it is considered as waste) remains within the inner bag. Through a pipettor and sterile pipettes (see figure), the liquid is recovered, and stored in sterile tubes at 4°C (or at room temperature, depending on the time between the homogenization and analysis) previously marked

Through the sterile spatula, 100 microliters of liquid (taken through a type Gilson pipette) were spread onto the agar plates. Inoculated plates were put at 37°C for 18-24 hours

Plates containing one of the chromogenic media (in red), inoculated with the samples to be analysed and kept into the incubator at 37°C

The list of media that should be used is in the following table. Comparing the data sheet of the media, the operator could decide in strategic manner, what are the most useful media that he could use to save time. These media are as dried powder. For the preparation of broth (or agar plates) it is possible to follow the instructions provided by the producers. Some of these media can be directly prepared and sterilised; for some of them the sterilisation is damaging, but the operator, reading the instruction, can know it.

HI CHROME EC0157:H7 SELECTIVE AGAR	(can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C)
HI CHROME coliform agar can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
HI CHROME SALMONELLA AGAR, IMPROVED	this should be stored at 4°C, but it can be substituted also with 90918
HI CHROME RAJHANS MEDIUM,	which can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C
VIOLET RED BILE AGAR can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
NUTRIENT BROTH N2 can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
TRYPTONE can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
HI CROME RAPID ENTEROCOCCI AGAR : this medium should be stored at 4°C; thus, to avoid potential damage, we could use another medium: tripticase soy yeast extract (from Sigma with code number Z699195 (Trypticase Soy Broth (TSB) Single strength, Bottled Broth), which can be stored at RT	
HI CROME MAC CONKEY SORBITOL AGAR it should be stored at 4°C, thus we can use HI CROME coliforms agar	
HI CROME BACILLUS AGAR can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
LISTERIA SELECTIVE AGAR can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
BACTERIOLOGICAL AGAR can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
TRYPTONE YEAST EXTRACT AGAR (FOR MICROORGANISM GENERAL) can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
YEAST EXTRACT can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
SLANETZ BARTLEY MEDIUM (FOR THE ENTEROCOCCI) can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
LAB LEMCO AGAR (FOR MICROORGANISM GENERAL) can be stored at temperatures ranging from 2 to 25°C	
Addendum: If the operator would prepare the growth media as broth instead than plate, starting from media containing agar (for example Hi Crome Bacillus agar) he can dissolve the powder with the necessary deionised water and wait for the precipitation of the agar, then proceed with the conventional procedure of sterilization (when not forbidden)	

Results

Rocket salad

In the following figures, we can observe the diverse behaviour (in terms of microbial presence) of samples untreated (control) or treated with hypochlorite or sodium bicarbonate. On the whole, rocket salad and tomato were much more contaminated than sweet pepper.

Untreated rocket salad was really contaminated by coliforms (colonies blue colored). By the observation of plates under UV light, many of the colonies seemed not belonging to the E.coli, because they were not fluorescent (as indicated in the manufacturer instructions). Treatment with “Amuchina” and sodium bicarbonate decreased the number of cfu, although they did not avoid completely the presence of coliforms.

A similar result was observed as regard as the test to detect the presence of total coliforms using another HICHROME media. Compared to the control, we observed a strong decrease of cfu of total coliforms

In this case (medium HiChrome Salmonella agar), high contamination of *Escherichia coli* (colonies blue to purple) and *Proteus vulgaris* (colonies light brown) was evident in the untreated samples. No presence of Salmonella was observed. *E. coli* decreased mainly using hypochlorite in the washing step of the vegetable. Treatments had weaker effect on *Proteus vulgaris*.

Sweet pepper exhibited a different behaviour in terms of microbial contamination, offering fewer chances to bacteria for their proliferation

The test performed to evaluate the presence of coliforms, for example, did not evidenced the presence of such genera of bacteria, in all three types of situations (control, samples treated with hypochlorite, samples treated with sodium bicarbonate). Probably, the different growth situation affected in different way the microbial presence on pepper. All plates were completely free of coliform and/or *E. coli* contamination.

The picture shows (using HiCHROME rapid coliforms media) the potential presence of coliform in the three samples of pepper: control (untreated sample, upper plates), pepper treated with sodium bicarbonate (plates on the middle) and samples treated with hypochlorite (amuchina, plates in the inferior part of figure).

The test, performed using the HiChrome Salmonella test, evidenced contamination with 100 cfu of *Salmonella* spp/25 grams of samples, absence of *Salmonella* in samples treated with sodium bicarbonate and 100 cfu of *Salmonella* spp/25 grams of samples treated with Hypochlorite (Amuchina). This is very important, and, at least for *Salmonella*, treatment with sodium bicarbonate could avoid the presence of this pathogenic genera.

The test performed onto HiChrome Enterococci plates did not show any contamination for each of species suitable to be detected using such medium (*Enterococcus faecalis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*)

Tomato

HiCrom Coliform Agar is a selective chromogenic medium recommended for simultaneous detection of *Escherichia coli* and total coliforms in water and food samples. Sodium lauryl sulfate inhibits Gram-positive organisms. The chromogenic mixture contains two chromogenic substrates, Salmon-GAL and X-glucuronide. Salmon-GAL and X-glucuronide. The enzyme β -D-galactosidase produced by coliforms cleaves Salmon-GAL, resulting in the salmon-to-red coloration of coliform colonies. The enzyme β -D-glucuronidase produced by *E. coli* cleaves X-glucuronide. *E. coli* forms dark blue-to-violet coloured colonies due to cleavage of both Salmon-GAL and X-glucuronide. Using this medium, we observed both total coliforms and *E. coli* in samples of tomato. Even, treatment with sodium bicarbonate did not seem to cause a decreasing of such two microbial population, which, conversely, seemed to increase. In the case of tomato, treatment with hypochlorite gave more comforting results, although the presence of coliforms was unwanted in food (20 cfu in 25 grams of sample)

HiCrome™ Salmonella Agar, Improved (Salmonella Agar HiCrome™, Improved). A selective chromogenic medium used for simultaneous detection of *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli* from food and water samples. HiCrome Salmonella Agar uses only a chromogenic mixture for identification and differentiation of *Salmonella* species. Peptone special and Yeast extract provides nitrogenous, carbonaceous compounds, vitamins and other essential growth nutrients. Deoxycholate inhibits most Gram positive organisms. *E. coli* and *Salmonella* are easily distinguishable due to the colony characteristics. *Salmonella* give pink red colonies. *E. coli* has a characteristic blue colour, due to the presence by enzyme β -glucuronidase. Other organisms give colourless colonies. The characteristic light purple colour is due to the chromogenic mixture. The medium allowed us to detect the presence of *Salmonella* both in the control and in samples treated with sodium bicarbonate. The presence of *E. coli* was also confirmed in these two samples. Treatment with hypochlorite avoid the presence of *E. coli* and *Salmonella*

Using the HiChrome Enterococci medium, we did not observe neither Enterococci nor *Staphylococcus aureus* in all three types of sample (control treated with sodium bicarbonate, treatment with hypochlorite)

2) Test on rocket salad grown in Porano

The second step of the experiments was to test the potential microbial contamination using rocket salad grown at IBAF-CNR Porano.

5 gr-samples were carefully collected in sterile Falcon tubes with glycerol (sterile) 20%. All tubes were kept at -80°C . For the growth conditions of rocket salad see report of IBAF-CNR. All samples were analysed in triplicate at ISA-CNR in Avellino. Samples were put in Stomacher bags in sterile conditions, added with deionised sterile water and processed with Stomacher, two cycles at 260 rpm for 30". The supernatant was collected in sterile falcon tubes and used for the evaluation of microbial charge. The dilution used was 1×10^{-1}

Preparation of media. All media were prepared following the instruction of producer (SIGMA) as previously described and distributed in plates under sterile conditions. Samples were spread onto plates and incubated at $35-37^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24-48 h. in this case, we carried also the experiments to detect the potential presence of *Listeria*, having meanwhile, purchased, the specific medium.

	V1 (SD)	V2 (SD)
<i>Salmonella spp</i>	0 (0)	0
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	65.8 (0.57)	13.15 (0.57)
<i>Total coliforms</i>	0 (0)	0(0)
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	106.5 (1.57)	0 (0)
<i>Listeria</i>	0 (0)	0 (0)
<i>St aureus</i>	71.35 (3.05)	160 (17.3)
<i>E coli</i>	0(0)	0(0)
<i>S.thyphi</i>	0(0)	0 (0)
Total count	402 (4.61)	410 (3.21)
Cfu present in 5 grams of sample from V1 and V2 cassettes		
The experiments were performed in triplicate; the data are expressed as average (\pmStandard Deviation)		

All results indicate that: the products should be treated in double, with sodium hypochlorite and sodium bicarbonate, to avoid at the greatest every potential contamination for the consumers who are there and, in the future, for the people on the ISS. A presumptive way of operating could be:

- Recover vegetables in a clean way
- Weight them
- Wash with current water
- Treat with 5% (v:v respect to water) of hypochlorite for 15 minutes
- Wash repeatedly until the stink of hypochlorite is vanished
- Treat vegetables with sodium bicarbonate as previously indicated
- Wash vegetables
- Proceed with homogenization and the microbial analysis

1.8.4 Food Safety and Quality – LIT

Analysis to date has by LITs CELLS Research Group has focused on developing baseline data for compositional and sensory analysis of all grown plant samples. Optimization of all methods was carried out using shop bought consumer ready produce. While specific species were not known, the confirmation and quantification of the target analytes within the sample was the only requirement at this stage.

Analytical Data is still being compiled for some of the samples and new produce is growing with varying harvest times. This is for both completion of the baseline data for the sensory analysis and for analytical nutritional composition determination.

In addition, selection and operating method validation of the hand-held meters for the qualitative analysis of produce grown in the MTF on Antarctica was completed.

1.8.4.1 Confirmed Standard Operating Procedures for Hand-Held Tools for MTF.

A number of hand held meters for the analysis of nutritional composition within the plants grown in the MTF have been tested and confirmation of procedures as they will be used by the Neumeyer III Station crew is complete. In addition to the hand-held devices, a number of instruments will be used for the preparation of samples for storage prior to shipping back to the home laboratories. For work package 4.3, two means of storage will be utilized, mainly short-term storage and long-term storage, and this will be discussed in greater detail in section 1.8.4.5. However, for the purposes of the standard operating procedures manual, SOP 004 and SOP 005 (to be included in the next draft of this document) are included in this section. SOP 007 to 011 refer to the use of the hand-held meters discussed above, It is important to note that the Hanna Instruments Nitrate Ion Meter, while included here (SOP 011), will not be sent to the MTF due to the hazardous nature of the standards, reagents and waste materials generated when analysis of the plant tissue is complete. A new Nitrate meter which directly reads NO₃⁻ with very little sample preparation is currently being tested for use in the MTF and the SOP for this meter will be included in the next version of this document.

The original instrument manuals will also be made available to the crew of Neumeyer III Station for troubleshooting purposes with the instrument if required. However, as these instruments are quite rugged and versatile, we do not expect many difficulties with them for the duration of the stay on Antarctica.

The packing list including all the hand-held meters and spares can be found in Appendix 18.4.7.

SOP 004 - Freezer-drier Operation

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 004	Revision Number: 2.0	
	Equipment Model: FreeZone® 6 Liter Benchtop Freeze Dry System (77520 Series)	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages: 7	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document creation Establishment of procedure
2.0	29 th May 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of Control Record Procedure update

Purpose:

Lyophilisation of plant material for bioactive analysis.

Scope:

Freeze drying is an important process in sample preparation and for the preservation and storage of biologicals, pharmaceuticals and foods. Of the various methods of dehydration, freeze drying (lyophilisation) is especially suited for substances that are heat sensitive. Lyophilisation is a process whereby water, or another solvent, is removed from frozen material by converting the frozen water directly into vapour without the intermediate formation of liquid water. The basis for this sublimation process involves the absorption of heat by the frozen sample in order to vaporise the ice, the use of a vacuum pump to enhance the removal of water vapour from the surface of the sample, the transfer of water vapour to a collector, and the removal of heat by the collector in order to condense the water vapour. In essence, the lyophilisation process is a balance between the heat absorbed by the sample to vaporise the ice and the heat removed from the collector to convert the water vapour into ice.

Environmental Health and Safety:

Electrical Requirement

The Freeze Dryer requires a dedicated electrical outlet. An outlet equipped with a 15 Amp circuit breaker or fuse is required for models rated at 230V (50/60 Hz).

Vacuum Pump Requirement

A vacuum pump with a displacement of 144 liters per minute and 0.002 mBar ultimate pressure is adequate for most samples. The inlet fitting on the vacuum pump must be suitable for 3/4" ID vacuum hose and is provided. Vacuum pumps used with 230V models should be equipped with a reverse IEC plug. This plug is included with 230V models. This will allow the vacuum pump to be plugged into the receptacle on the back panel of the freeze dryer.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

User's Manual: FreeZone® 6 Liter Benchtop Freeze Dry System (77520 Series) attached.

Set-up:

Refer to *Chapter 3: Getting Started* of the User's Manual for information on Vacuum Pump connection, electrical connection, and drying manifold installation.

Sample Preparation:

Harvested tissue samples of select weight and quantity should be placed in labelled, sealable aluminium foil bags and stored at -80 °C until ready for lyophilisation. The fresh-weight of the bag containing the sample should be recorded before freezing.

Pictorial View of Freeze Drier Control Panel:

Freeze-drier Controls:

parameters, set-up parameters and alarm messages.

2. **Menu Switch** – This switch is used to change the display from operating system parameters to set-up parameters.
3. **Select Switch** – Used to select set-up parameters.
4. **Vacuum Switch** – Used to start or stop the vacuum pump when operating in manual start-up mode.
5. **Vacuum Indicator** – This green LED indicates that power is being supplied to the vacuum pump receptacle on the back of the Freeze Dryer.
6. **Manual Refrigeration Switch** – Used to start only the refrigeration module.
7. **Manual Operation Indicator** – When lit, the green LED indicates the Freeze Dryer is being controlled manually by the operator. The operator must start each function.
8. **Auto Mode Switch** – Used to start or stop the refrigeration and the Auto Mode process.
9. **Auto Mode Indicator** – When lit, the green LED indicates that the Freeze Dryer is in Auto Mode. In this mode, the vacuum pump will start when the collector temperature reaches -40°C .
10. **Vacuum Graph Display** – This display indicates the relative system vacuum level. The highest LED indicates that the vacuum level is above 2.0 mBar. The indicators will sequence down when the vacuum level reaches 2.0, 1.0, 0.8, 0.6, 0.45, 0.12 mBar. The lower green LED flashes when the system vacuum level is 0.45 to 0.12 mBar and illuminates steadily below 0.133 mBar.
11. **Collector Temperature Graph Display** – This display indicates the temperature of the collector. The highest LED indicates the collector temperature is warmer than 10°C . The indicators will sequence

down when the temperature reaches 10, 0, -10, -20, -30, -40°C. When the collector temperature is – 40°C or lower the green indicator will light.

12. **Alarm Indicator** – This red LED indicates that a system alarm has occurred. Press the Menu Switch to display the alarm message on the LCD display.
13. **Main Power Switch** – Turns the Freeze Dryer on or off. (Not shown, located on the left side of the cabinet.)

Instrument Initialisation:

1. Ensure the dryer manifold and collector are dry. Remove any moisture before continuing with operation
2. Turn ON the **Main Power Switch** – located on the left side of the cabinet.
3. Place the drying manifold on top of the collector, ensuring the rubber seals are aligned.
4. Press the **Manual Refrigeration Switch**. The freezer dryer will begin cooling to -50C.

Sample Addition and Drying:

1. Once the **Collector Temperature Graph Display** indicates that the temperature has adequately reduced place the samples (in an appropriate partially sealed sample bag), upright where possible, into the drying manifold.
2. Place the lid onto the drying manifold, ensuring it is secure, close the valve.
3. Press the **Auto Mode Switch**. This will switch off the manual function.
4. Press the **Auto Mode Switch** a second time to initiate the vacuum.
5. Monitor the **Vacuum Graph Display** until the lower green LED light is steadily illuminated.
6. Once the **Collector Temperature Graph Display** and **Vacuum Graph Display** both have the lower green LED lights steadily illuminating, the sample have begun lyophilising.

Sample Removal:

1. Once the samples have been adequately dried for between 24 and 36 hours, depending on the tissue quantity, press the **Auto Mode Switch** to turn off the vacuum.

2. Relieve the vacuum by opening the drying manifold valve slightly and very gently. **NOTE:** Opening the valve too quickly or completely at first will cause the vacuum to be released too soon resulting the samples being destroyed or ejected from the sample bags.
3. **Optional:** The collector drain hose, located on the right side of the cabinet, may also be opened to speed up dissipation of the vacuum in the system. However, this should only be done after the manifold valve has been slightly opened.
4. Once the vacuum has completely dissipated, as indicated by the **Vacuum Graph Display**, the drying manifold can be carefully taken off the drying chamber using an upwards motion.
5. The samples can now be removed and the sample bags fully sealed shut.
6. The sample bags can then be stored at room temperature until analysed, if available the samples can also be stored at 4°C.

Instrument Shut-off:

1. Defrost the ice build-up inside the drying chamber by either exposing the chamber to ambient temperatures and allow to melt naturally, or by adding warm water to aid the process.
2. Open the hose on the right of the chamber to drain the waste water.
3. Once drained reseal the hose and dry the inside of the chamber with some paper towels or a cloth.
4. The **Main Power Switch** can then be switched to the OFF position.

Troubleshooting:

Refer to *Chapter 7: Troubleshooting* of the User's Manual if you are experiencing problems with the Freeze Dryer.

SOP 007 - Refractometer Operation

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 007	Revision Number: 2.0	
	Equipment Model: HANNA HI 96801 Refractometer	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages: 7	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document creation • Establishment of procedure
2.0	29 th May 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of Control Record • Procedure update

Purpose:

Measurement of refractive index to determine the % Brix of sugar in aqueous solutions.

Scope:

The Brix determination is made by measuring the refractive index of a solution. Refractive Index is an optical characteristic of a substance and the number of dissolved particles in it. Refractive Index is defined as the ratio of the speed of light in empty space to the speed of light in the substance. A result of this property is that light will “bend”, or change direction, when it travels through a substance of different refractive index. This is called refraction.

In the HI 96801, light from an LED passes through a prism in contact with the sample. An image sensor determines the critical angle at which the light is no longer refracted through the sample. The HI 96801 automatically applies temperature compensation to the measurement and converts the refractive index of the sample to sucrose concentration in units of percent (by weight) Brix.

Environmental Health and Safety:

There are no significant hazards or special instructions relating to the procedures outlined in this SOP that need to be detailed.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

Instruction Manual: HI 96801 Refractometer for Sucrose Measurements attached.

Instrument Overview:

TOP VIEW

14. **LCD Display**

15. **Secondary Display**

16. **Primary Display**

17. **READ Key** – User measurement.

18. **ZERO Key** – User calibration.

19. **ON/OFF**20. **Stainless steel sample well and prism**

DISPLAY ELEMENTS

1. **Battery** (blinks when low battery condition detected)
2. **Primary Display** (displays measurement and error messages)
3. **Measurement in Progress Tag**
4. **SETUP:** Factory Calibration Tag
5. **CAL:** Calibration Tag
6. **Measurement Unit**
7. **Automatic Temperature Compensation** (blinks when temperature exceeds 10-40 °C range)
8. **Temperature Units**
9. **Secondary Display** (displays temperature measurements; when blinking, temperature has exceeded operation range: 0-80 °C)

Calibration Procedure:

Calibration should be performed daily, before measurements are made, when the battery has been replaced, between a long series of measurements, or if environmental changes have occurred since the last calibration.

1. Press the **ON/OFF** key, then release. Two instrument test screens will be displayed briefly; all LCD segments followed by the percentage of remaining battery life. When LCD displays dashes, the instrument is ready.

2. Using a plastic pipette, fill the sample well with distilled or deionized water. Make sure the prism is completely covered.
 - a. **Note:** If the ZERO sample is subject to intense light such as sunlight or another strong source, cover the sample well with your hand or other shade during the calibration.
3. Press the **ZERO** key. If no error messages appear, your unit is calibrated. (For a description of ERROR MESSAGES see page 11 of the Instruction Manual).
 - a. **Note:** The 0.0 screen will remain until a sample is measured or the power is turned off.
4. Gently absorb the ZERO water standard with a soft tissue. Use care not to scratch the prism surface. Dry the surface completely. The instrument is ready for sample measurement.
 - a. **Note:** If the instrument is turned off the calibration will not be lost.

Solid Sample Preparation:

1. Place approximately 2g of sample in garlic press and squeeze juice out.

Note: In the case of pepper, place approximately 2g leaf in garlic press and squeeze juice out.

Measurement Procedure:

Verify the instrument has been calibrated before taking measurements.

1. Wipe off prism surface located at the bottom of the sample well.
2. Using a plastic pipette, drip sample onto the prism surface. Fill the well completely.
 - a. **Note:** If the temperature of the sample differs significantly from the temperature of the instrument, wait approximately 1 minute to allow thermal equilibration.
3. Press the **READ** key. The result is displayed in units of % BRIX.
 - a. The last measurement value will be displayed until the next sample is measured or the instrument is turned off. Temperature will be continuously updated.
 - b. **Note:** The ATC tag blinks and automatic temperature compensation is disabled if the temperature exceeds the 10-40 °C range.
4. Remove sample from the sample well by absorbing with a soft tissue.
5. Using a plastic pipette, rinse prism and sample well with distilled or deionized water. Wipe dry. The instrument is ready for the next sample.

Making a Standard %BRIX Solution:

1. Place container (such as a glass vial or dropper bottle that has a cover) on an analytical balance.
2. Tare (zero) the balance using the T/Z button.
3. To make a known %BRIX solution weigh out a known amount in grams of high purity Sucrose (CAS #: 57-50-1) directly into the container.
4. Add distilled or deionized water to the container so the total weight of the solution is 100g.

Note: Solutions above 60 %Brix need to be vigorously stirred or shaken and heated in a water bath. Remove solution from bath when sucrose has dissolved. The total quantity can be scaled proportionally for smaller containers but accuracy may be sacrificed.

Example with 25 %Brix:

%Brix	g Sucrose	g Water	g Total
25	25.000	75.000	100.000

Troubleshooting:

Refer to page 11 of the *Instruction Manual* if you are experiencing problems with the refractometer.

Pictorial Demonstration:

Figure 1.8.4.1 Illustrates liquid standard or sample application to the Refractometer.

Figure 1.8.4.2 Calibrating the Refractometer.

Figure 1.8.4.3 Taking measurement of sample.

Expected %Brix Value / 2g FW of produce sample:

Produce	Avg %Brix
Rocket	4.57
Lettuce	1.47
Pepper (Green) (3gFW)	4.63
Pepper (Red) (3gFW)	4.83
Salad Tomato	4
Small Cherry	7.6
large Cherry	5.8

SOP 008 - Penetrometer

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 008	Revision Number: 2.0	
	Equipment Model: PCE Instruments Force Gauge PCE-FM 200	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages: 4	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document creation • Establishment of procedure
2.0	2 nd June 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of Control Record • Procedure update

Purpose and Scope:

Indicative measurement of fruit firmness for ripening.

Environmental Health and Safety:

There are no significant hazards or special instructions relating to the procedures outlined in this SOP that need to be detailed.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

PCE Instruments Manual: Force Gauge PCE-FM 200 as attached.

Instrument Overview:

3-1: Universal sensing head

3-2: LCD display

3-3: Fast indicator

3-4: FAST/SLOW button

3-5: LCD reverse display button

3-6: Zero button

3-7: g/oz/N unit switch

3-8: Power Off/On/Peak Hold

3-9: Mounting holes

3-10: Battery cover

3-11: Flat-head adapter

3-12: Cone adapter

3-13: Chisel adapter

3-14: Hook adapter (Not Applicable)

3-15: 120 mm extension rod

3-16: LCD back light button

3-17: DC 9V power adapter

3-18: RS-232 output

Sample Preparation:

No sample preparation is necessary as the instrument can be used directly on the fruit *in situ*.

Measurement Procedure:

1. Slide the **Power Off/On/Peak Hold button** to the “On” position.
 - a. 0 = Off, 1 = On
2. Select the measurement by pressing the **g/oz/N Unit Switch**.
3. Attach the cone adapter provided for measurement of tomato, bell pepper cucumber, and strawberry.
4. The compression measuring function is executed automatically.
5. The object being measure should be directly in line with the sensing head.
6. Zero the instrument by pressing the **Zero Button**.
7. Start the measurement by applying force (pushing the sensing adapter to the sample). The LCD display will display the average value
 - a. Note: the LCD display orientation can be reversed during measurement by pressing the **Reverse Button**.

Troubleshooting:

Refer to the *Instruction Manual* if you are experiencing problems with the penetrometer.

Pictorial Demonstration:

Figure 1.8.4.4 Taking measurement of sample.

Note: Use the cone attachment only for measurement of fruit / vegetable. Ensure that the motion used is constant and that the action is terminated end of the cone portion of the probe has been inserted into the sample.

firmness.
once the

Expected Values in g/oz/N for Produce Samples:

Produce	Avg g/oz/N	Std Dev	95% CI
Baby Vine Tomatoes, N=12 x 2 reps	0.74	0.12	0.002
Baby Vine Plum Tomatoes, N=14 x 2 reps	0.89	0.07	0.001
Large Vine Tomatoes, N=5 x 3 reps	1.15	0.12	0.003
Salad Tomatoes, N=4 x 3 reps	1.82	0.05	0.001
Green Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	2.18	0.25	0.009
Yellow Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	2.02	0.05	0.002
Red Bell Pepper, N=3 x 4 reps	1.56	0.10	0.004
Cucumber, N=3 x 6 reps	2.17	0.08	0.003
Strawberries, N=18 x 2 reps	0.24	0.05	0.001

SOP 009 - Colourimeter Operation

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 009	Revision Number: 2.1	
	Equipment Model: PCE Instruments Colourimeter PCE-CSM 1	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages: 12	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document creation • Establishment of procedure
2.0	29 th May 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of Control Record • Procedure update

Purpose:

Measurement the colour co-ordinates of food samples.

Scope:

To use the colour of the food sample as an indication of the bioactive content.

The CIE system coordinates (L*, a*, b*) are commonly used in the food industry. Using the colorimeter these coordinates were directly read.

The parameter a* takes positive values for reddish colours and negative values for the greenish ones, whereas b* takes positive values for yellowish colours and negative values for the bluish ones. L* is an approximate measurement of luminosity.

Note: This instrument can only be used on larger fruits and vegetables such as tomatoes (including baby tomatoes), bell pepper, cucumber and larger strawberries.

Environmental Health and Safety:

There are no significant hazards or special instructions relating to the procedures outlined in this SOP that need to be detailed.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

Instruction Manual: Colourimeter PCE-CSM 1, PCE-CSM 2, and PCE-CSM 4 as attached.

Instrument Overview:

1. On/Off button
2. Up button ↑
3. Down button ↓
4. Menu button ☰

5. Back button ↶
6. Enter button ↵
7. Testing button

- Mains adaptor: Only use the mains adaptor included in the package. If it breaks down, only use substitutions with the following characteristics: output 5 V DC, 2 A.
- USB interface: By using the USB interface, you can transfer data from the colorimeter to a PC. The baud rate is 115,200 bps.

Sample Preparation:

No sample preparation is necessary as the instrument can be used directly on the coloured fruit / vegetable *in situ*.

Calibration Procedure:

To get to the calibration menu, press the Menu button \equiv , select "Calibrate" and press Enter \leftarrow . Here you can select between white and black calibration. Use the arrow keys (\uparrow and \downarrow) to select and press Enter \leftarrow to confirm. A confirmation display with instructions will appear.

Note: A calibration is only reasonable in the following cases: when first using the device, after strong changes in the environmental conditions, when the device has not been used for a significant period of time or when the measurement results are inaccurate.

White calibration (recommended for all fruit and vegetable analysis)

White calibration is used to confirm luminosity intensity. To carry out a white calibration, turn the device upside down and place the white calibration plate (white paper provided) on the measuring aperture. After that, press the Testing button to start the calibration.

Black calibration

As per the white calibration, black calibration is used to confirm deep colour intensity. To carry out a black calibration, remove the calibration plate and place the device with the measuring aperture oriented upwards. Make sure that this calibration is carried out in a dark environment. Additionally, keep the device away at least 1 meter from reflecting objects like walls, tables or other objects. To start the calibration process, press the Testing button.

Measurement Procedure:

Turn on the device

Make sure the battery is installed or the device is connected to an external power source. Turn on the device by switching the On/Off button to “1”. After a few seconds, you are automatically directed to the “Standard Measurement” screen. The default setting for this measuring mode is L*a*b*C*H.

Taking a standard measurement:

- The standard measurement allows for clear identification of strong red, yellow and green colours. This can then be used to determine colour change in fruits and vegetables as they grow. Standard colour measurements are provided below for comparison purposes.
- Turn on the device and remove the black cap, the “Standard Measurement” screen appears. To take a measurement, follow these steps:
 1. Press and hold the testing button – located on the back panel of the device. Four (4) light cones appear to aid with selecting the measuring point.
 2. Move the device as close to the measuring point as possible.
 3. Release the testing button. The colorimeter now takes a measurement.
- After the measuring process has finished, you can see the results in the following display:

Taking a sample measurement

1. When in the result screen of a standard measurement, press the Enter button . The “Sample Measurement” display appears.
2. Take another measurement (same process as the standard measurement).
3. The deviation of the sample will appear in a display similar to the below:

Note: A '+' symbol appears on the colour gradient scale indicating the measurement is in progress (time duration: ~ 1 second), all buttons are inactive.

To go back to the "Standard Measurement" display, press the Back button ↶.

Averaging:

You can set the number of measurements which are performed during the measuring procedure. From these particular measurement results, the average value is generated.

To get to the averaging settings, press the Menu button ≡, select "Average" and press Enter ↵. Here, you can set the number of measurements. Use the arrow keys to select a number. Press Enter to get to the next digit. After confirming the last digit by pressing Enter ↵, the averaging is set.

Note: If you set "00" or "01", there will be no averaging.

Record Data:

All measuring results are recorded and saved to the internal memory of the colorimeter. To view the recorded data, press the Menu button ≡, select "Record" and press Enter ↵ to confirm. Now, you get to the following display:

Here, you can navigate between the individual measurements by using the arrow keys (↑ and ↓).

- If you have one or more sample measurements, you can view those by pressing Enter ↵. You can navigate through the sample measurements by using the arrow keys (↑ and ↓). If you want to delete a sample measurement, select it and press and hold the Back button, until a confirmation display appears. Now, press Enter ↵ to delete the sample or press Back to cancel. By pressing Back ↵ again, you can go back to the standard record display.
- If you want to add sample measurements to a standard measurement subsequently, select the standard measurement and press the Menu button ≡. Now, you are in the measurement display. Press Enter ↵ to get to the sample measurement display. Now you can take sample measurements which are added to the selected standard measurement.
- If you want to turn a sample measurement into a standard, select the sample measurement as described above and press the Menu button ≡. The device switches to the standard measurement screen and the sample becomes a standard.

Note: it is advisable to record all data as measurements are taken in case of memory failure of instrument.

Troubleshooting and Safety:

Refer to the *Instruction Manual* if you are experiencing problems with the colourimeter.

Standard Measurement Data (For Comparison Purposes):

The table below provides a range of values attributed to definitive Red, Yellow and Green fruits and vegetables. The fruits used as standard were shop bought and ready for consumption. In the colour palette below, figures (a) to (g) illustrate the varying colours of each sample tested, with bell peppers used as the standard red, yellow and green measurement.

Index of colour palette:

- | | |
|---------------------------------------|----------------------------|
| (a) Yellow, Red and Green bell pepper | (b) Strawberry |
| (c) Vine Baby Tomatoe | (d) Vine Baby Plum Tomatoe |
| (e) Cucumber | (f) Salad Tomatoe |
| (g) Vine Tomatoe | |

Example of typical white background values:

L* = 78.89 a* = 1.96 b* = -2.30

Sample type	N	L*	a*	b*	Bla ⁺⁺	Red ⁺	Yel ⁺	ΔE*
Yellow bell pepper	1	81.42	1.99	-2.59	-27.83	7.11	54.77	61.84
	2	70.5	1.88	-2.11	-16.58	9.65	53.58	56.91
	3	75.89	2.04	-2.35	-20.33	7.10	49.37	53.98
Green bell pepper	1	71.9	1.82	-2.12	-45.73	-13.69	19.59	51.60
	2	74.36	1.96	-2.37	-38.79	-14.02	28.03	49.87
	3	78.89	1.96	-2.30	-45.00	-12.90	24.19	52.69
Red bell pepper	1	76.18	2.03	-2.37	-49.88	33.22	19.43	63.00
	2	82.62	2.02	-2.37	-47.73	30.86	18.54	59.79
	3	77.97	2.02	-2.37	-47.21	31.11	18.10	59.37
Salad tomatoes (light red)	1	76.35	2.07	-2.52	-33.65	19.25	24.79	46.01
	2	78.57	1.98	-2.35	-42.23	25.62	28.38	56.97
	3	78.62	1.98	-2.35	-41.70	27.15	31.95	59.14
Large vine tomatoes (dark red)	1	56.22	1.73	-1.40	-23.40	27.51	24.05	43.39
	2	82.33	2.02	-2.69	-47.93	27.21	27.44	61.57
	3	73.38	1.90	-2.26	-45.80	25.85	23.00	57.40
Plum baby tomatoes (dark red)	1	71.19	1.85	-2.07	-38.61	26.10	18.99	50.32
	2	80.35	1.97	-2.44	-52.30	23.20	17.71	59.90
	3	82.39	2.02	-2.57	-55.24	22.94	17.74	62.39
Cherry tomatoes (dark red)	1	79.32	1.98	-2.30	-48.54	23.64	18.84	57.18
	2	79.09	2.00	-2.32	-47.23	23.17	18.09	55.56
	3	66.50	2.02	-1.74	-31.70	24.94	18.58	44.40
Cucumber (measured in the middle)	1	85.27	1.95	-2.57	-49.95	-12.12	25.67	57.45
	2	84.35	1.97	-2.58	-45.10	-11.41	29.50	55.09
	3	81.38	2.00	-2.55	-43.58	-12.30	28.77	53.65
Strawberries	1	82.02	2.02	-2.62	-42.56	36.93	27.22	62.57
	2	86.07	1.90	-2.46	-50.20	38.38	30.39	70.11
	3	81.39	2.00	-2.45	-44.42	36.61	31.33	65.54

Pictorial Demonstration:

Figure 1.8.4.5 Taking measurement of sample.

Note: Ensure that the four light cones align within the black circle of the sensor head. This will become evident as the sensor is lowered to the sample to be analyzed. The sensor does not touch the sample but is just held above.

Figure 1.8.2.6 Colour Palette:

(g)

SOP 010 - Chlorophyll Meter

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 010	Revision Number: 2.1	
	Equipment Model: MINOLTA Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages: 4	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document creation Establishment of procedure
2.0	29 th May 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of Control Record Procedure update
2.1	2 nd June 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inserted page numbers

Purpose:

Measurement of chlorophyll content in plant leaves.

Scope:

The amount of chlorophyll present in plant leaves can serve as an indicator of the overall condition of plant health. In general, healthier plants contain more chlorophyll than less healthy plants.

The SPAD value determined by the SPAD-502 provides an indication of the relative amount of chlorophyll present in plant leaves. This SPAD value can be used to determine when and if additional nutrients are required.

Environmental Health and Safety:

There are no significant hazards or special instructions relating to the procedures outlined in this SOP that need to be detailed.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

Instruction Manual: Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502 attached.

Instrument Overview:

Sample Preparation:

No preparation is necessary as the Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502 can be used on plant leaves directly *in situ*.

Calibration Procedure:

Calibration is necessary whenever the meter is switched on after having been switched off.

1. Turn the power switch to ON.
2. When the word "Calibration" appears on the screen press close and hold the measuring head until a beep sounds and the following screen appears.

3. Calibration is now complete.
4. If a series of beeps sound and "Error" appears in the display, calibration was not performed correctly. Repeat Step 1 and 2.
5. If a series of beeps sound and "Error" and "E-U" appear in the display, then the measuring head may be dirty. Clean the windows and repeat steps 1 and 2.

Measurement Procedure:

1. Perform Calibration.
2. Insert the plant sample to be measured into the sample slot of the measuring head. Ensure the sample

completely covers the receiving window.

3. Press and close the measuring head. Hold until a beep sounds. The measurement will appear on the display and will automatically be stored in the memory.
 - a. **Note:** Do not take measurements in direct sunlight.
4. If a series of beeps sound and error is displayed on the screen measuring was not performed correctly. This may be due to the sample being too thick, the measuring head not being closed tightly enough or opened too soon. Repeat steps 2, 3 and 4.
5. If a series of beeps sounds and the word Calibration appears on the screen, then the temperature has changed by more than 10°C since calibration and needs recalibrating. Stored data will be deleted.

Troubleshooting and Storage:

Refer to pages 16 and 17, respectively, of the *Instruction Manual* for troubleshooting and care instructions.

Pictorial Demonstration:

Figure 1.8.4.7 Taking measurement of sample.

Figure 1.8.4.8 Examples of other leafy vegetables analyzed by Chlorophyll meter. (a) Lettuce *lollo rosso*; (b) chives; (c) parsley

Expected SPAD Chlorophyll values for produce sampled at multiple locations:

Produce	Avg Reading	Std Dev	95% CI
Red Lettuce (Outrageous) Inner Green Leaf N=12	5.98	1.99	0.04
Red Lettuce (Outrageous) Outer Red Leaf N=12	29.33	7.25	0.13
Butterleaf Lettuce (Red Variety) Inner Green Leaf, N=10	3.79	2.50	0.05
Butterleaf Lettuce (Red Variety) Outer Red Leaf, N=10	36.08	10.52	0.21
Chives (leaf Bottom), N=6	34.13	8.77	0.22
Chives (leaf Middle), N=6	39.48	9.86	0.25
Chives (leaf Top), N=6	31.18	8.55	0.11
Parsley (Leaf), N=7	29.80	19.22	0.46
Parsley (Top of Stalk), N=7	15.43	7.79	0.18
Parsley (Bottom of Stalk), N=7	11.36	4.86	0.05

SOP 011 - Nitrate Ion Meter

	Identification Number: S.O.P. 011	Revision Number: 2.0	
	Equipment Model: Horiba LAQUA Nitrate NO ₃ ⁻ Meter (B-743)	Serial Number:	
	Document Owner: Limerick Institute of Technology/EDEN-ISS		
	Document Status: Approved	No. of Pages:	Language: English
	Document Type: Standard Operating Procedure (Internal)	Contact/Creator: Ms. Michelle McKeon-Bennett	

Revision History

Revision No.	Date	Comments
1.0	25 th April 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document creation Establishment of procedure
2.0	29 th May 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Addition of Control Record Procedure update
3.0	26 th June 2017	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Original Meter Replaced by Make & Model included in SOP, due to testing finding it not fit-for-purpose.

Purpose:

Measurement of nitrate levels in plant sample as an indication of anti-nutritional capacity.

Scope:

The amount of Nitrate ion (NO₃⁻) in a food sample is determined via colorimetric analysis.

Environmental Health and Safety:

There are no significant hazards or special instructions relating to the procedures outlined in this SOP that need to be detailed.

Personnel Requirement

Use routine laboratory Personnel Protective Equipment.

Related documents:

Instruction Manual: Horiba LAQUA Nitrate NO₃⁻ Meter (B-743).

Instrument Overview:

- | | |
|----------------------|-----------------------------|
| 1 Flat sensor | 9 MEAS icon |
| 2 Light shield cover | 10 CAL icon |
| 3 Lithium batteries | 11 Battery alarm icon |
| 4 MEAS switch | 12 Temperature alarm icon |
| 5 ON/OFF switch | 13 Stability icon |
| 6 CAL switch | 14 Measured value display |
| 7 Waterproof gasket | 15 Measurement unit display |
| 8 Strap eyelet | |
| A Liquid Junction | B Response membrane |

Power On/Off:

Power ON

1. Press and hold the ON/OFF switch for over 2 seconds.
2. The power is turned ON, and the meter model number is displayed on the LCD.

Power OFF

1. Press and hold the ON/OFF switch for over 2 seconds.
2. The power is turned OFF.

Just press to enter GLP mode. In calibration mode press to edit the date and time.

Sensor Replacement:**Sensor Attachment**

1. Confirm that the waterproofing gasket is clean and undamaged.
2. Slide the sensor onto the meter so that catch "A" on the back of the meter fits into hole "a" on the sensor tongue as displayed below.

Note: Be careful not to twist the waterproof gasket.

Sensor Removal:

1. Lift the sensor tongue tip and slide the sensor a little away from the meter.

2. Pull out the sensor all the way from the meter.
3. When removing the sensor, do not let any water get inside the meter. If some moisture remains on the waterproof gasket, wipe it off carefully.

Note: Ensure the sensor tongue is remains outside the meter case to avoid damage to the connector.

Calibration Procedure:

Two Point Calibration:

1. Press and hold the MEAS switch for over 3 seconds in the measurement mode to enter the special setting mode.

All items appear on the LCD,
below.

and then the display changes as shown

2. Press the **CAL** switch until the **CAL** symbol appears.
3. Press the MEAS switch for 0.5 seconds. This will display the current calibration setting.
4. Press the **CAL** switch for 0.5 seconds to change the calibration setting. Change the setting to Two Point Calibration, this will be indicated by the number 2 as displayed below.

5. Press the **MEAS** switch to apply the setting. The measurement mode is returned.
6. Open the light shield cover and put some drops of the low-concentration standard solution on the flat sensor to cover the entire flat sensor.
Note: Washing the sensor with the standard solution beforehand may provide more accurate calibration.
7. Close the light shield cover and press the **CAL** switch for over 2 seconds.
8. The **CAL** and ☺ symbols will blink and the calibration value will be displayed.
9. Once calibration is complete the **CAL** and ☺ symbols stop blinking and remain steady.
10. After the calibration for low concentration is completed, open the light shield cover to remove the low-concentration standard solution and wipe off moisture on the sensor.
11. Put some drops of the high-concentration standard solution on the flat sensor to cover the entire flat sensor.
Note: Washing the sensor with the standard solution beforehand may provide more accurate calibration.
12. Close the light shield cover and press the **CAL** switch for over 2 seconds.
13. The **CAL** and ☺ symbols will blink and the calibration value will be displayed.
14. Once calibration is complete the **CAL** and ☺ symbols stop blinking and remain steady.
15. Clean the sensor with tap water and remove moisture.

16. Press the **MEAS** switch for 0.5 seconds to enter the measurement mode and prepare for measurement.

Measurement Procedure:

Note: Ensure the instrument is in measurement mode.

1. Crush 1g of fresh sample to release sample liquid.
2. Open the light shield cover and put some drops of sample liquid on the flat sensor to cover it entirely.
3. Close the light shield cover.
4. When the 😊 symbol lights up the measurement is completed.
5. To lock the measured value, press the **MEAS** switch for 0.5 seconds.
6. When the **MEAS** and 😊 symbols stop blinking and remain steady the measurement is locked.
7. Press the **MEAS** switch for 0.5 seconds to return to the measurement mode.

1.8.4.2 Crop Growth Data and Sample Handling Protocols.

1.8.2.4.1 Growth Chamber Setup and Growing Conditions

All crop testing has been carried out in an M-48 EGC growth chamber, located in the CELLS Lab in LIT. The chamber set-up was as follows:

Photoperiod (hrs):	12 hour light (08:00) 12 hour dark (20:00)
PPF:	300
Temperature:	12 hours at 19°C 12 hours at 20°C
CO ₂ :	750ppm
Wavelengths:	22% 450nm 78% 660nm

A 0.5x Hoaglands nutrient solution was prepared as per the following recipe :

MicroMix:

Consisted of the following:

- 4.75mM H₃BO₄
- 3.70mM MnCl₂.4H₂O
- 0.64mM ZnSO₄.7H₂O
- 0.52mM CuSO₄.5H₂O
- 0.01mM (NH₄)₆ Mo₇O₂₄.4H₂O

These salts were combined and made up to 1L with deionised water.

0.5x Hoaglands:

The following were combined:

- 50mls 1M Ca(NO₃)₂.4H₂O
- 50mls 1M KNO₃
- 20mls 1M MgSO₄.7H₂O
- 10mls 1M K₂H₂PO₄
- 112mls 8.96 mM FeCl₃.6H₂O HEDTA
- 50mls Micro Mix

This was made to a final volume of 20L using deionised water.

Growth studies commenced in February 2017 and coded according to Table 1.8.4.1 below. The growth studies were completed in December 2017 and supplied the produce for the analytical baseline determination for nutritional composition and sensory analysis.

Table 1.8.4.1 Illustrates the growth schedule coding system used for Planting and Harvesting.

<i>Code</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
CEL1	CE: Common experiment (No CO ₂ at beginning) L: Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) 1: First Run/Batch
CERoc1	CE: Common experiment Roc: Rocket/Rucola (EDEN cultivar) 1: First Run/Batch
CERh1	CE: Common experiment Rh: Radish (Purple Plum) 1: First Run/Batch
CES1	CE: Common experiment S: Spinach (Cello F1 hybrid) 1: First Run/Batch
CEL2	CE: Common experiment L: Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) 2: Second Run/Batch
CEBL1	CE: Common experiment L: Butterhead Lettuce 1: First Run/Batch
CEL3	CE: Common experiment L: Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) 3: Third Run/Batch
CESp1	CE: Common experiment Sp: Spinach (Cello) 1: First Run/Batch
CERoc2	CE: Common experiment Roc: Rocket (EDEN cultivar) 2: Second Run/Batch
CERH2	CE: Common experiment Rh: Radish (Purple Plum) 2: Second Run/Batch
CERan1	CE: Common experiment Ran: Radish Annabel 1: First Run/Batch
CEMt1	CE: Common experiment Mt: Mint (Spearmint) 1: First Run/Batch
EDRlen1	Radish (Lennox) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDRrax1	Radish (Raxe) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDSgold1	Spinach (Golden Eye) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch

EDSred1	Spinach (Red Kitten) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDLexp1	Lettuce (Crispy Green Cv Expertise) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDLbat1	Lettuce (Batavia Cv. Othilie) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDLred1	Lettuce (Red Romaine Cv. Outredgeous) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDRoc1	Rocket ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDRM1	Red Mustard (Frizzy lizzy) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDSC1	Swiss Chard (Ruby Red) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDBas1	Basil (Genovese) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDCor1	Coriander (HI 13475 HEC) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDPars1	Parsley (Moskrul 2-Verta RZ) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDDT(F1)1	Dwarf Tomato (F11202) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDDT(34)1	Dwarf Tomato (3469B) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDPep1	Pepper (1601-Mini Pepper) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDCuQu1	Cucumber (Quarto) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDCuPi1	Cucumber (Picowell) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch
EDTcan1	Compact (CandyTom 12.829) ED: EDEN growth setting 1: First Run/Batch

1.8.4.2.2 Harvest Data

Harvest Data compilation is ongoing with corresponding analytical data and will be included in the final work package report in conjunction with FEG compositional analysis results. However, figures 1.8.4.9 to 1.8.4.12, illustrate plant growth chamber set-up and harvest data collection. The EGC M-48 Growth Chamber which is 1.82m x1.82m, has four x Heliospectra EDEN-ISS LED Arrays. The chamber orientation involves four trays x 2 LED Arrays on either side.

Figure 1.8.4.9 Set-up of EGC M-48 Growth Chamber. (a) Set-up and (b) During Growth Study.

Figure 1.8.4.10 Romaine Lettuce (CEL1) at 28DAP: (a) in growth chamber and (b) after harvest.

Figure 1.8.4.11 Radish (CERh1) at 35DAP: (a) in chamber and (b) after harvest.

Figure 1.8.4.12 Rocket (CERoc1) at 28DAP: (a) in chamber and (b) after harvest.

Moisture Content of harvested plant tissue.

The data below for 'leafy greens' illustrates an average % Moisture content of 90% under the current growth conditions. This data will be reviewed in full when nutritional composition data analysis is complete.

Table 1.8.4.3 illustrates the % Water Content for Harvested Plant Tissue from 21 to 56DAP.

% Water Content for Harvested Plant Tissue from 21 to 56DAP						
Sample	Code	DAP	Fresh Wt. (g)	Dry Wt. (g)	% Recovered	% Moisture Content
Lettuce	CEL1	21	5.192	0.45	8.67	91.33
		28	52.508	4.42	8.42	91.58
		56	459.71	31.61	6.88	93.12
Lettuce	CEL2	21	17.464	1.52	8.70	91.30
		28	34.04	2.31	6.79	93.21
		35	215.26	13.15	6.11	93.89
Rocket	CERoc1	21	1.24	0.18	14.52	85.48
		28	16.25	1.58	9.72	90.28
Radish	CERH1	21	4.326	0.14	3.24	96.76
		35	190.27	12.791	6.72	93.28
Lettuce	Oakleaf		68.69	6.22	9.06	90.94
Rocket	Tracey Sensory		50.36	5.97	11.85	88.15

1.8.4.3 Composition Analysis and Safety Protocols.

1.8.4.3.1 Solvent Optimisation for Extraction of Target Molecules for further analysis.

To ensure maximum target molecule (bioactive) extraction from plant tissue for further analysis, it was necessary to determine the best solvent type to use that could be applied to some or all composition analysis methods. Four solvents were tested in the extraction of bioactives from shop bought Radicchio, Rocket and Tomato. The solvents included 70% Acidified Acetone, 75% Acetone, 80% Acidified Methanol and 70% Ethanol. The percentage concentration was based on standard extraction methods reported in literature. The four extracts for each sample were then assayed for Total Polyphenol Content (TPC), Total Flavonoid Content (TFC) and FRAP analysis.

Figure 1.8.4.13 Comparison of Extraction Solvents for shop bought Rocket.

From the results of the FRAP assay, there was a statistically significant difference observed between the four extraction solvents in their efficacy to extract bioactive compounds for each of the three samples, with 75% Acetone, 70% Acidified Acetone and 75% Acetone extracting the most bioactive compounds from the radicchio, tomato and rocket respectively.

Figure 1.8.4.14 illustrates the best solvent for use in bioactive extraction for TFC analysis of shop bought Radicchio.

The results of the TPC assay also displayed a significant difference between the solvents. 80% acidified methanol extracted the most phenolic content from all three plant samples (Figure 1.8.4.14). A statistically significant difference was again observed between the four solvents for each sample from the results of the TFC assay. 80% acidified methanol extracted the most compounds from the radicchio, while the 70% acidified Acetone extracted the most from the tomato and rocket.

1.8.4.3.2 Total Carotenoid Content and Relationship with Colour

During the validation of the operating procedure for the colorimeter, it was discovered that a correlation existed between Total Carotenoid Content (TCC) and the *colour* values obtained from the hand-held meter. A simple test was

set-up to confirm this correlation in which both the TCC assay and the colourimeter were used to test the colour of four tomatoes at varying stages of ripening (red pigment development).

(a) Figure 1.8.4.15 (a) illustrates the correlation of TCC concentration (ug/g) in shop bought baby tomatoes against colour value a* observed from the Colourimeter. (b) illustrates the visible gradient in colour of the baby tomatoes analysed. (c) illustrates the colour extracted from the baby tomatoe tissue.

Further analysis of this observation is required across more plant tissues and replicates to confirm this correlation, however if there is a direct correlation of colour intensity to TCC, the ease of determining ripeness and high nutritional content and bioactive concentration will be as simple as using the colourimeter for the Neumeyer III crew. In addition, comparison of other bioactive data is also underway to determine other bioactive versus colour intensity relationships in the selected EDEN ISS plant cultivars.

In summary, the following methods have been carried out on shop bought and home laboratory grown samples and results are currently being compiled.

- ✓ Total Phenolic Content (TPC)
- ✓ Total Flavonoid Content (TFC)
- ✓ Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP)
- ✓ Total Carotenoid Content (TCC)
- ✓ Glucosinolates (Gluc) using LCMS - These samples include samples provided by CNR
- ✓ B-Carotene and Lutein analysis using LCMS

1.8.4.3.3 Preliminary Discussion on Compositional Analysis.

All compositional analysis of crop samples were carried out in triplicate of compositional samples. The following section goes through preliminary results for four of the 20 species of fruit and salad crops grown by CELLS for EDEN-ISS. Most of the 20 species were from the same seed bank as those grown in the FEG by DLR. Replicate samples were used in all analysis and statistical analysis including ANOVA and t test are ongoing on all data obtained within the growing period of 28 to 56 DAP for most salad crops and up to 100 DAP for cucumber. All growth studies were carried out under the EDEN ISS FEG growth conditions to allow for baseline determination.

Lactuca Sativa L.,

The effects of plant growth duration on chlorophyll content was examined at 3 different number of Days After Planting namely 28, 35 and 56 DAP. As illustrated in Figure 1.8.4.16 and as expected, chlorophyll content in lettuce species increases with increase in DAP. Figure 1.8.4.17 illustrates the variation among three lettuce species at 28 DAP.

Figure 1.8.4.16. The chlorophyll content of Red romaine lettuce from DAP 28 to 56.

Figure 1.8.4.17: A comparison of the chlorophyll content of the three different lettuce species analyzed

The chlorophyll content of Crispy Green Lettuce plants at 28 DAP, was 37.03% and 68.64% higher than that of the red romaine and bativa species. Due to the fact that chlorophyll content increases with time it would be recommended that perhaps the growth duration of the bativa lettuce should be extended to increase the chlorophyll content produced.

The red romaine lettuce grown as part of the EDEN growth studies also demonstrated a greater total carotenoid content compared to the shop bought red romaine lettuce. The red romaine lettuce grown produced a total carotenoid content of 705.41µg/g, a 39.23% increase compared to the 506.65µg/g carotenoid content in the shop bought red romaine lettuce. Illustrating that the growth conditions utilized for the EDEN ISS project produce plant species with greater total carotenoid content compared to similar plant species purchased.

Figure 1.8.4.18 The total carotenoid content of Red romaine lettuce at different growth durations.

As illustrated in Figure 1.8.4.18, the effects of plant growth duration (DAP) on the total carotenoid content in Red Romaine Lettuce was examined at 3 different DAP (28, 35 and 56). Similar to the results of the chlorophyll content,

the total carotenoid content for the Red Romaine lettuce increased with growth duration. The highest carotenoid content was at 56 DAP producing 1606.77 $\mu\text{g/g}$ total carotenoid content while the lowest carotenoid content produced was at 28 DAP, with a result of 705.41 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Therefore, to obtain the highest nutritional benefit, Red Romaine should be harvested at 56 DAP.

The ash content of the lettuce 74.4% gave comparable results to the shop bought lettuce 82%. No major impact on plant mineral content is expected. The data from mineral analysis is being compiled.

The EDEN and shop bought red romaine lettuce had significantly higher anthocyanin content compared to the other species tested with 26.68 $\mu\text{g/g}$ total anthocyanin content. The presence of anthocyanins results in the red, blue and purple colours of many fruit and vegetables, therefore it is expected that red romaine lettuce would have a high anthocyanin content. From the result it would be recommended to grow red romaine lettuce as a consumable source of anthocyanins compared to the other plant species.

Figure 1.8.4.19. The total anthocyanin content of red romaine lettuce at different growth durations.

The effects of plant growth duration on the total anthocyanin content was examined at 3 different number of DAP namely 28, 35 and 56 DAP (Figure 1.8.4.19). There is a 23.18% increase in the total anthocyanin content when the growth duration is extended from 28 days to 35 days. After this however there is decrease in anthocyanin content with increase in growth duration, with the total anthocyanin content only reaching 5.59 $\mu\text{g/g}$. This proves that the optimum growth duration for producing maximum anthocyanin content in red romaine lettuce is at 35DAP. If the lettuce is grown for longer than 35 days there is a decrease in the total anthocyanin content. It would therefore be recommended harvesting the lettuce at 35 DAP for maximum anthocyanin content.

The red romaine lettuce grown as part of this project produced the highest phenolic content with 43.34 mg/g compared to the other plant species analyzed (Figure 1.8.4.20). It was 8.89% higher in phenolic content compared to the shop bought red romaine lettuce. This indicates that the growth conditions utilized for the EDEN ISS project produce plant species with greater total phenolic content compared to similar plant species purchased.

Figure 1.8.4.20. The total phenolic content of red romaine lettuce at different growth durations

The effects of plant growth duration on the total phenolic content was examined at 3 different number of DAP namely 28, 35 and 56 DAP (Figure 1.8.4.21). The results of the total phenolic content at different growth durations was similar to that of the total anthocyanin content. The phenolic content in the red romaine lettuce increases from 28DAP to 35DAP and then decreases at 56DAP. It would therefore be recommended harvesting the lettuce at 35 DAP for maximum phenolic content. From the plant species analyzed the red romaine lettuce grown as part of this project produced the highest flavonoid content with 89.92mg/g. This is a 21.51% increase compared to the shop bought red romaine lettuce.

Figure 1.8.4.21. The total flavonoid content of red romaine lettuce at different growth durations.

The effects of plant growth duration on the total flavonoid content was examined at 3 different number of DAP namely 28, 35 and 56 DAP (Figure 1.8.4.21). There was a similar trend observed for the total flavonoid content as there was for the total phenolic and total anthocyanin content. There was an increase in the total flavonoid content of the red romaine lettuce increasing from 89.93mg/g at 28 DAP to 93.16mg/g at 35 DAP. When the growth duration was extended to 56 days there was a 16.40% decrease in the total flavonoid content. It would therefore be recommended harvesting the lettuce at 35 DAP for maximum flavonoid content. The red romaine lettuce grown under the EDEN growth settings gave similar results to the shop bought red romaine lettuce.

Figure 1.8.4.22. The total antioxidant power of red romaine lettuce at different growth durations.

The effects of plant growth duration on the total antioxidant power of the plants was examined at 3 different number of DAP namely 28, 35 and 56 DAP (Figure 1.8.4.22). Following the same trend as the anthocyanin, phenolic and flavonoid results the total antioxidant power of the red romaine lettuce increased from 28 days to 35 days after planting, with a decrease observed when the plant growth was extended to 56 days. It would therefore be recommended harvesting the lettuce at 35 DAP for maximum antioxidant power as well as anthocyanin, phenolic and flavonoid content.

From LCMS analysis lettuce samples contained both β -carotene and lutein, to nutritionally valuable levels. The red romaine lettuce grown was found to contain both β -carotene and lutein while neither biomolecule was identified in the shop bought lettuce. From the results of the total carotenoid assay it was found that the red romaine lettuce grown for the EDEN project had a higher total carotenoid content than the shop bought lettuce. These results are reflected in the LCMS data, proving further that the growth conditions utilized for the EDEN ISS project produce plant species with greater total carotenoid content compared to similar plant species purchased. Each of the plant species was analyzed for the presence of chlorogenic acid, caftaric acid, cyanidin-3-malonyglucoside, quercetin-3-glucoside, kaempferol-3-glucuronide and rutin. The red romaine lettuce grown during this project contained all six compounds. The shop bought red romaine lettuce however did not contain rutin.

Eruca sativa Mill.

The EDEN rocket cultivar also produced a high total carotenoid content of 1029.21 μ g/g. This is a 19.71% increase compared to the shop bought rocket which was analyzed for comparison. Mean ash content of rocket samples was 77.9% and comparable to the shop bought rocket 79%.

The rocket also produced a high total phenolic content of 28.47mg/g. This is a 32.79% increase compared to the shop bought rocket which was analyzed for comparison. This indicates that the growth conditions utilized for the EDEN ISS project produce plant species with greater total phenolic content compared to similar plant species purchased. Both the shop bought rocket and EDEN rocket grown during this project provided similar total flavonoid values of 37.1mg/g and 32.07mg/g respectively. The rocket grown under the EDEN growth settings gave similar results to the shop bought rocket.

From LCMS analysis of the plants it was found that the rocket samples contained both β -carotene and lutein. Chlorogenic acid, caftaric acid, Cyanidin-3-malonyglucoside, Quercetin-3-Glucoside and Kaempferol-3-Glucuronide were each identified in the rocket grown during this project. The shop bought rocket did not contain Cyanidin-3-malonyglucoside. These results highlight the effects of different growth settings on the bioactive content produced by a plant. It also proves that the settings used for the EDEN ISS project produce plants with polyphenolic compounds that are not present in shop bought samples.

Raphanus sativus L.,

Both of the radish species tested produced very low levels of total carotenoid content and would not be recommended as a consumable source of carotenoids compared to the other plant species. The purple plum radish had significantly higher anthocyanin content compared to the other species tested with 24.59 μ g/g total anthocyanin content. The presence of anthocyanins results in the red, blue and purple colours of many fruit and vegetables, therefore it is expected that the purple plum radish would have a higher anthocyanin content as they are purple in colour.

The Anabel radish had significantly lower anthocyanin content compared to the purple plum radish producing 1.25 μ g/g and 24.59 μ g/g total anthocyanin content respectively, however the purple plum radish has darker purple pigmentation than the Anabel radish which is contributed to by the anthocyanin content. From the result it would be recommended to grow purple plum radish as a consumable source of anthocyanins compared to the other plant species.

The Anabel radish had the lowest total flavonoid content, 0.32mg/g. The purple plum radish produced 14.1mg/g total flavonoid content and would therefore prove to be a more nutritional radish than the anabel species. Neither of the radish species were found to contain either β -carotene and lutein. Chlorogenic acid, caftaric acid, Cyanidin-3-malonyglucoside, Quercetin-3-Glucoside and Kaempferol-3-Glucuronide were each identified in both Raddish species.

Spinacia oleracea L.,

From the plant species tested, similar to the results of the chlorophyll analysis it was the spinach which produced the highest carotenoid content with 1686.89 μ g/g total carotenoid content. Spinach had the highest antioxidant power compared to the other plant species analyzed however there was no plant species found to be significantly lower. From LCMS analysis of the plants it was found that spinach samples contained both β -carotene and lutein.

Table 1.8.4.4 details collated data from handheld, nutritional analysis, and bioactive identification. Section 1.8.4.4 will review the sensory output for all EDEN-ISS growth studies in CELLS laboratory.

Food Sample\Code	Handheld Analysis						Other Analyses (As Specified Non-Handheld Device Analyses)															
	Penetrometer	Colorimeter 1 (L*)	Colorimeter 2 (a*)	Colorimeter 3 (b*)	Chlorophyll (SPAD units)	Nitrate Ion (NO ₃ -)	Refractometer Sugar (%Brix)	Total Phenol Content (mg/g)	Total Flavonoid Content (mg/g)	FRAP (mM/g)	Anthocyanin (mg/ml)	Total Carotenoid Content (ug/g)	Glucosinolate (Sinigrin)	Total Ash (% Ash)	Polyphenol (LCMS)						Carotenoid (LCMS)	
															Chlorogenic Acid	Caftaric Acid	Cyanidin-3-malonylglucoside	Quercetin-3-Glucoside	Kaempferol-3-Glucuronide	Rutin	β-Carotene	Lutein
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc1 28 Rep 1					58.48		1.1	17.08	33.79	62.56	-0.75	973.16	-	77	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc1 28 Rep 2					47.78		1.1	17.49	33.23	62.69	-1.38	973.14										
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc1 28 Rep 3					52.66		1.2	16.83	35.19	65.56	-0.63	992.25										
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc2 28 Rep 1					49.38		1.2	38.83	29.66	57.19	3.26	1055.50	-	78.8	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc2 28 Rep 2					52.48		1.1	40.24	29.94	55.44	0.75	1081.53										
Rocket -Rucola (Eden Cultivar - CERoc2 28 Rep 3					49.06		1.2	40.33	30.60	56.94	1.63	1099.65										
Raddish (Annabel) CERan1 28 Rep 1	3.43	54.13	31.35	6.40	52.20		5.3	10.83	0.04	49.44	1.38	21.12	-	87.6	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
Raddish (Annabel) CERan1 28 Rep 2	3.52	47.90	35.77	9.63	55.10		5.3	11.83	0.23	48.81	1.38	8.05										
Raddish (Annabel) CERan1 28 Rep 3	3.57	42.47	37.25	8.25	43.14		5.4	11.49	0.69	49.06	1.00	17.23										
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH1 35 Rep 1	3.78	37.72	16.75	2.01	34.00		5.8	10.91	4.16	55.94	15.78	42.75	-	84.6	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH1 35 Rep 2	3.93	45.98	11.50	-0.02	42.34		6	9.99	4.54	55.56	15.66	96.75										
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH1 35 Rep 3	3.83	39.49	15.27	-1.20	36.54		5.9	10.49	4.63	57.06	14.03	128.30										
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH2 28 Rep 1	4.01	33.97	24.14	-1.48	43.84		5.2	15.16	14.38	57.31	24.80	65.76	-	80	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH2 28 Rep 2	3.41	32.79	19.64	-1.56	48.84		5.2	15.66	13.82	59.06	24.42	50.12										
Raddish (Purple Plum) CERH2 28 Rep 3	3.62	39.38	24.54	-1.58	47.06		5.2	17.16	14.10	59.44	24.55	56.09										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 28 Rep 1					29.46		1.3	39.83	84.88	37.94	19.91	418.42	-	78	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 28 Rep 2					28.58		1.2	40.49	83.19	35.69	14.03	450.34										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 28 Rep 3					30.62		1.4	40.33	85.44	39.56	14.40	429.42										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 28 Rep 1					29.58		0.3	45.08	92.57	36.31	24.92	603.32	-	71.5	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 28 Rep 2					32.50		0.4	48.58	97.26	51.56	20.66	645.57										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 28 Rep 3					30.72		0.3	47.66	94.44	57.31	24.42	653.15										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 35 Rep 1					37.72		0.4	48.41	92.48	49.81	23.29	838.02	-	74.4	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 35 Rep 2					34.38		0.2	45.24	93.69	45.06	22.29	841.48										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL2 35 Rep 3					35.62		0.3	48.99	93.32	48.94	24.55	865.37										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL3 28 Rep 1					25.04		0.4	42.74	90.41	54.56	20.54	1059.55	-	77.2	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL3 28 Rep 2					24.58		0.3	43.16	89.76	56.44	14.15	1002.56										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL3 28 Rep 3					29.70		0.3	42.24	91.35	56.31	17.44	1086.43										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 56 Rep 1					43.44		0.3	39.83	77.76	44.56	5.51	1570.07	-	81.2	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 56 Rep 2					37.98		0.3	40.49	78.41	40.69	3.36	1575.84										
Lettuce (Red Romaine Outredgeous) CEL1 56 Rep 3					41.86		0.4	40.33	77.48	40.94	7.64	1674.41										
Spinnach (Cello F1 Hybrid) CESp1 28 Rep 1					59.92		1.1	9.74	15.51	73.56	-0.88	1650.43	-	75.8	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Spinnach (Cello F1 Hybrid) CESp1 28 Rep 2					75.30		1.2	9.58	16.91	72.19	-0.75	1711.29										
Spinnach (Cello F1 Hybrid) CESp1 28 Rep 3					71.80		1.1	9.24	17.48	70.69	-0.38	1698.94										

1.8.4.4 Organoleptic Analysis – Sensory Results.

1.8.4.4.1 Sensory Analysis – Initial Results

Sensory analysis was carried out from Wed 26th Apr to 22nd December 2017, using EDEN samples grown in CELLS growth chambers. The growth conditions of these samples are as discussed in section 1.8.2.3. Once nitrate levels were confirmed to be in safe levels for the Eden samples, they were washed, chopped and coded for blind sensory analysis. Shop bought controls were also treated in this manner. All plant tissues for sensory analysis were washed and stored in a sealable food bag at 0 to 4°C until use. Samples can be stored up to 4 days once prepared in this manner.

The samples were presented to the trained sensory panel and assessed for acceptability and descriptors. Below is the table of planned sensory samples, sessions.

Table 1.8.4.4: EDEN-ISS sensory session planning

Action	Description*	Date
LIT sensory session 1	Red romaine & Rocket	Apr 2017
LIT sensory session 2	Red romaine & Radish	May 2017
LIT sensory session 3	Red Romaine Lettuce Butterhead Lettuce Spinach Bell pepper Tomato	June 2017
LIT sensory session 4	Rocket Radish (Purple Plum) Radish (Anabel) Bright Red globe radish Mint (Spearmint)	June 2017
LIT sensory session 5	Radish (Raxe)	Sept 2017
LIT sensory session 6	Radish (Lennox)	Sept 2017
LIT sensory session 7	Red Mustard (Frizzy Lizzy)	Sept 2017
Bremen training of crew	1-2 days (8hrs/day) to train	Sept 2017
LIT sensory session 8	Red Romaine Rocket	Oct 2017
LIT sensory session 9	Basil	Oct 2017
LIT sensory session 10	Lettuce (Crispy Green) Lettuce (Bativa) Spinach Swiss Chard	Oct 2017
LIT sensory session 11	Tomato (3469) Tomato (F11202) Cucumber (Quatro) Cucumber (Picowell)	Dec 2017
LIT data analysis of Antarctica sensory analysis	LIT data analysis of sensory data sent back from Antarctica	Jan 2018

*2 samples/cultivars per session where LIT CELLS EDEN samples are compare to a poly-tunnel/shop bought sample.

Sensory Data Results:
Table 1.8.4.5: EDEN-ISS Sensory Results for Acceptability & Descriptive Analysis

Sample	Harvest day	Acceptability Score	Crispness (limp-crisp)	Texture (soft-tough)	Flavour (bland-flavoursome)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Red Romaine	35	6.8	5.1	4.5	4.8	2.5
EDEN Red Romaine	56	6.8	6.1	6.5*	5.4	2.3
EDEN Red Romaine	28	6.7	5.0	5.4	5.1	3.2
			Colour (light-dark)	Texture (soft-tough)	Flavour (mild-strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Rocket	35	5.9	6.1*	5.3	6.9	7.3
EDEN Rocket	28	5.4	6.7**	4.8	8.1**	8.1**
			Crispness (soft-crisp)	Texture (pulpy-light & juicy)	Flavour (mild - strong)	Aftertaste (low-spicy)
EDEN Radish	35	5.6	4.3	5.3	4.9	5.6
EDEN Purple plum radish	28	6.9	5.3	5.0	5.3	5.1*
EDEN Anabel Radish	28	6.8	5.5	5.6	5.5*	5.1*
EDEN Radish Raxe	28	5.9	4.9	5.4	4.9	4.4
EDEN Radish Lennox	28	6.7	5.1	5.9	6.1	5.3
			Colour (light-dark)	Texture (soft-tough)	Flavour (mild-strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Spinach	28	5.8	7.8*	6.5*	5.6	4.8**
			Colour (green-purple)	Flavour (mild-strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)	
EDEN Red mustard Frizzy Lizzy	28	4.9	2.4**	5.4	5.6**	
			Colour (light-dark)	Texture (soft-tough)	Flavour (mild-strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Rocket	28	7.0	8.0**	6.4	6.8	7.4**
			Appearance (flat-curved)	Flavour (mild-strong)	Texture (soft - crunchy)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Basil	35	7.5	7.8	8.0	7.0	6.8
			Texture (limp-crispy)	Flavour (mild - strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)	
EDEN Lettuce Crispy green	42	6.8	5.3	5.4	5.3	
EDEN Lettuce Bativa	42	6.4	5.3	5.5	4.9	
			Colour (light - dark)	Texture (soft-tough)	Flavour (mild - strong)	Aftertaste (low-high)
EDEN Spinach Red kitten	42	6.9	6.8**	4.9	5.9	5.3
EDEN Swiss chard	42	5.8	7.6	7.4	7.1	6.6
			Colour (orange-red)	Texture (soft-hard)	Flavour (bland-flavoursome)	Skin texture (light-thick)
EDEN Tomato 3469	na	6.8	3.0**	3.1**	4.5	4.1**
EDEN Tomato F11202	na	6.2	6.2	3.6**	4.2	4.3**
			Colour (light-dark)	Texture (pulpy-crisp)	Juiciness (dry-juicy)	Flavour (mild-strong)

EDEN Cucumber (Quatro)	na	7.2	3.7	5.2	5.5*	5.7
EDEN Cucumber (Picowell)	na	6.5	4.7	4.5	6.3*	4.8

Results that are significantly different from the shop control with a P value of *<0.5, ** <0.01

Cultivar Results Analysis:

Red Romaine day 56 (CEL1 56)

Picture 1: Shop bought control (left) & EDEN red romaine (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought red romaine are comparable in terms of acceptability. Similarly, for descriptive analysis the descriptors for the red romaine – crispness, texture, flavour and aftertaste are also comparable.

Figure 1 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Figure 2 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Red Romaine day 28 (CEL3 28)

Picture 2 Shop v EDEN day 28 Red Romaine

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought red romaine are comparable in terms of acceptability.

Figure 3 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Similarly, for descriptive analysis the descriptors for the red romaine – crispness, texture, flavour and aftertaste are also comparable.

Figure 4 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Red Romaine day 35 (CEL2 35)

Picture 3 EDEN day 35 Red Romaine

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN red romaine scores highly in terms of acceptability.

Figure 5 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Similarly, for descriptive analysis the descriptors for the red romaine – crispness, texture, flavour and aftertaste are also comparable.

Figure 6 Descriptive analysis of EDEN red romaine

Red Romaine day 28 (EDLred1 28)

Picture 4 EDEN day 28 Red Romaine

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN red romaine scores highly in terms of acceptability.

Figure 7 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Similarly, for previous day 28 Red romaine descriptive analysis the descriptors for the red romaine – crispness, texture, flavour and aftertaste are also comparable.

Figure 8 Descriptive analysis of EDEN red romaine

Rocket

Rocket day 35 (CERoc1 35)

Picture 5 Shop bought control (left) & EDEN rocket (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Rocket are comparable in terms of acceptability. For descriptive analysis the EDEN Rocket scores higher for colour (darker), but for texture, flavour and aftertaste both samples are comparable.

Figure 9 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought rocket

Figure 10 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Rocket day 28 (CeRoc2 28)

Picture 6 Shop bought control (left) & EDEN rocket (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Rocket are not significantly different in terms of acceptability.

Figure 11 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought rocket

The descriptors for the Rocket – colour, texture, flavour and aftertaste differ between the EDEN Rocket and the shop bought rocket. The EDEN Rocket scores higher for colour (darker), flavour (stronger) and aftertaste (higher).

Figure 12 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought rocket

Rocket day 28 (EDRoc1 28)

Picture 7 Shop bought control (left) & EDEN rocket (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Rocket are not significantly different (as the error bars overlap). For the shop rocket there is a greater variation among the sensory panel with an increase std deviation with regard to acceptability.

Figure 13 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought rocket

The descriptors for the Rocket – colour, texture, flavour and aftertaste differ between the EDEN Rocket and the shop bought rocket. The EDEN Rocket scores higher for colour (darker), flavour (stronger) and aftertaste (higher).

Figure 14 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought rocket

Radish

Radish day 35 (CERh1 35)

Picture 7 Shop bought control (left) & EDEN radish (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought radish are not comparable in terms of acceptability. The shop bought Radish is more acceptable than the EDEN radish. Descriptive analysis shows that the shop bought sample is crispier and has less of an aftertaste. Hence there is a difference between the EDEN and shop bought samples. The EDEN radish samples were harvested at 35 days. This may be the reason for the lower acceptability and crispiness. From the picture above the radish grown by EDEN is quite large. This is to be repeated with an earlier harvest date and compared to the shop bought sample.

Figure 15 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought radish

Figure 16 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought radish

Radish day 28 (Purple plum CERh2 28 & Anabel CERan1 28)

Picture 8 Shop bought control, EDEN Purple plum radish (CERh2 28) & EDEN Anabel radish (CERan1 28)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN radishes and the shop bought radish are comparable in terms of acceptability.

Figure 17 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought radishes

Descriptive analysis shows that the shop bought sample has less flavour and has less of an aftertaste. Hence there is a difference between the EDEN and shop bought samples. This does not however affect acceptability.

Figure 18 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought radish

Radish day 28 (Raxe EDRrax1 28 & Lennox EDrlen1 28)

Picture 9 Shop v EDEN day 28 EDEN Radish Lennox & Raxe

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought radish are comparable in terms of acceptability.

Figure 19 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought radish

Descriptive analysis shows the shop bought radish to be slightly crisper. All were similar in relation to texture. The EDEN Lennox radish had a slightly stronger flavour. The EDEN radish Raxe scored lowest for all descriptors.

Figure 20 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought red romaine

Spinach & Swiss chard

Spinach day 28 (EDRM1 28)

Picture 10 Shop bought & EDEN day 28 Spinach

Similar to Rocket the bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Spinach are not significantly different. However, from the mean scores the EDEN Spinach is liked less. For the EDEN Spinach there is a greater variation among the sensory panel with an increase std deviation with regard to acceptability.

Figure 21 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought Spinach

The descriptors for the Spinach – colour, texture, flavour, texture and aftertaste differ between the EDEN Spinach and the shop bought Spinach. The EDEN Spinach scores higher for colour (darker), texture (tougher), flavour (stronger) and aftertaste (higher). These differences may account for the higher standard deviation and lower mean score for the EDEN Spinach acceptability above.

Figure 22 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought Spinach

Spinach day 42 (EDSred1 42) & Swiss chard day 42 (EDSC1 42)

Note: As there was no available shop swiss chard sample (due to seasonality) the swiss chard was tested with the spinach as this was deemed a comparable sample.

Picture 11 EDEN Spinach (left) Shop bought control (right) & Swiss chard (far right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought spinach are not significantly different. The Swiss chard is liked less than the spinach.

Figure 23 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought spinach & Swiss chard

The descriptors for the spinach & swiss chard – colour, texture, flavour and aftertaste differ between the EDEN and the shop bought spinach. The EDEN spinach is significantly darker with slightly stronger flavour and aftertaste.

In comparison to the spinach the swiss chard is comparable in colour to the EDEN spinach with significantly tougher texture, flavour & aftertaste.

Figure 24 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop spinach & swiss chard

Red Mustard

Red mustard day 28 (EDRM1 28)

Picture 12 Shop bought red mustard (left) & EDEN red mustard (right)

Figure 25 Shop bought control (left) & EDEN red mustard (right)

The bar chart above shows that the EDEN and the shop bought red mustard are not significantly different (as the error bars overlap). For the EDEN red mustard there is a greater variation among the sensory panel with an increased std deviation with regard to acceptability.

The descriptors for the Red mustard – colour, flavour and aftertaste differ between the EDEN and the shop bought red mustard. The EDEN red mustard greener with the shop bought sample being purple (this maybe cultivar related). The flavour (stronger) and aftertaste (higher) score much higher for the EDEN red mustard. These differences may account for the higher standard deviation for the EDEN rocket acceptability above. Meaning some panellists like the stronger flavour and after-taste for the EDEN sample

Figure 26 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought red mustard

Basil

Basil day 28 (EDBas1 35)

Picture 13 EDEN Basil (left) & shop basil (right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Basil are not significantly different (as the error bars overlap) in terms of acceptability. However, the EDEN basil seems to be liked slightly more than the shop basil.

Figure 27 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought rocket

The descriptors for the basil – appearance, texture, flavour and aftertaste differ between the EDEN basil and the shop bought basil. The EDEN basil scores higher for appearance (curled), flavour (stronger), texture (crunchy) and aftertaste (higher).

Figure 28 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought Basil

Green Lettuce

Green lettuce day 28 Batvia (EDLbat1 42) & Crispy green (EDLexp1 42)

Picture 14 Shop bought control (left), EDEN lettuce Batvia (right) & Crispy Green (far right)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought Lettuce are not significantly different.

Figure 29 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought lettuce

The descriptors for the Lettuce - texture, flavour and aftertaste do not differ between the EDEN and the shop bought lettuce.

Figure 30 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought lettuce

Tomato

Picture 15 Shop bought control (124), EDEN tomato 3649 (234) & EDEN tomato F11202 (567)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought tomato are not significantly different.

Figure 31 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought tomato

The descriptors for the tomato – Colour, texture, flavour and skin texture do differ between the EDEN and the shop bought lettuce. The texture of the EDEN samples is softer and less hard,

Figure 32 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought tomato

Cucumber

Picture 16 Shop bought control (124), EDEN cucumber Quatro (234) & EDEN cucumber Picowell (567)

The bar chart below shows that the EDEN and the shop bought cucumber are not significantly different.

Figure 33 Acceptability of EDEN & shop bought cucumber

The descriptors for the cucumber – Colour, texture, flavour and juiciness do differ between the EDEN and the shop bought lettuce. The texture of the EDEN samples is juicier.

Figure 34 Descriptive analysis of EDEN & shop bought cucumber
Summary table EDEN v shop sample results:

EDEN code	Sample	Acceptable/unacceptable	Descriptive analysis
CEL2 35	Red Romaine day 35	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
CEL1 56	Red Romaine day 56	Acceptable	EDEN Red romaine at day 56 has a tougher texture
CEL3 28	Red Romaine day 28	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
EDLred1 28	Red romaine day 35	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
CERoc1 35	Rocket day 35	Acceptable	EDEN rocket is greener
CeRoc2 28	Rocket day 28	Acceptable	EDEN rocket is greener with stronger flavour and aftertaste.
EDRoc1 28	Rocket day 28	Acceptable	EDEN rocket greener, stronger flavour and aftertaste
CERh1 35	Radish day 35	Acceptable	EDEN radish is less crisp with a significant aftertaste.
CERh2 28	Radish day 28 Purple plum	Acceptable	EDEN Purple plum has stronger flavour & after taste.
CERan1 28	Radish day 28 Anabel	Acceptable	EDEN Anabel has stronger flavour & after taste.
EDRrax1 28	Radish day 28 Raxe	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
EDRlen1 28	Radish day 28 Lennox	Acceptable	EDEN Lennox has a stronger flavour.
CESp1 28	Spinach day 28	Acceptable	EDEN spinach is darker green with a tougher texture, stronger flavour and aftertaste.
EDSred1 42	Spinach day 42 Red kitten	Acceptable	EDEN spinach is darker with a stronger flavour & aftertaste.
EDRM1 28	Red mustard day 28	Acceptable	EDEN red mustard is green (rather than purple) with a stronger flavour and aftertaste.
EDLexp1 42	Lettuce day 42 Crisp green	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
EDLbat1 42	Lettuce day 42 Batava	Acceptable	Same as shop control.
EDSC1 42	Swiss chard 42	Acceptable	EDEN Swiss chard is darker with a stronger flavour & aftertaste (<i>when compared to spinach</i>).
3469	Tomato	Acceptable	EDEN tomato softer with a lighter skin texture.
F11202	Tomato	Acceptable	EDEN tomato softer with a lighter skin texture.
Quatro	Cucumber	Acceptable	EDEN cucumber is juicier.
Picowell	Cucumber	Acceptable	EDEN cucumber is juicier.

Conclusion

Sensory evaluation can be used to compare a range of foods and verify whether a final food product meets its pre-determined specification and/or acceptability. Sensory evaluation uses trained human assessors to score each sample for acceptability and quantitative descriptive analysis. In this study a shop bought control is used for comparison purposes to assess the EDEN closed crop growth samples. The trained assessors evaluated each of the crops for overall acceptability. In addition, the group evaluated plant specific sensory descriptors e.g. appearance, flavour, texture and aftertaste.

The results showed that all of the plants grown by EDEN were acceptable when compared to a shop bought sample. None of the EDEN samples scored significantly lower than the shop samples when rated for likeability. Hence all of the samples were acceptable and palatable.

Quantitative descriptive analysis identified that some of the EDEN samples scored significantly higher in terms of colour, flavour, juiciness and aftertaste.

Red romaine harvested at day 56 had a tougher texture. This texture score reduced when the Red romaine was harvested at an earlier day 35 harvest date. Rocket scored significantly higher for colour, flavour and aftertaste. Anabel radish scored higher for flavour and aftertaste. Spinach scored higher for colour, texture and aftertaste. Red mustard was green (rather than the usual red colour) and scored higher for aftertaste. Tomatoes scored lower for texture and skin toughness. Cucumbers scored higher for juiciness.

Some of these differences measured maybe due to a difference in cultivar between the EDEN and the shop bought controls. However, in general the EDEN samples due to the closed optimum protected system produced plants with enhanced colour and flavour. In terms of texture this can be increased e.g. spinach or decreased e.g. tomatoes.

Regardless of the specific sensory descriptor differences all of the EDEN grown plants are acceptable and palatable. In general, the significant differences between the EDEN and the shop bought controls are favourable and may in some cases produce an enhanced product once harvested at an earlier rather than late harvest date.

1.8.4.4.3 Sensory Analysis Pre-Antarctica Neumeyer III Crew Training, Bremen, September 2017

Overview:

Limerick Institute of Technology, as a partner in the EDEN-ISS project, will contribute their expertise to the food quality, safety and processing experiments which will be carried out in the Future Exploration Greenhouse that will be built as part of the project in Antarctica.

The Food Development Services Centre at LIT will also be involved by offering organoleptic (sensory) analysis expertise and training as a measure for food quality during the project. Food sensory evaluation is a scientific discipline that analyses and measures human responses to the composition of food and drinks, e.g. appearance, touch, odour, texture, temperature and taste. Sensory evaluation can be used to compare similarities/differences in a range of foods, verify whether a final food product meets its pre-determined specification and provide objective feedback to enable informed decisions for product development. Sensory evaluation can be utilized in a closed environment crop growth system to determine the palatability of the fresh produce for consumption.

Dr Tracey Larkin's research focuses on sensory analysis and currently leads a trained sensory panel to assess sensory aspects of foods at the research facility Food@LIT. EDEN ISS will utilize these trained panelists to determine food sensory quality of the closed environment crops. The interactive nature of the trained panel will help to identify key product characteristics and provide insights to the crew perception of the crops. This information will then be used to enhance growth and train the crew in sensory evaluation prior to Antarctica. This way, EDEN ISS will add value to the knowledge and understanding of important food sensory factors essential for crew's acceptance of crops grown in closed environments. In addition, this may be of particular importance for long-duration space flights as positive sensory responses by astronauts to their food may stimulate positive psychological responses.

Crew training proposed schedule for the day:

10am – 11am Overview of sensory evaluation (presentation & taste tests)

Break

11.15-1pm Acceptability & descriptive analysis of 5/6 cultivars (romaine, rocket, radish, & tomatoes etc.)

Lunch

2-4pm Acceptability & descriptive analysis of 5/6 cultivars (lettuce, chives, herbs etc.)

Break

4.15-5pm Data recording & closing discussion

Special Resources:

1. Room with desks or round table for 10 people
2. Projector linked to computer for a power point presentation
3. Bottles of water (approx. 30 x 500ml)
4. White disposable plates (approx. 200 plates)
5. White drinking cups disposable (approx. 50 cups)
6. Orange juice (1L of freshly squeezed & 1 L of concentrate)

7. Crisps 3 x different flavors (1 bag of each)
8. Cultivars (lettuce, tomatoes, radish etc – we can confirm this list closer to the time)
9. Access to sink and prep area for the food samples.
10. Chopping board, knives, lettuce dryer, disposable kitchen towel, food grade salt, sugar & lemon juice.

Note: A Portable Sensory Booth will be shipped from LIT to Bremen in June 2017 to allow for familiarization of this environment for the crew involved in sensory analysis while on Antarctica.

1.8.4.5 Storage Methodology Development and Results.

1.8.4.5.1 Short Term storage for Crew Consumption

Passive Atmosphere

Following a decontamination procedure, e.g. dipping, portions for consumption will be stored in biodegradable, sealing bags at a temperature between 0,5 and 3 °C

Cold storage

Passive atmosphere bags will be stored and maintained at a temperature between 0,5 and 3 °C

1.8.4.5.2 Long Term storage – Effects on bioactive stability, An Accelerated Aging Study

Aim

During the Antarctic analogue mission (WP5) it is envisioned that plant samples will be harvested throughout and stored at -20 °C. They will then be shipped at this temperature to CNR and LIT laboratories for quantitative analysis. The timeline from the first harvest until arrival to the laboratories may run from February to December 2018, resulting in some samples being stored for at least 10 months. It has been shown previously that long-term freezer storage has a detrimental effect on various bioactive compounds, however these effects are strongly plant species-dependent (Puupponen-Pimiä et al, 2003). This experiment aims to examine whether long-term storage has an effect on the carotenoid and lycopene content of 3 plant species which may be grown on the MFT.

Accelerated Stability Tests

Shelf life is commonly estimated using two types of stability testing: real-time stability tests and accelerated stability tests. In real-time stability testing, a product is stored at recommended storage conditions until analysis. In accelerated stability tests, a product is stored at elevated stress conditions (such as temperature, humidity, and pH). Degradation at the recommended storage conditions can be predicted using known relationships between the acceleration factor and the degradation rate. Temperature is the most common acceleration factor and its relationship with the degradation rate is characterized by the Arrhenius equation.

Arrhenius Equation:

“The rule of 10”

The temperature coefficient (Q_{10}) represents the factor by which the rate (R) of a reaction increases for every 10-degree rise in the temperature (T).

$$Q_{10} = [R_1/R_2]^{10/(T_2-T_1)}$$

For the typical reaction $Q_{10} = 2$.

- **A (Accelerated aging rate) = $Q_{10}^{(T_e - T_a)/10}$**

T_a = Temperature of storage (storage of samples in Antarctica is -20 °C)

T_e = Tested temperature

- **B (Accelerated aging time duration) = desired time/A**

A timeline of 6 months and 12 months was tested

In this study, $T_e = 55$ °C

12 months

$$A = 2^{(55 - (-20))/10} = 2^{7.5} = 181.01$$

$$B = 365 \text{ days} / 181.01 = 2.01 \text{ days @ } 55 \text{ °C}$$

6 months

$$A = 2^{(55 - (-20))/10} = 2^{7.5} = 181.01$$

$$B = 182 \text{ days} / 181.01 = 1 \text{ day @ } 55 \text{ °C}$$

Method

Samples tested were tomato, rocket and radicchio. Commercially grown samples were bought, freeze-dried and ground into a fine powder. Samples were separated into treatments and either analysed immediately (0 months), stored at 55 °C for 24 h (6 months) or stored at 55 °C for 48 h (12 months) prior to analysis. Samples were analysed for total carotenoids and lycopene content as per methods in section 1.3.

Results:

The carotenoid content of the samples was highest in rocket and lowest in radicchio (Figure 1.8.4.29). There did not appear to be a change in carotenoid content over time in both the rocket and radicchio samples. However, a decrease in carotenoid content was observed in the tomato samples, with highest values achieved in the month 0 samples.

With regards to lycopene, highest values were seen in tomato samples and no lycopene was observed in the rocket samples (Figure 1.8.4.30). Similar to carotenoids, lycopene appeared to decrease in the tomato samples over time.

On the other hand, lycopene levels increased over time in the radicchio samples.

Figure 1.8.4.29 Carotenoid content in various plant species over time

Figure 1.8.4.30 Lycopene content in various plant species over time

Conclusion of Long Term Storage (Accelerated Aging) Study.

Long-term storage of plant samples, as represented by “accelerated aging” appears to have a detrimental effect on the bioactive content of tomatoes. As this has not been observed to the same extent in either rocket or radicchio, this may have implications for plant selection for the Antarctic mission.

While this study appears to indicate that bioactives degrade over time in certain plant species, further analysis would be required. It would need to be repeated to include more replicates and also more plant species. Real-time stability tests would also need to be performed to correlate the results with those obtained during accelerated stability tests.

1.8.4.6 Updated References:

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1.8.4.7 Appendix: Packing List for Antarctica

FREE EQUIPMENT									
Element/Component	Qty	Mass per element (kg)	Total mass (kg)	Mass comments	Dimensions per element (cm) (L x W x H)	Other misc. notes	+30 degC storable (Y/N)	-50 degC storable (Y/N)	Temp Range degC
Non-Boxed									
Refractometer	1	0.42	0.42		19 x 11 x 7		Y	N	10 - 40 degC
Deionised Water Bottle	1	0.03258	0.03258		14 x 8 x 5		Y	Y	
Paper Towel roll	2	4	8		40 x 24.5		Y	Y	
Plastic Pipette Dropper (Box of 500)	1	1	1		17 x 22 x 27		Y	Y	
Nitrate Meter	1	0.05	0.05		16.4 x 2.9 x 2		Y	N	
Weigh Boat	1000	0.0023	2.3		4 x 8 x 8		Y	Y	
Chlorophyll Meter	1	0.277	0.277		17 x 8 x 5		Y	N	
Colorimeter	1	0.5	0.5		9 x 8 x 22		Y	N	20 - 55 degC
Colorimeter Charger	1	0.181	0.181		6 x 10 x 7		Y	N	20 - 55 degC
Penetrometer	1	1.194	1.194		28 x 20 x 7		Y	N	0 - 50 degC
Aluminium Bags Small	500	0.0088	4.4		21 x 12		Y	Y	
Aluminium Bags Medium	500	0.01094	5.5		23 x 14		Y	Y	
Aluminium Bags Large	500	0.0177	9		29 x 18		Y	Y	
Aluminium Bags Extra Large	500	0.0214	10.7		31 x 22		Y	Y	
Minus 80 degC Freezer	1	60	60		50 x 66 x 68	Prefer not to be stored above 30°C due to overworking the compressor	Y	N	
Freeze Drier Chamber	1	9.5	9.5		35 x 65		Y	N	5 - 40 deg C
Freeze Dryer Dry Pump	1	26.2	26.2		43.2 x 30.2 x 30		Y	N	10 - 40 degC
Freeze Drier	1	68.2	68.2		72 x 83 x 67		Y	N	10 - 40 degC
Weighing Scale	1	1	1		19 x 30 x 8		Y	N	10 - 40 degC
Spare Drying Chamber	1	9.5	9.5		35 x 65		Y	N	5 - 40 deg C
Freeze Drier Critical Spares (Box of Spares)	1	1	1		40 x 20 x 25		Y	N	5 - 40 deg C
Battery (AA)	16	0.024	0.384		5 x 1.5		Y	N	minus 10 - 50 degC
Battery (9V)	2	0.046	0.092		4.7 x 2.7		Y	N	minus 10 - 50 degC
Sensory Booth Tent	1	TBC	TBC		1000x1000x2000	Stored Folded in Travel Bag	Y	Y	
Folding Table (For Sensory)	1	TBC	TBC		TBC	Stored Folded	Y	Y	
Folding Chair (For Sensory)	1	TBC	TBC		TBC	Stored Folded	Y	Y	
Portable Light (For Sensory)	1	TBC	TBC		TBC		TBC	TBC	

1.9 Addendum 1: General Detailed Procedures for Analogue Mission

Introduction

EDEN ISS was a work-in progress exercise during 2015-2017. First key steps were a) the selection of species by WUR and b) the definition of the growing conditions baselines for the MTF by the consortium. After that, CNR and LIT:

- i) screened the selected species for relevant quality parameters to be tested,
- ii) defined and identified for each of the selected species the Quality Driving Attributes (QDA),
- iii) screened and tested all methods to be used during the pre-mission, mission and post-mission activities, to evaluate quality attributes of the produce (technical, analytical and sensory)
- iv) evaluated environmental and growing variables that could be modulated in the MTF to influence relevant aspect of food quality and safety of the produce obtained with pre-mission experimental activities
- v) screened pathogens to be tested for safety reasons
- vi) screened available microbiological tests to verify the presence of pathogens in vegetables before consume
- vii) tested suitable procedures for produce sanitisation prior consume by the NM-III crew
- viii) provided all necessary material to DLR for quality and safety activities to be performed during the mission.

All the listed activities were reported in due documents (Reference list)

All the described work included a relevant level of uncertainty because the project was running with on-line adjustments and major fine-tuning of relevant aspects that would affect the Food Quality and Safety planning for the Mission and post-mission activities.

At this stage, several of the mentioned uncertainties are fixed and the overall planned Food Quality and Safety activity should be reviewed to the highest level of detail possible.

Furthermore, the results of the pre-mission experimental activities performed by IBAF, ISA, LIT and WUR, could guide planning of mission activities to maximise the practical, technical and scientific outputs.

The aim of the present document is to provide Paul Zabel (and any crewmember at the NM-III) with a detailed hands-on manual listing and describing activities needed for the topic Food Quality and Safety during the mission. The manual should also provide sufficient information for the crew members to make decisions about activities that cannot be planned in advance if decisions have to be taken during the mission with no possibilities of providing feedback with CNR and LIT in home laboratories.

The mission is a unique occasion to:

- a) produce vegetables for consumption in a remote environment,
- b) perform experimental activities on food quality and safety on vegetables produced under a fully controlled environment in a remote location
- c) test, on-site and after transfer back to home laboratories, food quality and safety parameters on samples produced during the mission.

It is crucial to harvest all possible data and samples during the mission to maximise the technical and scientific outputs of the EDEN ISS project. Vegetables have been produced by other initiatives in remote polar locations (Zabel et al. 2016). Another project (TIME SCALE <http://timescale.eu/Pages/TIME-SCALE-project.aspx>) is running at the moment by another consortium, on vegetable production under controlled conditions, in the same H2020 call. However, our project is the most focussed on the aspects of food production and its quality and safety evaluation. Salad, as other plant material was produced even on the ISS but the evaluation of the produce in terms of food characteristics has been done only sporadically (Colla et al. 2007, Wheeler 2017).

Hence, for practical purposes the manual includes two sections

Section 1 **routine activities**

Section 2 **experimental activities**. (this section will be implemented during the mission)

SECTION 1 ROUTINE ACTIVITIES

Routine activities are all those that Paul and the crew will perform on selected harvest for consumption.

Most of the produce will be harvested just for consumption by the crew with no further experimental treatments other than the routine growing under the baseline conditions. Nevertheless, these harvests contain a vast amount of information, beside its quantity, that should be measured and recorded to the possible. CNR and LIT have sent equipment and material to perform numerous analyses. Here we detail the procedures necessary to guarantee that vegetables are safe, the tests that can be performed and that useful data can be recorded on harvest for consumption with minimal time investment by Paul and the crew.

Routine activity for FQS. Paul will perform several harvests to feed the crew during the mission. Our goals are

- i) to ensure that food is safe
- ii) to measure and record quality and safety data.

Actions should be tailored to the produce obtained. The chef should define the minimum amount of each produce she needs to serve the all crew or to prepare a specific meal. This could influence the cropping area of vegetables, particularly that of salad, while tomato cucumber and pepper are fixed by the number of high compartments.

HARVEST

Details of harvest procedures for FQS sample collection are described in the PROCEDURE: “EDEN_3220_Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis_PRE”

The action of harvest will separate the produce from the rest of the plant. Two main organic matter streams are generated the “Produce” and the “Waste”.

A relevant parameter to be collected is the **HARVEST INDEX (HI)**

The **Harvest Index** is a relevant parameter because it measures the relative importance of the produce with respect to the total biomass produced. Waste material in Bioregenerative Life Support Systems (BLSS) should be managed for use and recycling, then its quantification and qualification is as important as those

on produce are. To calculate the **HI** both streams of biomass should be quantified. It is relevant to recall that our plant vegetables contain between 90 to 95% of water. Water can be lost quickly (in terms of minutes) depending on the conditions of storage. Then the fresh weight (FW) is a necessary but not sufficient measure of the product quantity. Hence, we suggest taking samples from harvest lots, to measure the **Dry Weight** of the biomasses obtained. This would also allow expressing the **HI** with reference to the **fresh biomasses** or **dry biomasses obtained**. **We suggest measuring both.**

It is also important to recall that plant tissues remain alive even when detached from the mother plant and even when chopped. Alive cells respire and perform metabolism thereby consuming resources such as carbohydrate and changing their own metabolic state affecting for example antioxidant content. **Always remember to work as fast as possible to collect samples that should be representative of what you want to measure.**

Two types of harvest will take place in the MTF:

- a) **total harvest**
- b) **spread harvest.**

Furthermore, produce might require selection after harvest, this would generate further waste streams.

CASE a) total harvest

Total harvest occurs, for example for some salad types (when the full bunch of salad is harvested) and for all crops types at the end of the growing cycle. In case of total harvest of the “crop”, **produce** and **waste** are generated at the same time. Separation will take place in the MTF. The two streams will be brought to the NM-III for further processing avoiding that they dry –up or freeze to below 0°C.

Before moving to the MTF

- a) prepare all necessary tools to be used for sample harvest and processing in the MTF after transfer to NM-III (pre-tared aluminium bags -two decimal points at least-, plastic bags, marker pen, lab book, scissors, isothermal container, scale....)
- b) prepare all necessary tools to be used after coming back to the NM-III with harvested samples for processing in the NM-III (marker pen, lab book, scissors,....)
- c) switch on all relevant equipment that will be used for sample analysis and further sample processing (Freeze drier, scales, and so on)

When in the MTF

- a) take a sufficient number of photos of the “crop” before harvesting, possibly shoots and roots.
- b) harvest produce (Produce1)
- c) confine Produce1 into labelled plastic bag(s);
- d) harvest waste (Waste1),
- e) confine Waste1 into labelled plastic bag(s), for roots, blot them dry with clean paper before further steps;
- f) record relevant data of the harvest in lab book (species and cultivar, date, time of the day, tray harvested, notes...)
- g) use an isothermal container for temporary storage in the MTF and for transport to the NM-III.

NOTES:

Harvest as close as possible to the time of transfer to NM-III. Be sure that there is sufficient time in the NM-III to further process the produce and waste ASAP after return. Additional care should be taken if panel testing is planned.

Weighing of the two streams (Produce1 and Waste1) can take place in NM-III. This would speed up work of Paul while in the MTF, and make it easier for other crewmembers to help, if needed. This is the reason why we suggest the use of pre-tared bags even for the harvest that should be consumed. This avoids bias due to water vapour loss from harvest until fresh weight measurements.

With some types of produce, a second waste (Waste2) can be generated when preparing the produce for consumption. In the case of pepper, for example, the petiole, the placental tissue and the seeds, are normally separated from the fruit flesh and discarded. Yellow, dead and dry leaves, if present, central axis in partially bolted lettuce, shoots in basil and parsley are also fractions that are not consumed and go to Waste2. This should be considered as described in the following chapters.

After returning from the MTF

- weigh bags with Produce1
- weigh bags with Waste1

TABLE A1. 1. Work flow for Routine Total Harvest.

With no Waste2	With Waste2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag; • select edible (Produce2) and non-edible (Waste2) fractions of Produce1. •
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of Produce1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight in lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variables (hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available; • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce1 to cook for crew consumption. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Produce2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight in lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variables (hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available; • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce2 to cook for crew consumption.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weigh Waste2 • Merge Waste1 and Waste2; • Weight merged waste fresh weight • take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste1+2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs.

Data after this procedure

1) Total harvested fresh matter; 2) Produce1 fresh weight; 3) Waste1 fresh weight; 4) Harvest index (FW); 5) Produce 2 fresh weight; 6) Waste2 fresh weight; 7) % dry matter produce1 or produce 2; 8) % dry matter Waste1 or merged waste; 9) HI (DW). Other data depending on measurements (nitrate concentration, hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content).

CASE b) spread harvest (SH)

Spread harvest occurs for pepper, tomato and cucumber and for some salad types, (refer to WUR planning). In this case, we have a NON-KILLING Harvest (NKH) type and a KILLING Harvest (KH) type. NKH occurs, for example, when a number of ripe tomato fruits are harvested, and the plant remains in place for further production. The waste material at NKH originates from the selection of the edible fraction of the produce. KH occurs at the end of the growth cycle when the whole plant is removed from the tray and the produce and total waste (root and shoot) are collected. When KH occurs in plants like tomato, pepper and cucumber, waste originates from both the root system and the stem and leaves (and unripe fruit if present). The two waste streams should be processed separately, to allow for the quantification of the root/shoot ratio, a relevant agronomic variable.

Furthermore, plants like tomato can have axillary shoots or old leaves that should be removed during the season, this generate a waste stream too, that has to be collected and weighted and summed up to other waste amounts.

CASE b.1 SH on salad type crops

Each harvest must be numbered sequentially. The first spread harvest would be SH at time 1 SHT1, the second SHT2, then SHTn and SHTF for the final harvest.

For any SHn

Before moving to the MTF

- d) prepare all necessary tools to be used for sample harvest and processing in the MTF before transfer to NM-III (pre-tared aluminium bags -two decimal points at least-, plastic bags, marker pen, lab book, scissors, isothermal container, scale....);
- e) prepare all necessary tools to be used after coming back to NM-III with harvested samples for processing in NM-III (marker pen, lab book, scissors,...);
- f) switch on all relevant equipment that will be used for sample analysis and further sample processing (freeze drier, scales, and so on);

When in the MTF

- h) take a sufficient number of photos of the “crop” before harvesting, preferably shoots and roots.;
- i) harvest produce (Produce1);
- j) confine Produce1 into labelled plastic bag(s);
- k) record relevant data of the harvest in lab book (species and cultivar, date, time of the day, tray harvested, notes...);
- l) use an isothermal container for temporary storage in the MTF and for transport to NM-III.

NOTES:

Harvest as close as possible to the time of transfer to NM-III. Be sure that there is sufficient time in the NM-III to further process the produce and waste ASAP after return. Additional care should be taken if panel testing is planned.

Weighing of the two streams (Produce1 and Waste1) can take place in NM-III. This would speed up work of Paul while in the MTF, and make it easier for other crewmembers to help, if needed. This is the reason why we suggest the use of pre-tared bags even for the harvest that should be consumed. This avoids bias due to water vapour loss from harvest until fresh weight measurements.

With some types of produce, a second waste (Waste2) can be generated when preparing the produce for consumption. In the case of pepper, for example, the petiole, the placental tissue and the seeds, are normally

separated from the fruit flesh and discarded. Yellow, dead and dry leaves, if present, central axis in partially bolted lettuce, shoots in basil and parsley are also fractions that are not consumed and go to Waste2. This should be considered as described in the following chapters.

After returning from the MTF

- weigh bags with Produce1
- weight bags with Waste2

TABLE A1. 2 Spread Harvest, for salad type crops.

With no Waste2	With Waste2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag • select edible (Produce2) and non-edible (Waste2) fractions of Produce1.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Produce1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variable (hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce1 to cook for crew consumption.. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Produce2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variable (hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce2 to cook for crew consumption..
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weigh Waste 2 • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (two decimal point at least); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR –LIT labs.

Data after this procedure

1) Fresh matter for each HT and total; 2) Produce1 fresh weight for each HT ad total; 3) Waste 1 fresh weight for each HT and total; 4) Harvest index (FW); 5) Produce2 fresh weight for each HT and total; 6) waste 2 fresh weight for each HT and total; 7) % dry matter Produce1 or Produce 2 for each HT and total; 8)

% dry matter waste 1 or merged waste for each HT and total; 9) HI (DW). Other data depending on measurements (nitrate concentration hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content).

For Final harvest (SHTF)

Follow procedure of TABLE A1. 1.

CASE b.2 SH on tomato type crops

Each harvest must be numbered sequentially. The first spread harvest would be SH at time 1 SHT1, the second SHT2, then SHTn and SHTF for the final harvest.

For any SHn

Follow procedure of TABLE A1. 2.

For final harvest (SHTF)

CONSIDER SUB SAMPLING WASTE3 and WASTE4 at the MTF if their amount is too large to use the pre-tared bags. In this case bring the scale in MTF. Weigh the total Waste3 and Waste4 amount and sub sample 500 g for each waste type and proceed as indicated in the following.

Before moving to the MTF

- g) prepare all necessary tools to be used for sample harvest and processing in the MTF after transfer to NM-III (pre-tared aluminium bags -two decimal points at least-, plastic bags, marker pen, lab book, scissors, isothermal container, scale....)
- h) prepare all necessary tools to be used after coming back to NM-III with harvested samples processing in the NM-III (marker pen, lab book, scissors,....)
- i) switch on all relevant equipment that will be used for sample analysis and further sample processing (freeze drier, scales, and so on)

When in the MTF

- j) take a sufficient number of photos of the "crop" before harvesting, preferably shoots and roots.;
- k) harvest produce (Produce1)
- l) confine Produce1 into labelled plastic bag(s);
- m) harvest shoot waste (Waste3),
- n) confine Waste3 into labelled plastic bag(s),
- o) harvest root waste (Waste4), for roots, blot them dry with clean paper before further steps
- p) confine Waste4 into labelled plastic bag(s),
- q) record relevant data of the harvest on lab book (specie and cultivar, date, time of the day, try harvested, notes...)
- r) use an isothermal container for temporary storage in the MTF and for transport to the NM-III.

NOTES:

Harvest as close as possible to transfer to NM-III. Be sure that there is sufficient time in the NM-III to further processing produce and waste ASAP after return. Additional care should be taken if panel testing is planned.

Weighing of the Produce1, Waste3 and Waste4 can take place in the NM-III. This would speed up work of Paul while in the MTF, and make easier for other crewmembers to help, if needed. This is the reason why we suggest the use of pre-tared bags even for the harvest that should be consumed. This avoids bias due to water vapour loss from harvest till measurement of the fresh weight.

With some type of produce, a further waste (Waste2) can be generated when preparing the produce for consume. In the case of pepper, for example, the petiole, the placental tissue and the seeds, are normally separated from

the fruit flesh and discarded. Yellow, dead and dry leaves if present, central axis in partially bolted lettuce, shoots in basil and parsley are also fractions that are not consumed and go to Waste2. This should be considered as described in the following chapters.

After returning from the MTF

- weigh bags with Produce1
- weigh bags with Waste3
- weigh bags with Waste4

TABLE A1. 3 Final Spread Harvest on tomato type plants

With no Waste2	With Waste2
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract Produce1 from bag; • select edible (Produce2) and non-edible (Waste2) fractions of Produce1. •
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Produce1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book ((to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR –LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variable (hardness, color, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce1 to cook for crew consumption... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Produce2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book ((to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR –LIT labs; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); • test other variable (hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content) if relevant and time is available • sanitise product; • send remaining Produce2 to cook for crew consumption..
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste3, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book ((to at least two decimal point accuracy); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs. • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weigh Waste2 • take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste2, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book ((to at least two decimal point accuracy); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste4, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (two decimal point at least); 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste3, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (two decimal point at least);

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 3 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste4, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (two decimal point at least); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs.

TABLE A1. 4 Parameters

Parameters	Description	Units	Notes
Harvest Index (fresh or dry)	Ratio between the food harvested and the waste material	% or dimensionless ratio	One decimal point is normally sufficient
Fresh Weight	Weight in grams of the biomass as it is harvested	g	Depending on the weight measured use at least decimal point to account for not less than 10% of the measured weight
Dry Weight	Weight in grams of the biomass after drying to constant weight	g	Depending on the weight measured use at least decimal point to account for not less than 10% of the measured weight
Spread Harvest	A sequence of more than one harvest event that takes place on the same plant and crop		
Total Harvest	A harvest event that ends the crop		

Data after this procedure

1) Fresh matter for each Harvest Time (HT) and total; 2) Produce1 fresh weight for each HT ad total; 3) Waste 1 fresh weight for each HT and total; 4) Harvest index (FW); 5) Produce2 fresh weight for each HT and total; 6) waste 2 fresh weight for each HT and total; 7) % dry matter produce1 or produce 2 for each HT and total; 8) % dry matter waste 1 or merged waste for each HT and total; 9) fresh and dry weight of waste 3 and 4; 10) HI (DW). Other data depending on measurements (nitrate hardness, colour, BRIX, chlorophyll content).

References Addendum 1

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1.10 Addendum 2: Detailed Procedures for Analogue Mission: the case of *E. Sativa*

Eruca sativa Mill. (Rocket)

CASE a) total harvest (as planned)

Expected Produce and Waste availability for one rocket tray.

NOTE: details are for tray because this will be the cropping unit.

Crop	FW (g m ⁻²)	FW (g tray ⁻¹ 6.2*0.24)	Plants tray ⁻¹	Expected g fw plant ⁻¹	dm %	Expected g dw plant ⁻¹	Duration (weeks)	Remark
Rocket Produce	6200	1450	75	19.33	7*	1.35	4	Single harvest
Rocket waste (roots)	620*	145	75	1.93	6*	0.116	4	Probably impossible to separate roots of each plant

* estimated from pre-mission activities.

Before moving to the MTF

- s) prepare all necessary tools to be used for sample harvest and processing in the MTF:
- scissor for plant harvest;
 - portable camera for extra photos of crop, shoots and roots;
 - plastic gloves;
 - paper to blot dry the root system;
 - coolbox;
 - plastic bucket to help collecting Produce during harvesting;
 - one (or more) large pre-tared plastic bag for the Produce plus seal to close it;
 - one (or more) large pre-tared plastic bag for the Waste plus seal to close it;
 - lab book for notes;
 - pencil;
 - marker pen.
- (pre-tared (zeroed) large bags could be tared (zeroed) with two decimal points at least).
- t) prepare all necessary tools to be used after coming back to the NM-III with harvested samples for their processing;
- scissor, knife and scalpel for sampling the plant material harvested;
 - plastic gloves;
 - lab book for notes and data recording;
 - pencil;
 - marker pen.
- u) switch on all relevant equipment that will be used for sample analysis and further sample processing;
- freeze drier,
 - nitrate meter
 - scales, ...and so on.

When in the MTF

- m) take a sufficient number of photos of the “crop” before harvesting, possibly shoots and roots.
- n) harvest produce (Produce1)
- o) confine Produce1 into labelled and pre-tared bag(s);
- p) harvest waste (Waste1);
- q) for roots, blot them dry with clean paper before further steps,
- r) confine Waste1 into labelled and pre-tares bag(s);
- s) record relevant data of the harvest in lab book (see the chapter Labelling in this document for detail);
- t) use the cool box for temporary storage in the MTF and for transport to the NM-III.

NOTES:

Harvest as close as possible to the time of transfer to NM-III. Be sure that there is sufficient time in the NM-III to further process the Produce and waste ASAP after return. Additional care should be taken if panel testing is planned.

Weighing of the two streams (Produce1 and Waste1) can take place in NM-III. This would speed up work of Paul while in the MTF, and make it easier for other crewmembers to help, if needed. This is the reason why we suggest the use of pre-tared bags even for the harvest that should be consumed. This avoids bias due to water vapour loss from harvest until fresh weight measurements.

We assume that there will be no further waste than the root system. NO Waste2).

These procedures for sample preparation and harvesting for the MTF should also be replicated for the ISPR Module Harvest.

After returning from the MTF

- weigh bags with Produce1 and record data in lab book
- weigh bags with Waste1 and record data in lab book

TABLE 1. Work flow for Routine Rocket Total Harvest (one tray).

With no Waste2	With Waste2
Extract Produce1 from bag.	•
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 4 sub samples of about 10 g each, of Produce1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight in lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR–LIT labs and store them at -20°C; • test nitrate ion concentration (NO₃⁻); please, while following the provided procedure, please take care of: i) carefully sub sample the Produce, ii) carefully weigh the amount of Produce you use for NO₃⁻ extraction. Procedure indicate to use one g of fresh Produce, it does not make a huge difference if it is not a precise g, provided that you record the precise weight of the Produce you extract, so that NO₃⁻ concentration can be calculated on the f.w. basis. If you find a too high NO₃⁻ concentration (if it does not fit in the calibration limits) just dilute the extract as needed with distilled water. If the reading is too low either, extract twice the 	•

<p>amount of sample in ½ of water (4 times more concentrated) or just conclude that NO₃⁻ is too low to be detected and hence it is not dangerous.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test colour; • estimate chlorophyll content); • sanitise product; (<u>see the chapter Sanitisation procedure in this document for detail</u>). • send remaining Produce1 to cook for crew consumption. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take 4 sub samples of about 10 g each, of the Waste1, insert each in a new separate pre-tared aluminium bag; • record the total fresh weight (sample +bag) of each sub sample in the lab book (to at least two decimal point accuracy); • discard extra waste; • freeze dry each bag to constant weight and record total dry weight on lab book; • keep dried samples for transfer back to CNR-LIT labs and store them at -20°C. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •

Data obtained with this procedure

- 1) Produce1 fresh weight;
- 2) Waste1 fresh weight;
- 3) Total harvested fresh matter;
- 4) Harvest index (FW);
- 5) % dry matter Produce1;
- 6) % dry matter Waste1;
- 7) Harvest index (DW);
- 8) Nitrate concentration;
- 9) Colour;
- 10) Chlorophyll estimation.

Sanitisation procedure for the rocket Produce.

(Expected Produce amount 1450 g – one tray).

Use provided file for solution volume calculations. ([Preparation of sanitisation solutions.xls](#)).

The sanitizer used is concentrated Amuchina and the following steps are performed:

Sanitisation with Amuchina.

Use large plastic washbasin;

Put the Produce in the washbasin and add a sufficient solution volume to cover the product with the sanitisation solution.

The result of adding 1000 ml solution to 100 g of Produce is shown in figure below.

This Solution volume/Produce ratio seems sufficient for 100 g of Produce.

100 g rocket leaves

1000 ml of sanitisation solution volume

As described in the file excel, to prepare a 1000 ml sanitisation solution, 20 ml of Amuchina is added to 980 ml of tap water.

Use 1000 ml and 100 ml graduated cylinder provided to measure the volumes;

pour 20 ml Amuchina in the 100 ml cylinder

pour 980 ml of water in the 1000 ml cylinder

pour the Amuchina volume in the water cylinder,

close the 1000 ml cylinder with a square piece of Parafilm, and while holding it in place with one hand mix by inverting the cylinder 4 times (take care to avoid spills and particularly take care to your eyes).

pour the solution into the washbasin with the produce

repeat as necessary to be sure that all Produce is in contact with the solution.

use disposable gloves to help you mix the product in the basin.

Leave Produce in solution for 15 minutes, by gently mixing every 5 minutes.

Discard solution.

Add water to at least covering the Produce, mix gently 2 minutes and discard water.

Repeat washing 4 times or as needed to eliminate smelling of Amuchina solution from Produce.

Eliminate excess water from Produce with salad spinner.

Enclose Produce in a plastic bag, close bag and store in fridge at 4°C until use.

For 1450 g of rocket Produce total sanitization solution volume will be 14l.

Sanitisation with Sodium Bicarbonate.

The sanitisation procedure with Sodium bicarbonate is similar to that with Amuchina. The main differences are

- u) Sodium bicarbonate is solid and must be solubilised
- v) concentration is 5% and is expressed in g/volume

To prepare 1 litre of solution of sodium bicarbonate weigh 50 g sodium bicarbonate and dissolve in 1000 ml of tap water:

- weight the sodium bicarbonate and add it into a cylinder containing 1000 ml of tap water,
- cover with parafilm and mix as previously indicated.
- make sure that all Produce is in contact with the solution.
- add more solution if needed, and if necessary, use plastic gloves to mix Produce.
- leave Produce in solution for 15 minutes, by gently mixing every 5 minutes.
- discard solution.
- add water to approximate volume, mix gently 2 minutes and discard water.
- eliminate excess water from Produce with salad spinner.
- enclose Produce in a plastic bag, close bag and store in fridge at 4°C until use.

For 1450 g of Produce use this solution, contains 210 grams of bicarbonate and 14 l of tap water.

Labelling

Labelling all samples produced during the mission is important and a common labelling procedure should be defined, agreed and adopted. Some of the samples will be analysed by different partners during the post-mission activity, and each should have access to relevant info about each sample. Sample coding should be written on bags and tubes where samples will be stored. This labelling should be unequivocal but concise.

Our proposal is to label bags and tubes as follows:

dd/m/y-ACT –XX- SX

were

dd= day

m=month

y=year

ACT= defines that these samples are of the Food Quality and Safety activity.

XX= progressive number for the set of samples defined by the previous codes.

SX= code for sub sampling **when relevant**. E.g. S1, S2 (this can be useful only in special cases in general I will skip it)

Assuming that rocket will be harvested the 28/3/2018

1 Large pre-tared plastic bag for Produce1 transfer from FLG to NMIII lab. Labelling of this bag will be:

28/03/2018- FQS 1

1 large pre tared plastic bag for Waste1 transfer from FLG to NMII lab. Labelling of this bag will be:

28/03/2018- FQS 2

4 medium size pre-tared aluminium bags for the 4 sub-samples of fresh produce (appr. 10 g each) for sample freeze drying. Labelling of these bags will be:

28/03/2018- FQS 3

28/03/2018- FQS 4

28/03/2018- FQS 5

28/03/2018- FQS 6

4 medium size pre-tared aluminium bags for the 4 sub-samples of fresh waste (appr. 10 g each) for sample freeze drying. Labelling of these bags will be

28/03/2018- FQS 7

28/03/2018- FQS 8

28/03/2018- FQS 9

28/03/2018- FQS 10

Labelling should be written by a black marker pen (to be tested in advance) on two opposite sides on the bag and on the tubes.

In addition to labels on bags and tubes, a **Laboratory Book** should be compiled. All other relevant info about each set of samples, sample and sub samples should be defined and recorded. For example:

In this specific harvesting the Lab Book record will be:

dd/mm/2018 Operator: Paul Zabel <i>Eruca sativa</i> Mill (Rocket) Activity: FQS									
Routine Harvest Tray n° L3-2L									
Further notes: Extra photos recorded in: detail the file name for extra photo taken									
Samples from: 28/03/2018-FQS 1 to 28/03/2018-FQS 10									
Sample N	Plant Species	Material type	Day-Time of harvest	Treatment	Replicate	Bag tare (g)	Gross fresh weight (g)	Gross dry weight (g)	Other relevant info:
28/03/2018 - FQS 1	Rocket	Produce1 total harvest	10:30	baseline	Not relevant	25.55	1475.55	127.05	No damages leaves, 10 cmr external row with no plants.
28/03/2018 - FQS 2	Rocket	Waste1 total harvest	10:35	baseline	Not relevant	15.27	155.27	23.97	White roots, less roots in left side of the tray.
28/03/2018 - FQS 3	Rocket	Produce sub sample	10:40	baseline	I	5.43	15.55	XX	Freeze drying completed on day 30/03/2018 time 16:30
28/03/2018 - FQS 4	Rocket	Produce sub sample	12.00	baseline	II	5.05	14.99	XX	As before
28/03/2018 - FQS 5	Rocket	Produce sub sample	12.05	baseline	III	5.07	15.30	XX	As before
28/03/2018 - FQS 6	Rocket	Produce sub sample	12.10	baseline	IV	4.99	15.27	XX	As before
28/03/2018 - FQS 7	Rocket	Waste sub sample	12.15		I	5.16	15.16	15.52	Freeze drying completed on day 30/03/2018 time 16:30
28/03/2018 - FQS 8	Rocket	Waste sub sample	12.20		II	XX	XX	XX	As before
28/03/2018 - FQS 9	Rocket	Waste sub sample	12.25		III	XX	XX	XX	As before
28/03/2018 - FQS 10	Rocket	Waste sub sample	12.30		IV	XX	XX	XX	As before

Sub-sampling and replicates

Sampling is dramatically important to determine significant analytical data acquisition. Replicates allow us to calculate statistical variables of the samples obtained and to perform statistical analysis of results. It is crucial that variability is reduced or samples. Operating carefully, for example when taking measurements reduced variability.

When sub-sampling non-uniform populations of leaves from a crop (like in the case of rocket), it is important that all types of leaves are sampled in each sub sample in the same relative abundance as they are present in the total harvest. If size of units of the sample (leaves for example) is not compatible with the size of the sample special care should be taken.

In this case, the final sub sample size is 10 g. Unfortunately, a large and old leaf can be heavier than 10 g but it is not representative of the characteristics of all the population of leaves present in the sample the i) it cannot be samples as the sub sample ii) it cannot be excluded from the sample.

In other words, it is difficult to collect in a 10 g sub sample all the leaves type in the right relative amount. In this case proceed as follow.

- a) produce a first sub sample large enough to contain all component types in the right proportion (representative sub sample, approximately 100-200 g)
- b) chop the first sub sample in small pieces and mix them to uniformity;
- c) collect 4 subsamples

1.11 Addendum 3: Procedure for Nitrate measurement during the Mission

Reference to file EDEN_3234_Quality Measurements_NitrateMeter_Operations_PRE

Why is the addendum necessary?

The Procedure on Nitrate measurement describes appropriately the use of the equipment that was sent to NMIII for *in situ* analysis of nitrate content of produce.

We realized that it does not include:

- i) a short and clear description of the reasons of nitrate measurements;
- ii) practical indications on how to avoid misleading measurements due to sample heterogeneity;
- iii) a practical tool to calculate the nitrate content in measured samples;
- iv) suggestions on how to deal with produce that shows very high nitrate content;

These are necessary for proper management of this relevant quality and safety variable.

i) Reasons of nitrate measurements in vegetable food

Scientific Background.

Nitrate abundance in plant food has quality and safety relevance. Plants take up different forms of nitrogen from the environment; one of the most relevant is NO_3^- . Nitrogen availability is one key factor limiting plant growth and productivity, it also affects the amount of proteins and other compounds in plant tissues and hence quality. NO_3^- is taken up at the root level, and it is in general transported to the aerial part of the plant where it is reduced in a two-step process to nitrite and then ammonia that is used for the synthesis of nitrogen compounds (amino acids and so on). Reduction requires energy and ammonia should be used rapidly. For this reason, when NO_3^- is abundant, the plant accumulates it in the vacuole to have it in large amounts when required. Light activates the biochemical pathway leading to NO_3^- reduction and ammonia use depends on photosynthetic products availability and growth. Hence, in general terms, low light and high NO_3^- availability promotes accumulation of nitrate in plant tissues. Accumulation also depends on the species and on the type of tissue. Leaves contain in general more nitrate than tubers and seeds, but

TABLE A3. 1. From Santamaria 2006 DOI: 10.1002/jsfa.2351

Table 4. Classification of vegetables according to NO_3^- content (mg kg^{-1} fm)				
Very low (<200)	Low (200–500)	Middle (500–1000)	High (1000–2500)	Very high (>2500)
Artichoke	Broccoli	Cabbage	Celeriac	Celery
Asparagus	Carrot	'Cima di rapa' (broccoli rab)	Chinese cabbage	Chervil
Broad bean	Cauliflower	Dill	Endive	Cress
Brussels sprouts	Cucumber	'Radicchio'	Escarola	Lamb's lettuce
Eggplant	Pumpkin	Savoy cabbage	Fennel	Lettuce
Garlic	'Puntarelle' chicory	Turnip	Kohlrabi	Radish
Onion			Leaf chicory	Red beetroot
Green bean			Leek	Rocket
Melon			Parsley	Spinach
Mushroom				Swiss chard
Pea				
Pepper				
Potato				
Summer squash				
Sweet potato				
Tomato				
Watermelon				

in a bunch of salad, very young leaves can have low NO_3^- while old leaves can have high NO_3^- content. (See Table A3. 1 for examples of NO_3^- content in various plant foods). The amount of nitrate ion in vegetable food can also depend on storage and cooking procedure. Therefore, we can expect a large variability on NO_3^- content in vegetables in general and even in MTF products.

TABLE A3. 2. COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1258/2011 of 2 December 2011

3.12.2011 EN Official Journal of the European Union L 320/17

ANNEX

Section 1: Nitrate

Foodstuffs ⁽¹⁾		Maximum levels (mg NO_3^- /kg)	
1.1	Fresh spinach (<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>) ⁽²⁾		3 500
1.2	Preserved, deep-frozen or frozen spinach		2 000
1.3	Fresh Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.) (protected and open-grown lettuce) excluding lettuce listed in point 1.4	Harvested 1 October to 31 March: lettuce grown under cover	5 000
		lettuce grown in the open air	4 000
1.4	"Iceberg" type lettuce	Harvested 1 April to 30 September: lettuce grown under cover	4 000
		lettuce grown in the open air	3 000
1.5	Rucola (<i>Eruca sativa</i> , <i>Diplotaxis</i> sp., <i>Brassica tenuifolia</i> , <i>Sisymbrium tenuifolium</i>)	Harvested 1 October to 31 March:	7 000
		Harvested 1 April to 30 September:	6 000
1.6	Processed cereal-based foods and baby foods for infants and young children ⁽³⁾ ⁽⁴⁾		200'

NOTE mg/kg equivalent to ppm.

There is a vast literature dealing with the danger of ingesting a too high amount of NO_3^- with the diet. The danger mainly relies on the fate of the NO_3^- ion (not toxic on itself) in our body. Nitrate is converted to nitrite that can combine with amines and amides to form N-nitrose compounds. Nitrite itself can determine an acute effect combining with hemoglobin to form the methemoglobin; this can be a real problem in infants. N-nitrose compounds are carcinogenic in mammals (potential target organs: stomach, pancreas and brain). Fortunately, formation of N-nitrose compounds can be limited by Vitamin C and other plant antioxidants; hence, the presence of known positive quality related molecules in vegetables can also reduce the health risk of nitrate intake.

The EU agency EFSA (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it>) analyzed the risk of nitrate intake and produced a specific opinion document (EFSA 2008). As a follow-up the EU Commission imposed legal limits (Table A3. 2) to the presence of NO_3^- in various types of vegetables for health safety reasons. (CE 2011).

More recently, an increasing body of evidence pointed to NO_2^- and NO as positive metabolites for

humans. In particular, it is accepted that they can reduce blood pressure and increase muscle efficiency (Bailey et al 2010). Since NO_2^- and NO are a byproduct of NO_3^- intake, the use of high nitrate containing food was suggested as food supplement *e.g.* as a way to contrast salt induced high blood pressure, and high nitrate products are considered food supplement to sustain muscles exercise (Kurtz et al. 2018).

Potentially bad and good effects have then to be both considered and balanced while assuming nitrate rich foods. The Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) in its most recent review in 2002 reconfirmed an Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 0-3.7 mg/kg b.w. for nitrate and set an ADI of 0-0.07 mg/kg b.w. for nitrite (FAO/WHO, 2003a, b). EFSA accepted this ADI in its Opinion (EFSA 2008) (Table A3. 3). It should be recalled that other alimentary sources of nitrate are water and cured meat that can contribute on average with 35-44 mg/person per day (EFSA 2008). This provides reference values to consider while assessing the consumption quantities of nitrate rich vegetables.

TABLE A3. 3. From: EFSA 2008 The EFSA Journal, 689, 1-79.

Table 18. Summary of the NOELs from toxicological studies used to derive ADI values for nitrate and nitrite in the latest the JECFA (FAO/WHO, 2003a,b) evaluation.

Type of study	Toxicological Endpoint	NOEL ¹⁷ sodium salt/anion mg/kg b.w./day	ADI sodium salt/anion mg/kg b.w./day	Reference
Nitrate				
Subchronic study in dogs (125 days)	Growth depression	500/370	5.0/3.7	Lehman, 1958 cited in JECFA 1962
2 year chronic study in rats	Growth depression	500/370	5.0/3.7	Lehman, 1958 cited in JECFA 1962; Lijinski, 1973
Nitrite				
2 years study in rats	Heart and lung toxicity	10/6.7	0.1/0.07	Maekawa <i>et al.</i> , 1982

^{a)} mg/kg body weight per day

ii) practical indications on how to avoid misleading measurements due to sample heterogeneity

Sub-sampling with heterogeneous material and extraction procedures

One single leaf of lettuce (or even a small cherry tomato) can be heavier than the requested amount of a sub sample. The procedure for NO_3^- measurement requires extracting 1g of fresh material. In a bunch of lettuce there is a population of leaves, the external ones are the older, the thicker, the more active in transpiration and photosynthesis, the most coloured (in terms of both chlorophyll and anthocyanins) the most active source organs, and also the richer in NO_3^- . The young internal ones are sink organs, they are pale yellow, do not have chlorophyll, do not perform photosynthesis and survive on resources, even sugars, provided by the more active leaves of the

same bunch, and have low content of NO_3^- . The composition of the two types of leaves can be dramatically different and cause a large variability among samples and sub-samples if they are not corrected subsampled.

In this case, final sub-sample should be generated with extra subsampling steps.

- a) Detach all leaves from stem (not necessary in case of spread harvest)
- b) Distribute your lettuce leaves population as a thin layer on a flat surface
- c) Pick, randomly, small amounts of lettuce from 4-5 different positions on the distributed lettuce bed and make a first sub sample (Subsample1) large enough to be representative of the total produce.
- d) Check visually that the appearance of the Subsample1 is similar to that of the total produce *e.g.* all leaves type are equally represented in Subsample1.
- e) Use a knife to chop leaves of the Subsample 1 to pieces sufficiently small to be several times smaller than the size of the final sub sample you require
- f) Distribute your chopped Subsample1 as a thin layer on a flat surface
- g) Pick, randomly, small amounts (4-5 “pick” should be sufficient to have a homogenous subsample) of the chopped Subsample1 to reach the final expected weight of your final subsample.
- h) Repeat point g for each of the required subsamples.

Notes:

- 1) **A MINIMUM OF 4 REPLICATE MESUREMENTS ARE NECESSARY TO OBTAIN A GOOD ESTIMATE OF THE NITRATE CONTENT OF EACH LOT OF PRODUCE;**
- 2) the subsample 1 would be probably unusable for consume, so be careful to collect sufficient but not too large amount;
- 1) After chopping tissue metabolism will be disrupted, so depending on the reason why you are subsampling, consider this aspect while proceeding. Be quick is always a good suggestion.

Extraction procedures.

Extraction has the scope to solubilize NO_3^- from the plant tissue into water. NO_3^- is readily soluble in water, so the problem is to allow that it escapes from the vacuole (the cellular compartments where it is partitioned in living cells) and mix with extraction water. The vacuole is surrounded by a single layer membrane, which is easily broken upon cell freezing.

Freezing the sample prior of grinding would help extraction.

Grinding the sample would speed up extraction, for this, pestle and mortar are perfect. Try to grind with no or limited water first and add volumes of water in steps to add the final volume into the mortar. Grind thoroughly, at least for 2-3 minutes each sample. If you grind vigorously, the sample to homogeneity there is no need to wait minutes after the extraction prior to measurement. Collect part of the sample using a plastic pipette into an Eppendorf tube (1.5 ml volume) wait one or two minutes to let debris to settle and proceed with measurement.

If you add 1g of sample to 5 ml of water, you dilute the NO_3^- in the sample by a factor of 6 (assuming that 1g of sample adds almost 1 g of water is an acceptable approximation).

Just I don't know if the instrument makes calculation automatically or not.

We assume that the instrument you have provides you the Nitrate concentration in ppm in the solution you generated by extracting the sample, and that no further calculations are done by the instruments itself.

Remember that measurements should be in the range limited by the calibration procedure. If your reading is too high (unlikely) just dilute your extracted sample (use Gilson type pipettes) or just extract it in more water.

iii) a practical tool to calculate the nitrate content in measured samples;

The file "NITRATE concentration and ADI calculator AB 23-03-2018.xls" allows you to calculate the Nitrate concentration in the produce using the measuring values.

It also allows you to calculate the amount of a specific produce that a crewmember can eat without exceeding the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of Nitrate, assuming that a fixed amount of Nitrate is taken up from other sources (drinking water, cured meat) and considering the specific body weight of each crewmember.

iv) suggestions on how to deal with produce that shows very high nitrate content;

If the produce of the MTF were intended for the market, species listed in Table A3. 2 that would exceed the maximum allowed concentration of nitrate could not be commercialized.

In pre-mission studies, Rocket produced at IBAF and WUR premises did not exceed the legal limits. However, red mustard produces at WUR showed an estimated nitrate concentration far higher than the maximum allowed for salad and Rocket. The content was estimated because samples were delivered dry from WUR to IBAF and the water content at harvest was not measured. Hence, we could measure nitrate content on a dry weight basis and could only estimate (with 10% error approximately) the nitrate content on a fresh weight basis. Preliminary data produced of nitrate content on Red Mustard produced in FEG during the mission confirmed our preliminary estimates. Red Mustard might have more than a 10000-ppm nitrate on a fresh weight basis.

As discussed previously, some authors contrast the view of nitrate being dangerous and instead suggest consuming functional food with high nitrate content. Furthermore, the ADI for nitrate was derived from studies on rat and dog assuming an uncertainty factor of 100. That means that the ADI is 100 times lower than the concentration of Nitrate that caused damage to studied animals. Hence exceeding the ADI to a limited extent should be safe.

Suggestions:

- a) check the nitrate concentration on all lot of produce
- b) calculate the ADI using the provided spreadsheet calculator
- c) consume an amount of produce close to ADI on a daily base
- d) consider the cumulative effect of eating more than one product on a daily base
- e) store exceeding product for consume on different days
- f) boil in large amount of water, 10 l of water/1 kg of produce should dilute 10 times nitrate.

References A3

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1.12 Addendum 4: Nitrate calculation spread sheet

A spreadsheet was produced that allows

- A) the calculation of the nitrate content in 4 replicate samples and the average nitrate content of produce harvested during the Mission using i) the nitrate measurement taken, ii) the amount of sample used and iii) the dilution caused by the extraction.

Type of produce	Data of Harvest	Replicates	Fw of sample used (g)	Volume of water used for the extraction (ml)	Reading (ppm)	Total Extracion volume (ml- assuming the weight of fw is equivalent a volume of water)	NO3- (ppm)	NO3- (mg/100 g fw)
Eruca Sativa	dd/mm/2018	1	1	5	300	6	1800	180
	dd/mm/2018	2	1,2	5	340	6,2	1757	176
	dd/mm/2018	3	0,98	5	280	5,98	1709	171
	dd/mm/2018	4	1,1	5	315	6,1	1747	175
	AVERAGE							1753
Brassica juncea	dd1/mm1/2018	1	1	5	1800	6	10800	1080
	dd1/mm1/2018	2	1,2	5	1950	6,2	10075	1008
	dd1/mm1/2018	3	0,98	5	1780	5,98	10862	1086
	dd1/mm1/2018	4	1,1	5	1820	6,1	10093	1009
	AVERAGE							10457
Lactuca sativa	dd2/mm/2018	1	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd2/mm/2018	2	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd2/mm/2018	3	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd2/mm/2018	4	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	AVERAGE							#DIV/0!
New specie	dd1/mm2/2018	1	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd1/mm2/2018	2	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd1/mm2/2018	3	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	dd1/mm2/2018	4	0	0	0	0	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!
	AVERAGE							#DIV/0!

add as needed

NOTE: this sheet allow you to calculate the NO3- concentration in each produce using measurement data. Two forms of results are produced. In the first, the nitrate concentration is expressed as ppm on the fresh product which is equivalent to mg kg fw-1. In the second is expressed as mg 10 g fw, which is equal to pp/10. The value of the nitrate concentration in pp is used by the specie related sheets for the calculation of the ADI (Acceptable Daily Intake)

B) The calculation of the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) for each member of the crew, for each

Type of produce	Data of Harvest	Crew Member	Body weight (kg)	Personal NO3- ADI (Acceptable Daily Intake mg day-1)	Personal Estimated daily consume from other sources (mg day-1)	Personal Produce Allowed NO3- ADI (mg day-1)	NO3- ppm on fresh weight -	Personal estimate maximum produce consume to reach the NO3- ADI (g fw)
Eruca Sativa	23/03/2018	Paul Zabel	95	351,5	35	316,5	1753	181
		2	50	185	35	150	1753	86
		3	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		4	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		5	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		6	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		7	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		8	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		9	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		10	60	222	35	187	1753	107
		11	60	222	35	187	1753	107
Total Consume (g day-1)								1226

	Input crew member body weight
	Calculated values
	Fixed estimated value
	Value of NO3- concentration obtained by the Nitrate calculator

NOTE: this allows you to calculate the amount of a specific product that can be eaten by each of the crewmembers to reach the ADI, based on the measured concentration of Nitrate on the product.
 The nitrate concentration of the produce is automatically transferred from the nitrate calculator. To add a new box for a second harvest of the same specie you can copy and paste the entire box on the right side of the present one. In this case, you must link the H4 cell to the appropriate cell of the calculator
 To calculate ADI for a new specie (product) copy and paste the entire box in a new sheet and link the calculated value of Nitrate in the Nitrate Calculator sheet to the new H4 cell. See example in the third sheet.

of the measured produce.